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CONTENTS

SOCIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- Monitoring in the local government control system
Rychikhina Elina Nikolaevna, Romanova Elena Vladimirovna 7
- Effective PR strategies for surviving “cancel culture”
Shchukina Anastasia Alekseevna, Todis Larisa Mikhailovna 13
- The axiological prism of the postwar period in the example of the Republic of Azerbaijan
Zumrud Novruzali Huseynova 18

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- The picture of the world of AIDS-respondents
Barysheva Elena Ivanovna 24
- Text versus voice modality in cognitive behavioral therapy digital diaries: a study protocol comparing perceived empathy, engagement, and usage frequency
Alekhin Aleksei Victorovich 33
- The psychological relationship between adolescents’ self-concept and suicidal tendencies
Primantayeva Gulnaz Umirserikovna 44
- The interrelationship of cognitive processes and psychological well-being in primary school children
Baidina Daria Ivanovna 51

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

- The potential of the legacy of the classics of Russian pedagogy in modeling the content of the socio-informational competence of future preschool education teachers
Chebotareva Irina Vladimirovna, Demenkov Ilya Alexandrovich 55
- On the issue of discursive space in the process of learning a foreign language
Andreeva Svetlana Mikhailovna 61
- From theory to practice: game technologies in robotics education using the example of all-russian children’s center “ORLYONOK”»
Putrenok Ekaterina Leonidovna 68

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

Restoration of statehood of the repressed peoples <i>Akkieva Svetlana Ismailovna</i>	76
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ART HISTORY

Poetry of Russian modern style and music <i>Gladkova Olga Igorevna</i>	84
Public art in the digital era: interactivity, placemaking, and the construction of social identity <i>Huderichaolu</i>	93
Baikal is so different in the visual arts <i>Gorbonos Olga Konstantinovna</i>	96
Angles of Victoria Pitirimova's reality. On the issue of the formation of the author's visual vocabulary <i>Shipitsyna Elena Akramovna</i>	103

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Approaches to designing online training for future journalists in the form of practice-oriented courses <i>Doroschuk Elena Sergeevna</i>	110
Marshak's translation heritage (from English classical poetry) <i>Autleva Fatima Askarbievna, Simbutetova Rima Kazbekovna, Hachetsukova Zarema Kushukovna</i>	118
The color continuum of I.S. Turgenev's "Sketches from a hunter's album" cycle <i>Ivanova Elena Stanislavovna</i>	122
The Post-Apocalyptic Genre in Vladimir Sorokin's Prose <i>Cheremina Ekaterina Arkadievna</i>	131
Methods of rendering English vowel sounds in writing <i>Shilikov Sergei Ivanovich, Sozonov Mikhail Alekseevich</i>	138

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

About the Russianness of Russian Music <i>Klujev Aleksandr Sergeevich</i>	146
Categories as an invariant basis of thinking <i>Chernyakova Natalia Stepanovna</i>	153
The development of a person's worldview. The role of a tutor in modern education <i>Shipovskaya Lyudmila Pavlovna</i>	158

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MONITORING IN THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT CONTROL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the capabilities and structure of the social control mechanism within local self-government bodies, and examines the influence of the structural model of local self-government bodies on the organization of social control based on management monitoring. It is proposed to establish a control system on a monitoring basis and to conduct an assessment of the effectiveness of local self-government bodies, taking into account the population's opinion, as determined through sociological surveys based on regular observations.*

Keywords: *Local self-government, social control, functions of social control, monitoring, social mechanism, digital environment.*

The development of local self-government represents a significant factor in the overall development of society, as evidenced both by the attention from government authorities and the establishment of legislative norms regulating its activities at the federal and regional levels. The search for new forms of management at the municipal level leads to the emergence of new mechanisms, including an increased use of project management methods, which, in turn, demand new approaches to the organization and execution of social control. Social control functions as a specific self-regulation mechanism intended to reinforce order and preserve stability at the municipal level. It is precisely these circumstances that enable the identification of the key reasons for addressing the stated topic:

— Social control serves as a foundation for the stable development of local self-government;

— The effectiveness of social control largely determines the efficiency of local self-government;

— The interaction of local self-government bodies with the population constitutes an important component of society's influence on municipal governance.

Both foreign and domestic researchers have addressed the issue of social control. One of the first to address the issue of social control was É. Durkheim [4]. Contributions to the development of this issue were made by T. Parsons [13], I. Prigogine, I. Stengers [15], and many other foreign authors. General approaches to social control have been studied by such domestic authors as G. I. Kozyrev [7], M. Yu. Kravtsov [8], and others.

Significant attention to the issue of local self-government by domestic researchers has been observed since the beginning of the 21st century, following the adoption of the Federal Law 'On the General Principles of Organization of Local Self-Government in the Russian Federation' [1]. The growing interest in the issue of local self-government is evidenced by the adoption in 2025 of the new Federal Law 'On the General Principles of the Organization of Local Self-Government in a Unified System of Public Authority,' which will come into effect in 2027. These circumstances highlight the significant role of local self-government and the necessity for its enhancement amid contemporary transformations. Among the researchers examining the issue of local self-government are political scientists, lawyers, sociologists, and economists, including the works of V. G. Ledyeva [9], E. G. Kovalenko, and T. S. Korchagina [6], R. V. Petukhova [14] and other authors. Special attention is paid by contemporary researchers to the issues of digital support for local self-government bodies. Among the authors who have addressed these issues in recent years, A. S. Anushyan [2], L. A. Vasilenko and V. V. Zotov [3], S. A. Melkov and A. S. Sushansky [10], A. S. Nikitin [11], and others.

The study relies on the foundations of a systemic approach, employing both general scientific dialectical methods — such as analysis, synthesis, induction, analogy, generalization, and modeling — and specialized methods, including surveys and the analysis of secondary empirical research conducted by VCIOM.

The extensive use of the concept of 'social control' in academic literature and practice prevents the establishment of a unified approach to its content with respect to local self-government. From the author's perspective, social control in local self-government is understood as a mechanism within the local self-government system aimed at identifying deviations in its development and determining sanctions to eliminate the detected deficiencies and problems. At the same time, the historically established system of formal control in contemporary conditions requires improvement, considering the current digital era context.

Social control performs various functions, among which the central ones are diagnostic, accounting, managerial, educational, formative, orienting, and stimulating. At the same time, the organization of control based on management monitoring serves as a crucial factor in the effective resolution of management issues,

as substantiated by E. N. Rychikhina, who regards monitoring as a general function of management [16].

Analyzing the system of local self-government, it should be noted that, for the realization of citizens' interests, it is necessary, on the one hand, to involve residents in its development and, on the other hand, to possess information regarding the existing problems of municipal territories. This foundation establishes the necessity for regular collection of indicators and metrics within the local self-government system, necessitating a monitoring approach to control. Figure 1 illustrates the components of the social mechanism for establishing local government monitoring, comprising six principal areas that enable the integration of all collected information into a cohesive whole. The authors conceptualize the social mechanism of forming the management monitoring system as a systemic interaction among subsystems and elements of the municipal entity, state, and regional authorities, grounded in an established system of norms and social institutions engaged in the creation, implementation, and dissemination of monitoring data.

Fig. 1 — Components of the mechanism for establishing monitoring of social control in local self-government.

To assess the effectiveness of local self-government functioning, the following key indicators are identified for the formation of a social management mechanism, which should be emphasized during the social control process:

1. Compliance with the social order and the socio-economic needs of the municipal entity.

2. Stability, understood as the consistency of management activity results over time.

3. Competence of management entities in understanding the essence and significance of the collected indicators and metrics.

4. Accounting for the integrativity of all components of local self-government.

When examining the structure of local self-government of the urban district of Fryazino in the Moscow Region, as presented in Figure 2, it is essential to emphasize the necessity of interaction both within the management system itself, among the five components of this system, and with other governance elements at the regional and federal levels.

Fig. 2 — Structure of the local self-government bodies of the urban district of Fryazino.

However, the primary source of social control through monitoring remains the population, whose engagement is facilitated through citizens' meetings and conferences, referendums, public hearings, citizen-initiated legislative initiatives, participation in surveys, and other forms. Based on management monitoring, it is necessary to develop a system of surveys for the population to identify changes in opinions and the dynamics of evaluating the performance of local self-government bodies [5].

A crucial component of monitoring should be the dissemination of information to the public. According to VCIOM research data, the primary sources of

information regarding the activities of local self-government are television (42%) and the Internet (over 30%) [12]. This circumstance necessitates enhancing interaction within the digital environment, fostering convenient communication among all interested parties. Expanding interaction opportunities in the digital environment will facilitate the involvement of citizens across different age groups in the local self-government system. Practical sociological research provides an instrumental foundation for diagnosing issues in local self-government, constituting an essential component of feedback with the population, facilitating the identification of urgent problems faced by the local community, and enabling the development of effective solutions.

Thus, the analysis of the current situation indicates that the improvement of local self-government is currently being prioritized, with social control — rooted in the principles of managerial monitoring — serving as a crucial element. An integral component of this monitoring should be a system of sociological surveys, enabling the acquisition of significant information for the formulation and adoption of management decisions within the local self-government system.

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EFFECTIVE PR STRATEGIES FOR SURVIVING “CANCEL CULTURE”

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Abstract. *The article is dedicated to the issue of “cancel culture” that threaten someone’s or an organization’s reputation in today’s digital environment. The article analyzes effective and ineffective public relations strategies for overcoming such crises. It focuses on two examples from Russia: the “Pims” coffee shops chain, which failed to improve its image, and media figure Regina Todorenko, who successfully managed to restore her reputation through significant personal transformation. Based on this analysis, the article suggests some useful strategies for PR professionals. The results emphasize that success depends on taking real responsibility, visible personal or institutional changes, and a well-thought-out plan for long-term social commitment.*

Keywords: *“cancellation culture”, PR strategies, anti-crisis management, reputation, apologies, “Pims”, Regina Todorenko, image restoration.*

Introduction

The concept of “cancel culture” refers to a contemporary social and cultural phenomenon in which a public figure or brand faces widespread public condemnation and exclusion in the digital world due to actions or statements considered unacceptable by the general public [1]. This phenomenon can be traced back to practices within marginalized communities, particularly African American communities, where the term “cancel” was used to refer to the termination of support for those who violated group norms. Nevertheless, within global media, cancel culture rose more within the end of the 2010s as a reaction towards #MeToo and other social

justice movements within cyber society. At first, it was seen as a way for voices to hold powerful individuals accountable, but it has since evolved to encompass a wider range of targets, often leading to controversial applications [2,3]. Within the prism of Russian media, there is a phenomenon that passed a period and stage of transition and today represents as a reputational risk. As an obstacle within crisis communications for various professionals and practitioners within public relationships, it induces an amplification and perpetuation within society about an act contrary to trust and loyalty. As it affects images created within society and cyber society as well, it moves and proceeds beyond an immediate decrease within support [4]. To appropriately practice coping and responding within developments and changes today, it requires precision and strategy within responding and coping.

This article will provide two contrasting examples from the practice of combating the “cancel culture” and examine them from a theoretical perspective, so as to formulate universal rules on how crises emerging as a result of public criticism should be managed.

Let us move to theoretical considerations within the concept ‘cancellation culture’ and methods of response to crises. The phenomenon of “cancel culture” has its roots in the digital media culture, wherein there are no distinctions between the personal and public realms and communications proceed at a very swift rate, making it possible for a large number of people to be mobilized instantly. It has been pointed out that cancel culture usually responds to instances of hypocrisy, violation of values, and value conflicts, sometimes on the part of people who are seen as socially aware and morally superior [3]. The psychological roots of cancel culture lie in the need for society to achieve social justice through collective action — a boycott.

To oppose the phenomenon of “cancel culture,” crisis communication strategies have evolved. Instead of relying solely on traditional tactics like outright denial, simple acknowledgment, or a perfunctory apology, companies are now adopting more holistic and integrated methods. Recent research highlights several key approaches [1,8]:

1. **Swift and Tailored Accountability:** A slow or generic corporate reaction to a crisis can worsen the situation.

2. **Action-Backed Commitments:** Apologies that are not supported by tangible actions, such as financial contributions or public service projects, erode public trust.

3. **Transformative Repositioning:** A crisis can be viewed as a chance for a fresh start, allowing for a revamped communication strategy that aligns with the values addressing the criticisms received.

4. **Sustained Dedication:** Building and maintaining trust is a continuous, long-term endeavor that necessitates consistent demonstrations of reliability and systemic adjustments.

Let's now examine two specific cases that exemplify situations involving "cancel culture." The problem with "Pims" coffee-shops chain emerged due to an advertising campaign that came off as unethical and trivializing social issues. The reaction of the company can be considered ineffective because it was delayed and the apologies were general and unpersonalized. The main issue with "Pims" advertising strategy was that it failed to be specific with their reaction. They failed to address the issue, failed to show that they understood what they had done wrong, and failed to make any serious statements regarding the actions they might undertake (for example, they have revised their creative standards or become partners with non-profit organizations) [5]. It merely emerged as a defense mechanism, which made the matters worse. Consequently, reputational harm ensued as a result of this, and thus, the scandal cemented its link with unethical marketing practices within society. As a warning signal, it highlights how taking matters formally within the current "cancel culture" will end up with the opposite reaction — enhancing negativity.

The second case is connected with Regina Todorenko, a media personality and TV host. After her words were perceived as downplaying domestic violence, criticism and accusations followed. Regina Todorenko distinguished herself by her courageous and thorough investigation of the issue prior to offering an apology [6]. She readily accepted responsibility without attempting to deflect blame. Her reaction transcended a simple verbal acknowledgment, evolving into a comprehensive and socially conscious initiative. Collaborating with other experts, Todorenko contributed to a documentary exploring violence against women and domestic abuse within Russia. This endeavor represented a profound shift for Todorenko, transforming her from a figure subject to criticism into a key participant in a vital societal conversation. Consequently, her public perception evolved from one associated with entertainment to one focused on critical social matters. Her persistent dedication to this subject, encompassing both the film and continuous public engagement, has not only mitigated the effects of past criticism but also bolstered her reputation on a fresh, more mature, and socially accountable foundation [7].

Practical recommendations for PR specialists

Based on the analysis of theoretical frameworks and the presented cases, practical measures can be developed for reputation management in a "culture of cancelation".

1. **Swift and genuine response.** The initial reaction should be immediate. An apology from the CEO or the individual herself should be issued, clearly explaining the nature of the mistake and demonstrating empathy for the public's emotions.

2. **Emphasizing substantive actions.** Verbal communication should be followed up by tangible actions. Public demands for change require more than just

words. This could take the form of financial compensation, institutional reforms, or, as in Todorenko's case, a significant social project addressing the controversy.

3. **Altering the approach.** The current situation should be seen as an opportunity for a fresh start. Communication should focus on new positive values that address the root causes of the issue, replacing old, negative narratives.

4. **Long-term Consistency.** Rebuilding reputation is a marathon, not a sprint. After the initial step, consistent efforts are required to demonstrate new behavioral patterns or a social mission in order to regain trust.

Overcoming the challenges caused by the “cancel culture” requires public relations (PR) professionals to go beyond short public statements and adopt a more strategic approach [8]. A successful strategy must be comprehensive, genuine, and action-oriented. The “Pims” incident can be considered a caution lesson, illustrating the disastrous outcomes of an inactive and formal approach, where the apologies are hollow, and there are no follow-up actions. On the other hand, the success of Regina Todorenko, shows the effectiveness of a model that embraces full personal responsibility and is followed by an extensive and meaningful transformation of the situation perception. Thus, it should be mentioned that in the current digital world, the ones who say “I’m sorry” may not be forgiven. Instead, the forgiveness is granted to those who show understanding, depth of remorse, and a readiness to make significant and measurable changes over time. Concluding this article, cancel culture can be a daunting challenge for any brand, but it also presents an opportunity for introspection, growth, and engagement with your audience on a deeper level.

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THE AXIOLOGICAL PRISM OF THE POSTWAR PERIOD IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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SUMMARY

The reconstruction policy in the postconflict phase aims to be implemented through the reintegration of the liberated territories and their integration into the value chain as part of the overall development strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In accordance with the principles of the Fourth Industrial Revolution the liberated territories will be developed by implementing mega projects taking into account local resources and prospects. All relevant executive bodies of the country have been mobilized to realize the “Great Return” to our liberated lands. They have discussed various projects to implement the “Great Return” process. The most ambitious and sustainable of these were the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects.

Keywords: Republic of Azerbaijan, social, postwar, smart city, smart village.

Methods: Comparative method, analysis, retrospective and historical analysis, forecasting.

The goal: is to examine the effects of the reconstruction policy implemented and ongoing in the postconflict phase of the Republic of Azerbaijan after the Second Garabakh War which has left its mark on our country in a short time. The importance of Garabakh’s development strategy in this direction should also be emphasized. The implementation of a number of mega projects is targeted in the strategic phase covering 2021–2030. The most ambitious of these are the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects. It is noted what impact and results these projects will achieve in our country. The cases of expansion of the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects are analyzed.

Scientific innovation: A detailed analysis of the reconstruction strategies of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the postconflict phase, ways to properly implement a sustainable strategy without facing greater problems than other underdeveloped countries that have passed the postconflict phase, were explained. The integrated activities of specific areas that should be taken into account in the implementation of the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects were noted.

INTRODUCTION

The Azerbaijani army ensured the territorial integrity of the eternal and eternal lands of our country with the 44-day Victory March. This Victory was won thanks to the determination of President Ilham Aliyev, the blood of our martyrs and the solidarity of our people and nation. This victory did not only bring us victory. It also opened up new horizons for us. This was an impetus for our state to be recognized in the international arena by instilling truths, as well as for our progressive development within the state. After the war, Mr. President Ilham Aliyev laid the foundation for the reconstruction work related to the postconflict stage. At this stage it was planned to implement the development of the occupied territories of Azerbaijan, reconstruction, construction and humanitarian activities with the involvement of international development partners and investors, cooperation between the state and the private sector, the return of internal opportunities, the resettlement of internally displaced persons to their homelands and the development of social capital by applying an approach to the implementation of special state programs.

Postwar stage in Azerbaijan

The reconstruction policy in the postconflict phase aims to be implemented through the reintegration of the liberated territories and their integration into the value chain as part of the overall development strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In accordance with the principles of the Fourth Industrial Revolution the liberated territories will be developed by implementing mega projects taking into account local resources and prospects. Currently, the most important and focused strategy related to the overall development strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the development strategy of Garabakh. This strategy covers short, medium and long-term activities at the local, regional, national and international levels. The main goal of reconstruction strategies in the postconflict phase is to achieve sustainable economic growth and human development. The implementation of reconstruction strategies in the postconflict phase is not only being implemented in our country. When looking at world experience countries such as Iraq, Afghanistan, Kosovo and Croatia are clear examples of this study. The reason for the economic revival of those countries that have passed the postconflict phase is that countries in the postconflict phase face greater problems than countries that have not been stably developed. There are several reasons for this:

1. First of all, the internal human capital that covers the population of the postconflict zone should be assessed.

2. Actors ensuring economic development in these countries should not passively wait for funding from foreign investors. On the contrary they can create added value themselves by showing hard work, strong determination to fight and innovation. If development strategies are based on social dynamics and full awareness

of institutional processes this process will be more sustainable. A management, monitoring and financing mechanism should be created to ensure the implementation of the Garabakh development strategy. Currently, in the liberated territories decontamination including construction and improvement works have been launched in accordance with the new master plans of cities, settlements and villages. This is aimed at developing infrastructure in two different directions:

1. Economic infrastructure

Creation, restoration and development of economic infrastructure in the territory, including roads, land reclamation and irrigation systems, electricity, gas, water supply, sewage, etc. systems

2. Social infrastructure

Development of social infrastructure including education and healthcare. In the liberated territories ensuring the full functioning of state and municipal bodies, development of competitive sectors of the economy and employment including self-employment should be a priority. The gradual return of internally displaced persons to their places of residence taking into account economic and social issues, development of human capital, attraction of foreign and local investments along with the state and support for economic development are also among the priorities. In the liberated territories there is a potential to develop such sectors as mining, metallurgy, food industry, processing industry, tourism and recreation, creative industry, pharmaceuticals, grain growing, vegetable growing, viticulture, cotton growing, fruit growing, livestock breeding, poultry farming, beekeeping, and production of construction materials. Investments in these sectors are of great importance both in terms of increasing non-oil exports and import substitution, and joining value chains. In general the mega projects prepared and launched for Garabakh create the basis for its becoming a new geographical development center in Azerbaijan. As a result of investment in this region and the implementation of reconstruction works, gross domestic product growth in Azerbaijan is projected to accelerate.

“Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects

In the postconflict stage the names of “Smart City” and “Smart Village” are frequently used in our country. I would like to note that recently there has been rapid development in the world, especially in science and technology. This situation has spread to our lives. Generally speaking, our life has already taken the form of “Smart life”. Therefore, innovations in science and technology are now being taken into account in the implementation of state policy. Smart life is often described as a unity of artificial intelligence and natural beauty. This harmony stems from development. Development and innovation depend on new initiatives. The most important of these is the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” project. It plays the role of a kind of nervous system of the country. The Republic of Azerbaijan has always

supported progressive development and has signed new projects taking into account the assessment of prospects. The most ambitious of these projects are, of course, the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects which are intended to be established in the lands liberated after the Second Garabakh War. In world experience, several world countries such as Singapore and Helsinki have already gained the status of “Smart City”. “The idea of “smart villages” in the world is not new and exists in several countries. For example, in Turkiye there is the “Smart Village” project with the support of “Vodafone”. In Kazakhstan there is the “Village Kazakhstan” project, in Rwanda there is the “Smart Village” project and in Ukraine there is the “Autonomous Smart Village” project”¹.

The implementation of these projects planned to be established in our country is based on and benefits from the experiences of the above-mentioned projects which have been confirmed in world experience. “On the other hand, according to the results of the UN research conducted in 2016, 54 percent of the world’s population lives in cities. It is predicted that 60 percent of the world’s population will live in modern cities by 2030 and 70 percent by 2050”². The reason for this is the creation of urban models equipped with highly developed information and communication technologies. The current state policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan is based on promoting our state in the world arena and confirming its innovativeness. The Garabakh region will open up great opportunities in the implementation of this policy. The application of innovative technologies will be more effective in these areas. Because in the areas where the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects, the indicators of which were determined by the UN in 2015 are implemented, innovative work is being carried out covering almost all societal systems of society. The “Smart City” which is considered an innovative city using information technologies in turn stimulates people’s life activities and living standards in a positive direction. For example, it creates conditions for improving the standard of living, making services more efficient and meeting the economic, social and cultural demands of citizens. Within the framework of this project it is planned to build a “Smart City” or “Smart Village” project not only in Garabakh, but also in every inch of Azerbaijani lands. All relevant executive bodies of the country have mobilized to realize the “Great Return” to our lands liberated from occupation. They have discussed various projects to implement the “Great Return” process. The most ambitious

¹ «Ağillı kənd» - ölkəmiz üçün yeni təcrübə - ARAŞDIRMA <https://hafta.az/-agilli-kend-olkemiz-ucun-yeni-tecrube-arasdirma-%C2%A0-296939-xeber.html> 18.02.2021, 12:32

² İşğaldan azad edilmiş ərazilərdə “ağillı şəhər”, “ağillı kənd” layihələrinin təbiiqi əhalinin rifahının yüksəldilməsinə hesablanıb https://azertag.az/xeber/Isgaldan_azad_edilmis_erazilerde_agilli_seher_agilli_kend_layihelerinin_tetbiqi_etalinin_rifahinin_yukseldilmesine_hesablanib-1784491 19.05.2021, 20:07

and sustainable of these was the “Smart City and Smart Village” project. The main idea of the “smart city” and “Smart Village” projects is to combine and manage all services and facilities in a single system. As a result, “citizens will be provided with an easier and safer life and social and economic quality will improve”¹. Currently, this project is in the attention of the local and world community. Because it is also part of the “Great Return” process.

CONCLUSION

Reconstruction works have been launched in the Republic of Azerbaijan in a ten year phase covering the years 2021–2030. The plan to implement the “Great Return” in the territories liberated from occupation successfully continues. The repair, restoration and reconstruction works carried out in the Garabakh region lay the foundation for it to become a new geographical development center in Azerbaijan in a short time. Since the basis of our state policy is to have progressive development covering all areas of the social system and to ensure a standard of living in society that meets international standards, the implementation of the “Smart City” and “Smart Village” projects will be successful. The initial stage of these projects has already been implemented as planned.

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¹ “Ağillı şəhər”, “ağillı kənd” layihələrinin tətbiqi Qarabağ regionunun inkişafında mühüm rol oynayacaq. <https://science.gov.az/az/news/open/17052> 02.06.2021, 09:52

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THE PICTURE OF THE WORLD OF AIDS-RESPONDENTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to studying the characteristics of the worldview of HIV/AIDS-infected individuals, specifically their attitudes toward the world, themselves, and others. The article presents the results of an empirical study on the attitudes of HIV/AIDS-infected individuals toward themselves and others, as well as the subjects' world feeling at the level of their reflections and impressions that they are aware of and can verbalize.*

Keywords: *HIV/AIDS-infected individuals, worldview, value system, world feeling, attitude toward others, attitude toward oneself, psychological support.*

Problem statement. The worldview of an individual as a phenomenon currently attracts keen interest not only from psychological science, which is entirely natural, but also from other human sciences — philosophy, sociology, anthropology, and others, each examining this issue from its own perspective. The peculiarities of worldviews and self-perceptions are manifested in aspects of self-consciousness, self-knowledge, and knowledge of others; in the understanding of human actions; in reflexive evaluation; in the characteristics of moral consciousness and intellectual development; in the comprehension of various life situations; and in the ability to recognize what is occurring and draw conclusions. The issue of worldview at the present stage of scientific development also arises because contemporary individuals are actively influenced by mass culture in their lives. E. Toffler describes 'clip culture' as a distinctive marker of the contemporary youth worldview in its standardized and simplified form. Fragmented, unsystematized, and sporadic notions and impressions, influenced by mass communication media and modern information systems, create a mosaic worldview where knowledge about the world and oneself is marked by chaotic perception, heterogeneous information, and superficial understanding. All of this influences the formation of a person's way of life and provokes events in their life, often related to their responsibility for what happens around them and to themselves.

Life challenges that a person encounters (whether personal situations, such as illness, or large-scale social crises, such as armed conflicts and the extreme experiences associated with them) significantly affect their self-awareness, attitude toward the world and themselves, toward others, influence the perception and sense of justice as a principle of existence, and shape the distinctiveness of their character. The experience of illness as a crisis situation, the study of the psychology of the sick individual, and the changes in their psyche, behavior, and attitudes toward others, the world, and themselves are associated with the peculiarities of the internal experience of illness as an individual distinctiveness of attitude. The discovery of HIV infection in a person constitutes an acute crisis state.

A person's knowledge of their own HIV-positive status radically alters their world perception, as well as their perception of their own life and fate. The most common reactions are diametrically opposed: from desperately living out the last years of life to the fullest extent possible given one's condition, to existential reflection on the finitude of existence and, perhaps for the first time, the ability to appreciate loved ones, life, its simple pleasures, and attempts to utilize one's abilities. A constant necessity is the need to change one's lifestyle, as the circle of friends, work, and relationships with others often change due to myths surrounding this disease; suspicions and resentments are difficult to cope with.

The issue of HIV/AIDS infection, actively studied in medicine since the 1980s and 1990s, has been less extensively a subject of scientific interest in psychology. However, as experience with this problem accumulated, it became clear that psychological support during the treatment process, the development of an internal representation of the illness, accompanying rehabilitation activities, the implementation of antiretroviral therapy (ART therapy), and ultimately palliative care, are very important and socially significant endeavors.

In medical science, the issue was studied by M. L. Aryaev, E. S. Belozerov, V. V. Belyaeva, Yu. I. Bulankov, T. N. Ermak, V. N. Zaporozhan, V. Kalyadin, Yu. V. Kobysya, V. V. Malyaev, V. I. Pokrovsky, V. V. Pokrovsky, N. A. Semina, A. M. Shcherbinskaya, O. G. Yurin, and others [1; 2; 4; 11].

Representatives of psychological science have made a significant contribution to understanding patients' conditions, their experiences, worldview, and picture of the world; these include S. V. Gorbatov, V. Krueger, B. Luban-Plozza, V. Peldinger, E. P. Purik, and others [6; 7; 8; 9].

Despite the progress made in combating infectious diseases, the incidence rate of HIV remains very high. HIV/AIDS is rapidly spreading across all continents of the world. Before the HIV epidemic, the issue of the social and psychological adaptation of infected individuals was not regarded as particularly important. Currently, there is an understanding that psychological support during this process enables the activation of patients' awareness of the necessity for lifestyle changes,

their adequacy, the social responsibility of individuals for the spread of the disease, and the identification of a significant number of psychological factors associated with this illness. It becomes evident that alongside medical and social issues, it is necessary to study the psychological characteristics of HIV-infected individuals, to understand the content of psychological assistance and support, and to outline the trajectory of socio-psychological rehabilitation work.

The aim of this article is to present our perspective on the peculiarities of the worldview of HIV/AIDS-infected individuals and to examine their attitudes toward the world, themselves, and others.

Theoretical aspects of the problem of studying the worldview of HIV-infected individuals.

The cognition of the surrounding world, reflected and consolidated in human consciousness in the form of knowledge, doctrines, skills, and types of behavior and communication, constitutes the basis for constructing a certain model — the worldview. Throughout the history of human cognition, numerous such perspectives on the world have been developed — worldviews distinguished by their perception of the world and their specific explanations of it. (K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, I. N. Kalinauskas, G. V. Platonov et al.). [5; 10]. V. N. Savchenko, V. P. Smagin, and E. M. Udovichenko, in their research, identify various types of worldviews: sensory-spatial, spiritual-cultural, physical, metaphysical, biological, philosophical, mythological, linguistic, artistic, religious, scientific, materialistic, cosmocentric, and others. [12, p.149]

In our view, the worldview is a complex-to-verbalize construct that is difficult to describe and structure. It is the foundation of world perception, uniting the images and concepts known to a person into a single, integrated picture, where everything a person encounters in life is combined and indirectly reflected, encompassing all that he is capable of comprehending.

A person's perception of the world results from the functioning of self-consciousness, which enables an individual, while exploring the external world, to be aware of himself within it and, consequently, to be able to explore his inner world, experience states, and relate to himself in a particular way.

Referring to the works of scholars E. G. Azimov, A. N. Shchukin, K. Aydukevich, A. Ya. Antsupov, V. S. Bezrukov, Yu. V. Bromley, J. Bruner, V. S. Zhitkov, K. V. Sokolov, V. I. Zorin, T. F. Kuznetsova, S. A. Lebedev, A. I. Panov, V. S. Stepin, E. S. Yakovleva, Wikipedia provides a generalized definition of the worldview in the following formulation: «The worldview is the totality of holistic and systematized representations, knowledge, and opinions of human communities and an individual (subject) about the world and the universe, based on the sense of the world, world perception, world understanding, and

worldview, as well as about cognitive and creative capabilities, the meaning of life, and the place of humans in it». [13].

Each of us, at some point, begins to reflect on how to build our life, what its meaning is, what the purpose of a person is, and how to live our life happily. When a person learns of their HIV-positive status, their world begins to collapse. What was important before then loses its value. Now, the person must look at the world with completely different eyes and undergo the process from rejection, denial, and indignation regarding their status to acceptance of the inevitability and reevaluation of their own life.

Let us present the statistical data. Statistics as of 24.11.2025 indicate that 1,215,000 people in Russia live with an HIV diagnosis (which is 0.83% of the country's population). The majority of people who were first diagnosed with HIV in 2024 were infected through heterosexual contacts — 80.9%, homosexual contacts account for only 3.8%, and 14% through drug use. (For comparison, in Ukraine there is a close link between HIV infection and drug addiction. According to the Ukrainian Center for Prevention and Control of AIDS, 57.8% of all HIV-positive individuals are people who use injectable drugs.) In Russia, children born to HIV-infected mothers account for 0.2% of the total number of infected individuals. Cases in which people become infected due to a medical error, such as an HIV-positive blood transfusion, are very rare. In Russia, an average of only 8 such cases are recorded annually. Until 2019, Russian medical professionals registered approximately 100,000 new cases of HIV infection each year. Since 2020, their number has been decreasing: in 2024, 51,984 new cases were registered, in 2023—58,740, in 2022—63,150, and in 2021—61,098.

Among those diagnosed with HIV in Russia, men predominate, comprising two-thirds of all registered cases. In 2023, approximately 68.9% of individuals diagnosed with HIV were Russians aged 30–49 years. Today, youth aged 15–20 years account for only 0.7% of all diagnoses. For comparison: in 2000, it was 24%. [14]

Research results. The study of the worldview can be conducted through various psychological phenomena. The structure of the worldview includes the respondent's representations of the system of values and meanings, their basic beliefs, attitude toward the World, toward themselves and others, worldview, world feeling, and world perception. Our article specifically addresses the attitude toward oneself, toward HIV/AIDS-infected individuals, and the world feeling of the subjects at the level of their reflections and impressions, which they consciously experience and can verbalize. This reflects the characteristics of self-awareness among HIV-positive respondents and their understanding of coping strategies and methods used in the challenging life situation of a severe illness.

Research sample. The study participants comprised 70 respondents aged 25–35 years (49 men, constituting 70% of the sample, and 21 women, constituting 30%

of the sample), with disease durations ranging from six months to ten years. These respondents were clients of the Trust Offices at the Centers for the Prevention and Control of AIDS in the Luhansk People's Republic. Among the sample participants, 63 % are employed, while 37 % neither study nor work and rely on occasional earnings. The educational level of this sample: secondary education — 22.85 % (16 respondents), secondary specialized education — 67.14 % (47 respondents), higher education — 10 % (7 respondents).

Diagnostic tools: 1) observation; 2) interview; 3) 'Level of Subjective Control' questionnaire (E. F. Bazhin, E. A. Golyunkina, A. M. Etkind); 4) Liry's method of diagnosing interpersonal relations; 5) Basic Beliefs Scale (R. Janoff-Bulman); 6) Quality of Life Assessment Scale (J. Endicott et al., adapted by N. E. Vodopyanova).

Let us describe the data obtained during interviews and conversations held in the course of counseling sessions. The interview aimed to determine the respondents' conscious assessment of their well-being and mood at the present moment regarding their health status, as well as to evaluate the respondents' reflective ability to assess and describe their emotional state, experienced feelings (positive and negative), satisfaction with various areas of their lives, whether they need support and receive it, and how they spend their time and what fills it.

Almost a third of respondents (27.14 %) report their 'normal' mood, which is periodically overshadowed by feelings of anxiety and fear, but only briefly. It should be noted that the very description in terms of 'normal' is extremely formal and vague; it is a general phrase typically used when one does not wish to delve into details, the person does not perceive nuances and subtle differences, and therefore such an assessment of the overall mood — which essentially provides no insight into the respondents' emotional state — rather indicates a lack of self-reflection among respondents.

61.42 % report experiencing depressed mood, noticing obsessive anxious thoughts that are difficult to dispel, and a reduced level of activity. When asked to name their feelings and experiences with specific words and to reflect on their emotional state, 77 % reported anxiety (it is worth noting that even within the normotypical sample, anxiety indicators — both objective according to the methodologies and subjective assessments — are at a fairly high level as a characteristic of this period), while 24 % of respondents reported irritation and aggressiveness; many factors provoke their anger, and they struggle to restrain themselves from engaging in conflicts, or do indeed engage in them. It is evident that anger and tension result from the experience of processing one's diagnosis, how to live with it, reflection upon and evaluation of one's life as a whole and its outcome, and the necessity to take certain steps. An attempt to avenge oneself on the entire world through aggression and irritation toward the surrounding world and people requires meticulous work by the psychologist with such a client, where an important part of

the process is the development of socially acceptable behavior, lifestyle changes, and adherence to ART therapy. A portion of respondents (17%) report experiencing sensitivity and tearfulness; some mention depression (without fully understanding the meaning of the term, but in any case, referring to a severe, depressed mood, lack of motivation for activity or proactive behavior, and an unwillingness to change anything in their lives). 37.14% speak of a fear of death and a sense of hopelessness — a distinct feeling that did not arise immediately upon learning the diagnosis, but appeared after some time, when awareness of the situation and understanding of the illness developed, and when the respondent began to reflect on the future and the inevitable deterioration of their condition. It is precisely these respondents who require special attention from the psychologist, as they are often susceptible to depression and experience suicidal thoughts. Yet, within this category, there is potential to foster motivation for lifestyle changes, reevaluation of life, discovery of its true meanings, engagement in accessible activities, and a drive to ‘manage to do something good’ with the successful implementation of psychological interventions. 27.14% report having developed a desire to build good relationships with their loved ones, resulting from an awareness of life’s finiteness, a need for warm emotional bonds and support, and, perhaps for the first time in their lives, an understanding of the phenomenon known as ‘forgiveness.’ Only 22.85% of respondents report good relationships with close individuals, although they fear possible changes in these relationships due to the discovered diagnosis. More than 40% describe difficult relationships with close ones, characterized by irritation, misunderstanding, reproaches, and lack of restraint, both from the respondent and family members. About 10% do not maintain relationships with relatives at all. However, approximately 63% of respondents require support from close individuals, while about 57% are unwilling to seek help from loved ones in difficult situations and rely on themselves.

The discussion of satisfaction with the quality of life revealed the following results. Only 10% of the sample are satisfied with the overall course of their life: they have family and friends, are employed and satisfied with their position, have a certain level of financial security, and anticipate support from close ones in the difficult situation of discovering a serious illness. The remaining respondents are dissatisfied to varying degrees with different areas of life: one-third report unsatisfactory relationships with close people, more than half note difficulties with work, about 70% are dissatisfied with their financial situation, and only 24.3% express dissatisfaction with their health status. The last figure typically causes bewilderment as to why HIV-infected respondents assess their condition in that manner. During conversations with respondents, we discovered that this category of subjects holds a distinctive attitude toward their lives, evidently from the moment they reconsidered their diagnosis and their overall perspective on life itself. In these assessments

of their health, we observe the individual's engagement with the 'here-and-now' situation: respondents explain that at that specific moment, they feel well, so there is no reason to complain. Planning for what will come next is uncharacteristic for them. Sixty-seven percent of the respondents recognize that they themselves are to blame for what happened, reflecting on the lifestyle they led. It should be noted that HIV infection is closely linked to drug use. Over 70% of respondents in our study sample had drug addiction.

We present the results of Leary's interpersonal relations diagnostic method in comparison with the normative sample to more clearly demonstrate the differences. The comparative analysis of the indicators enables us to draw the following conclusions. There are no significant differences between the experimental and control groups on the scales of 'Dominance,' 'Selfishness,' and 'Submission.' Regarding the scales of 'Dependence,' 'Friendliness,' and 'Altruism,' the following is observed: individuals living with HIV exhibit significantly lower levels of benevolence, are less oriented toward social approval, do not anticipate support despite obviously needing it, yet are neither ready nor able to accept it. They are not inclined to show sympathy themselves and do not take an interest in others; that is, they are very closed off to forming constructive, benevolent relationships both in professional and personal contexts. Furthermore, the scores of HIV-infected individuals significantly exceed those of the normative sample on the 'Aggressiveness' and 'Suspiciousness' scales. They are often characterized by a hostile attitude toward others and distrust of people, which was evidently observed in these respondents even before the onset of the disease. After confirmation of HIV seropositivity, fear of stigmatization also arises. Alienation towards the hostile world as they perceive it is observed, along with suspicion, touchiness, and distrust. An intrapersonal conflict between the desire for recognition and hostility towards others is observed in this sample. Statistical differences between the experimental and control groups were confirmed using Student's t-test.

Conclusions. Psychological science is naturally motivated to study various manifestations and aspects of the life space of HIV/AIDS-infected individuals. Such a study provides an opportunity to understand the individual in a crisis situation — a situation of health loss, a re-evaluation of one's life, and life under the threat of an incurable disease.

HIV-positive individuals must find their new place in life. The importance of understanding and becoming aware of one's new condition can lead to transformations of the inner world, whereby a person begins to appreciate the value of life, human relationships, and moral values. A person begins to contemplate matters they have never considered before. It is precisely this ordeal that has the potential to provide a person with understanding and a sense of life's value.

To a significant extent, how one's life will be structured after the diagnosis depends on the individual themselves. During psychological support, emphasis

should be placed on fostering a prosocial lifestyle in such clients, their readiness for personal transformation, and the development of self-sufficiency as a means of coping with life's challenges. As M. G. Ivashkina writes, 'it is important to remember that even the most terrible diagnosis is not the end of life.' It is possible that life simply offers a chance to see new facets of it.' [3].

The system of personal values and a person's worldview undergo profound changes as a result of the illness. The phenomenon of worldview has a complex, multi-level structure. The system of values reflects the main, essential markers of relationships with the world and others. Along with the value system, a person's life strategy also changes.

The study of psychological phenomena in individuals with severe illnesses will enable the development of more effective methods of psychological assistance, counseling, and psychotherapy, as well as the identification of the most effective preventive measures.

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TEXT VERSUS VOICE MODALITY IN COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THERAPY DIGITAL DIARIES: A STUDY PROTOCOL COMPARING PERCEIVED EMPATHY, ENGAGEMENT, AND USAGE FREQUENCY

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Abstract. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) relies heavily on homework and structured diary techniques such as Situation–Emotion–Reaction–Thought (SERT) records to consolidate therapeutic learning between sessions. Despite the accessibility benefits of digital CBT tools, low engagement and high attrition rates remain significant barriers to sustained clinical outcomes. While text-based conversational agents for mental health are well-established, emerging voice-based agents may enhance perceived empathy through prosodic cues, tone variation, and natural conversational flow. This paper presents a rigorous randomized controlled trial protocol comparing text-based and voice-based CBT diary assistants over a 4-week intervention period. We hypothesize that participants assigned to the voice-based assistant will report higher perceived empathy, greater engagement (measured by session completion and interaction duration), and higher usage frequency than those using the text-based assistant. Secondary objectives include examining therapeutic alliance with the digital assistant, preliminary symptom changes in depression and anxiety, and user satisfaction. If our hypotheses are supported, the findings will provide evidence-based guidance for designing more engaging and emotionally resonant digital mental health interventions.

Keywords: cognitive behavioral therapy; digital diary; voice assistant; conversational agent; perceived empathy; user engagement; therapeutic alliance.

1. Introduction

1.1. CBT Homework and the Engagement Challenge in Digital Environments

Cognitive behavioral therapy is among the most empirically supported psychotherapies for depression, anxiety disorders, and related mental health conditions. Central to CBT's therapeutic mechanism is the assignment and completion of between-session homework, which allows patients to practice newly learned skills

in naturalistic settings and consolidate learning outside the therapeutic hour. Structured diary techniques — such as ABC (Activating Event–Belief–Consequence) records or SERT (Situation–Emotion–Reaction–Thought) logs — are particularly valued components of CBT protocols, as they enable patients to identify cognitive distortions, monitor mood patterns, track behavioral responses, and develop adaptive thinking strategies.^{[1][2][3][4]}

Despite the theoretical importance of homework in CBT, adherence remains a persistent clinical challenge. Research consistently demonstrates that patients frequently struggle to maintain consistent diary completion over extended treatment periods. The emergence of digital CBT tools and smartphone applications was designed to address this gap by offering automated reminders, personalized feedback, convenient access, and reduced barriers to participation. However, engagement with digital CBT interventions remains suboptimal, with studies of smartphone-delivered CBT revealing that while participants typically initiate use, many discontinue within the first two to four weeks, significantly limiting the accumulation of therapeutic benefits and skill practice.^{[2][5][6]}

Understanding which design elements and delivery mechanisms enhance and sustain user engagement with digital CBT homework tools is therefore critical for maximizing the public health impact of these interventions and improving clinical outcomes.

1.2. Conversational Agents in Mental Health: The Question of Modality

In response to scalability challenges and the need to extend evidence-based care beyond traditional therapy, conversational agents — also termed digital assistants, chatbots, or dialogue systems — have emerged as a promising technological approach for delivering CBT-based support at scale. These artificially intelligent systems engage users through natural language interaction, simulating therapeutic dialogue, and providing structured psychoeducation, cognitive restructuring practice, and skill-building exercises. Emerging evidence suggests that well-designed conversational agents can deliver meaningful symptom improvements comparable to therapist-delivered brief interventions, often with engagement rates exceeding those of static digital applications.^{[7][8]}

However, the overwhelming majority of existing conversational mental health agents are text-based, operating through written chat interfaces. Emerging voice-based agents, powered by advances in automatic speech recognition and neural text-to-speech synthesis, represent a less-studied frontier in digital mental health. Voice-based interaction may differ fundamentally from text-based interaction in ways that substantially influence users' emotional experience and perception of the agent's therapeutic qualities. Voice naturally conveys prosodic information — pitch contours, intonation patterns, speech rate, voice quality, and emotional coloration — that text-based communication cannot encode. Additionally,

voice interaction more closely mimics natural human conversation, with authentic turn-taking, variable pacing, and paralinguistic cues such as brief vocal affirmations (“I see,” “That makes sense”) that may foster a heightened sense of social presence and responsiveness.^{[9][10][11][12]}

1.3. Perceived Empathy as a Mechanism of Therapeutic Change

In psychotherapy research, therapeutic alliance — defined as the collaborative relationship between therapist and client, encompassing agreement on treatment goals, agreement on treatment tasks, and an emotional bond between participants — is a robust and consistent predictor of treatment outcomes across diverse modalities and disorders. In digital mental health contexts, parallel constructs such as digital therapeutic alliance and perceived empathy have been examined. Perceived empathy refers to the user’s subjective sense that the digital assistant understands their emotional experience, validates their concerns, and responds warmly and supportively.^{[13][14][15][16]}

Recent qualitative and quantitative research demonstrates that users can and do develop meaningful therapeutic alliances with text-based conversational agents for mental health, as measured by validated instruments such as the Working Alliance Inventory–Short Revised (WAI-SR). However, direct empirical comparisons of perceived empathy and therapeutic alliance across different interaction modalities (text versus voice) remain scarce in the literature. Given accumulating neuroscientific evidence linking the perception of vocal prosody to activation of empathy-related brain regions, it is theoretically plausible that voice-based agents may elicit stronger and more immediate perceptions of empathy than text-based counterparts.^{[15][16][17][18][19][20][13]}

1.4. Study Aim and Significance

While conversational agents for mental health have proliferated, and while engagement in digital CBT has been extensively studied, direct comparisons of text-based versus voice-based CBT diary assistants on key dimensions — perceived empathy, user engagement, and usage frequency — are limited in the empirical literature. Most existing research examines either text-based or voice-based systems in isolation, or investigates engagement in generic mental health applications without isolating modality as a systematic independent variable.^[18]

The primary aim of this paper is to propose and describe a rigorous, adequately powered randomized controlled trial protocol comparing text-based and voice-based CBT diary assistants. By carefully controlling therapeutic content, structural elements, and behavioral contingencies while systematically manipulating interaction modality alone, we can rigorously isolate the effects of voice on users’ emotional experience, engagement patterns, and long-term usage behavior. We hypothesize that voice-based delivery will demonstrate superior outcomes on primary measures of perceived empathy, engagement, and usage frequency

compared to text-based delivery, with implications for clinical practice, digital mental health policy, and the design principles for next-generation conversational mental health agents.

2. Methods: Proposed Study Design

2.1. Study Design Overview

This investigation will employ a parallel-group, two-arm, individually randomized controlled trial design with 1:1 allocation. Participants will be randomly assigned to either a text-based CBT diary assistant or a voice-based CBT diary assistant. Both interventions will be structured identically with respect to therapeutic content, homework structure, and behavioral contingencies; the primary independent variable is interaction modality. The intervention period is 4 weeks, with assessment points at baseline (week 0), early intervention (week 1, to capture initial alliance and engagement trajectories), and endpoint (week 4). Recruitment will be conducted from outpatient mental health clinics, online mental health communities, and university-affiliated counseling centers.

2.2. Participants and Recruitment

Target Population: Community-dwelling adults aged 18–65 years with mild to moderate symptoms of depression and/or anxiety, or individuals currently engaged in mental health treatment for mood or anxiety conditions.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Meets diagnostic criteria for a current depressive disorder, anxiety disorder, or clinically significant subclinical depressive/anxiety symptoms (confirmed via clinical interview or validated screening questionnaire).
- Fluent in English.
- Owns a smartphone, tablet, or computer with reliable internet access.
- Provides informed consent and commits to 4-week study participation.
- No current active suicidal ideation or substance use disorder requiring intensive specialized intervention.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Severe psychiatric conditions (e. g., active bipolar I disorder, psychosis, substance use disorder requiring hospitalization).
- Acute suicidality or recent suicide attempt.
- Significant cognitive impairment or developmental disability preventing independent use of the digital system.
- Concurrent engagement in intensive face-to-face psychotherapy (more than one session per week during the study period) to minimize confounding therapeutic effects.
- Prior extensive experience with either the text-based or voice-based assistant to avoid familiarity bias.

Recruitment and Sampling: Participants will be recruited through a combination of channels including announcements at outpatient mental health clinics, postings in online mental health communities, university psychology department communications, and targeted social media outreach. Stratified randomization will be employed, stratifying by age group (18–34, 35–49, 50–65 years) and baseline symptom severity (mild versus moderate) to ensure balanced representation across these variables in both study arms. Target sample size: $n = 150\text{--}200$ for a fully powered trial; pilot phase $n = 20\text{--}30$ per arm.

2.3. Interventions: Therapeutic Structure and Modality

Common CBT Framework:

Both treatment arms will employ an identical evidence-based CBT framework centered on the SERT (Situation–Emotion–Reaction–Thought) model, widely used in both digital and face-to-face CBT implementations. Each structured diary entry will systematically guide the user through four key components:^{[4][21]}

1. **Situation:** Identifying and describing a specific recent triggering event or moment that precipitated an emotional response.

2. **Emotion:** Naming and quantifying the intensity of the emotional response experienced (using a 0–100 numerical scale).

3. **Reaction:** Describing the physiological, behavioral, and cognitive responses (what the body did, what actions were taken, what behaviors occurred).

4. **Thought:** Identifying automatic thoughts, interpretations, or core beliefs associated with the triggering event.

Following the completion of the diary entry, the digital assistant will provide:

- **Reflective feedback:** Validation of the user’s emotional experience and gentle identification of cognitive patterns or distortions.

- **Psychoeducational elements:** Personalized, concise explanations of relevant CBT principles (e.g., the relationship between thoughts, emotions, and behaviors).

- **Behavioral coping suggestions:** Tailored prompts and exercises to practice specific evidence-based coping skills (e.g., relaxation techniques, problem-solving strategies, cognitive restructuring).

Users will be encouraged to complete one diary entry per day, with each session requiring approximately 10–15 minutes. Optional automated reminders (via push notification or email) will be available at a user-selected time, but not mandated.

Text-Based Condition:

Participants in the text condition will interact with the assistant through a chat interface on their smartphone, tablet, or computer. They will type responses to the structured prompts, and the assistant will generate text-based responses in real time using a conversational, warm, and reflective tone. Responses will use second-person address (e.g., “I hear that you felt anxious when...”) to create a sense of attentiveness and understanding, but will be delivered solely through written text with no audio component.

Voice-Based Condition:

Participants in the voice condition will interact through a voice interface. Users will speak their responses aloud, with the system capturing speech via automatic speech recognition, and the assistant will respond using synthesized speech with carefully engineered prosodic features designed to convey empathy and warmth. Key design specifications for the voice assistant will include:

- **Prosodic design:** The synthesized voice will incorporate variable fundamental frequency (pitch), natural intonation contours, and appropriate speech rate variation to convey warmth, understanding, and responsive engagement.^{[10][19][22][9]}

- **Paralinguistic features:** Subtle vocal characteristics (e.g., slight breathiness, variable speech rate, and subtle vocal quality modulation) that listeners associate with agreeableness, emotional availability, and interpersonal warmth.^[9]

- **Conversational turn-taking and pacing:** Natural pausing, acknowledgments, and vocal backchannels (“I see,” “That makes sense”) to simulate authentic human dialogue.^[11]

- **Reflective, validating tone:** Similar linguistic and emotional content to the text condition, but conveyed through speech synthesis designed to sound warm, supportive, and engaged.

Critically, the semantic content of prompts, feedback messages, and behavioral suggestions will be held strictly constant between the two modality conditions, ensuring that modality — and specifically the prosodic and paralinguistic properties of voice — represents the primary differentiating independent variable.

2.4. Measures and Assessment Instruments

Primary Outcome Measures

Perceived Empathy of the Digital Assistant:

Perceived empathy will be measured using a validated or validated-adapted empathy or warmth assessment instrument, supplemented with items assessing the user’s perception of the assistant’s understanding and responsiveness. Candidate instruments include the Perceived Therapist Empathy Scale (PTES), adapted for digital agent context, or selected items from the Session Evaluation Questionnaire (SEQ) that capture the user’s subjective sense of being heard, understood, and supported. Assessments will be administered at week 1 and week 4 to capture both initial and sustained empathy perception across the intervention period.

User Engagement:

Multiple dimensions of engagement will be assessed through both system-tracked metrics and self-report:

Automated system metrics:

- Number of completed diary sessions throughout the 4-week period.
- Average duration per session (in minutes).
- Number of conversational turns (exchanges) per session.

- Proportion of calendar days with at least one diary entry (expressed as a percentage of the 28-day intervention window).

Self-report engagement:

- User Engagement Scale (UES) or equivalent short engagement questionnaire administered at weeks 1 and 4.

Usage Frequency:

- Percentage of days used: The proportion of calendar days (out of 28) during which the participant completed at least one diary entry.

- Mean number of entries per week.

- Time to disengagement: The number of days from first use to the final recorded interaction (if discontinuation occurs prior to study end).

Secondary Outcome Measures

Symptom Severity Measures:

To explore preliminary clinical effects and symptom trajectories, participants will complete:

- Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) for depression severity at baseline and week 4.

- Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) for anxiety severity at baseline and week 4.

These brief, validated instruments are sensitive to treatment effects in digital mental health trials and allow rapid assessment of clinically meaningful change.^{[8][23]}

Digital Therapeutic Alliance:

The Working Alliance Inventory–Short Revised (WAI-SR), a 12-item self-report measure assessing alliance across dimensions of task agreement, goal agreement, and therapeutic bond, will be administered at week 1 and week 4. The WAI-SR has been successfully adapted for digital mental health contexts and demonstrates adequate reliability and validity when measuring alliance with conversational agents.^{[16][17][13][15]}

User Satisfaction and Perceived Usefulness:

A brief post-study questionnaire (5–10 items) will assess overall satisfaction with the assigned assistant, perceived usefulness for emotion regulation and thought monitoring, likelihood of continued use beyond the study, and modality comfort and preference.

Qualitative Feedback:

Optional semi-structured interviews (15–20 minutes) or written open-ended responses will be collected from a purposive subsample ($n \approx 15$ –20 per arm) exploring subjective experiences, perceived strengths and limitations, engagement barriers and facilitators, and factors influencing adherence to diary completion.

2.5. Procedure

Baseline Phase (Week 0):

1. Online eligibility screening and informed consent.
2. Baseline questionnaires (PHQ-9, GAD-7, demographics, technology familiarity).
3. Random assignment via stratified web-based randomization.
4. Brief orientation to assigned assistant (instructional video and practice session).

Intervention Phase (Weeks 1–4):

1. Participants encouraged to complete daily diary entries.
2. Week 1: Empathy perception scale, engagement self-report, WAI-SR.
3. Week 4: All primary and secondary outcome measures, user satisfaction questionnaire, optional qualitative interviews.

Data Analysis:

- **Perceived Empathy & Engagement:** Repeated measures ANOVA (time × condition) for empathy; t-tests or Mann–Whitney U tests for engagement metrics.
- **Usage Frequency:** Chi-square tests and Kaplan–Meier survival analyses.
- **Secondary Outcomes:** t-tests for symptom change; mediation analyses examining empathy as a mechanism.
- **Sensitivity Analyses:** Controlling for baseline demographics, symptom severity, and technology familiarity.

Ethical Oversight:

Institutional review board approval required. Secure data encryption; anonymization via study ID; safety protocols for suicidal ideation (embedded crisis resources); informed consent and voluntary withdrawal provisions; compliance with GDPR/HIPAA or local data protection regulations

3. Expected Results and Hypotheses

H1 (Primary): Participants assigned to the voice-based assistant will report significantly higher perceived empathy scores compared to those assigned to the text-based assistant at both week 1 and week 4.

Rationale: Voice prosody and paralinguistic features convey warmth, understanding, and emotional availability. Neuroimaging evidence demonstrates that prosody perception engages empathy-related neural regions, suggesting a direct neurobiological link between vocal characteristics and empathic perception.^{[19][20][22][10][9]}

H2 (Primary): The voice-based group will demonstrate significantly higher engagement (more completed sessions, longer session duration, more turns per session) than the text-based group.

Rationale: Enhanced perceived empathy and conversational naturalness create a more engaging, emotionally resonant experience, increasing intrinsic motivation for sustained interaction.^{[12][11]}

H3 (Primary): The voice-based group will show significantly higher usage frequency (higher proportion of days with entries, more entries per week, fewer dropouts) over the 4-week period.

Rationale: If voice modality enhances perceived empathy and emotional connection, users experience greater satisfaction and motivation to return daily.^{[8][12]}

H4 (Exploratory): Perceived empathy will mediate the relationship between modality (text versus voice) and engagement/usage frequency, with a stronger mediation pathway in the voice condition.

H5 (Exploratory): Preliminary trends toward greater symptom reduction (PHQ-9, GAD-7) in the voice-based group, potentially mediated by higher engagement and greater skill practice.

4. Discussion

4.1. Clinical and Public Health Implications

If empirical findings support our hypotheses, the implications for mental health practice and public health are substantial. Digital CBT tools persistently suffer from poor engagement and high dropout rates; if voice-based delivery demonstrably enhances perceived empathy and sustained usage, this represents a potentially scalable solution to a critical clinical problem. Clinicians could integrate a voice-based CBT diary assistant as a between-session intervention, substantially increasing the volume of skill practice and therapeutic learning relative to in-person sessions alone. For individuals in underserved geographic or socioeconomic contexts unable to access traditional therapy, a highly engaging voice-based CBT assistant could serve a significant public health function.^[8]

4.2. Design Implications for Digital Mental Health Conversational Agents

This study challenges the implicit assumption that therapeutic content and structure alone determine digital intervention effectiveness, suggesting that modality — the sensory and interactive channel through which information is delivered — fundamentally influences emotional experience and engagement. Findings could highlight the importance of investing in high-quality voice synthesis with careful attention to prosodic design, natural turn-taking, and warmth-conveying paralinguistic features.^{[14][22][9]}

4.3. Acknowledged Limitations

- Sample likely comprises mild-to-moderate symptom severity and relatively high technology comfort; generalizability to severe conditions or low-literacy populations uncertain.
- 4-week intervention period is brief for examining long-term adherence or sustained symptom improvement.
- Voice synthesis quality varies; findings may not replicate across different text-to-speech engines.
- Self-selection bias may result in higher motivation and technology comfort in recruited sample compared to broader populations.

4.4. Future Directions

Pilot studies, extended intervention periods (8–12 weeks), multimodal designs (voice + avatar), systematic variation of prosodic parameters, extension to other clinical populations and therapeutic targets, and real-world implementation feasibility studies are warranted.

5. Conclusion

This study protocol presents a rigorous, theory-informed trial comparing text-based and voice-based CBT diary assistants on perceived empathy, engagement, and usage frequency. By directly testing whether voice modality — through prosodic warmth and conversational authenticity — enhances emotional experience and adherence to digital CBT homework, this work addresses a significant gap in the digital mental health literature. If findings support our hypotheses, the research will provide actionable evidence guiding the design of more engaging, emotionally resonant, and therapeutically effective digital mental health interventions.

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THE PSYCHOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS' SELF-CONCEPT AND SUICIDAL TENDENCIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the psychological relationship between adolescents' self-concept and suicidal tendencies. The impact of such factors as self-esteem, social acceptance, and a sense of meaning in life on suicidal behavior is analyzed. In addition, the importance of psychological support and effective ways of preventing suicide among adolescents are highlighted.*

Keywords: *adolescent, self-concept, suicidal tendencies, psychological support, prevention.*

Relevance of the Study: In modern society, the increase in suicidal behavior among adolescents has become a serious socio-psychological problem for the fields of psychology and education. International and national studies indicate that this phenomenon is closely related not only to social conditions but also to the level of an individual's internal psychological development. During adolescence, self-concept is not yet fully formed; emotional instability, decreased self-esteem, lack of clear life goals, and difficulties in relationships with peers and adults are frequently observed. Such conditions may intensify internal distress, increase feelings of loneliness, and lead to a loss of meaning in life. Moreover, the expansion of the modern information space, the culture of comparison on social media, cyberbullying, and instability in family relationships further deepen adolescents' psychological vulnerability. These factors distort the image of the "self" and contribute to a reduced sense of personal value. In this regard, a systematic scientific study of the relationship between self-concept and suicidal tendencies makes it possible to gain a deeper understanding of the psychological mechanisms of suicide, to identify adolescents at risk at an early stage, and to develop effective preventive programs in educational institutions. Therefore, this topic is highly relevant and has significant scientific and practical importance.

Purpose of the Study: To identify the psychological relationship between the level of adolescents' self-concept and suicidal tendencies and to substantiate ways of preventing them.

Objectives of the Study:

- to analyze the theoretical foundations of the concepts of self-concept and suicidal tendencies;
- to identify the psychological characteristics of self-esteem during adolescence;
- to systematize the main psychological factors of suicidal tendencies;
- to determine the relationship between self-concept and suicidal tendencies;
- to develop psychological recommendations aimed at suicide prevention.

Scientific Novelty of the Study: The study provides a comprehensive analysis of adolescents' suicidal tendencies from the perspective of the structural components of self-concept (self-esteem, personal identity, and meaning in life). In addition, practical psychological preventive approaches applicable in the educational environment are systematized and proposed.

Results of the Study: The study revealed that adolescents with a low level of self-concept and unstable self-esteem are more prone to suicidal thoughts. It was also demonstrated that students with a well-formed positive self-perception show higher resilience to stress and maintain stronger motivation for life.

Conclusion of the Study: The development of adolescents' self-concept is one of the key factors ensuring their psychological well-being. Low self-esteem, identity crisis, and social isolation contribute to the formation of suicidal tendencies. Therefore, systematic psychological work aimed at developing self-concept in educational institutions is an effective way to prevent suicide.

Socio-economic, cultural, and informational changes in modern society have a significant impact on the formation of adolescents' personalities. This period represents an important stage of development characterized by the awareness of one's own "self," the formation of values, and the determination of life goals. At this time, psychological stability tends to weaken, while susceptibility to emotional distress and internal conflicts increases. As a result, suicidal thoughts and behaviors may emerge. Therefore, a scientific analysis of the characteristics of adolescents' self-concept development and its relationship with suicidal tendencies is a pressing issue for both psychological science and educational practice.

The Concept of Self-Concept and Its Characteristics in Adolescence. Self-concept refers to an individual's perception of oneself as a unique person, as well as the awareness and evaluation of one's own qualities, abilities, capabilities, behavior, emotional characteristics, and social position. It forms the internal image of the "self" and determines the ways in which a person interacts with the surrounding environment. This concept includes self-knowledge, self-esteem, self-acceptance, life goals, and a system of values. Adolescence is a crucial stage

in which self-concept develops intensively and undergoes structural reorganization. During this period, a child begins to perceive oneself not only as a member of a family or a student, but also as an independent individual. Adolescents evaluate their appearance, behavior, social status, and abilities by comparing themselves with their peers. As a result, the image of the “self” may become unstable and full of contradictions. According to Erik Erikson’s theory of psychosocial development, the main psychological task of adolescence is the achievement of identity formation. In this process, young people seek answers to such questions as “Who am I?”, “What do I want to become?”, and “What is my place in society?”. If this task is not fully accomplished, adolescents may experience role confusion, lack of self-confidence, internal instability, uncertainty about the future, and a loss of meaning in life (Erikson, 1968).

Adolescents whose self-concept is insufficiently developed often demonstrate the following psychological characteristics:

- feeling unnecessary or insignificant in society;
- doubting their own personal value and abilities;
- predominance of hopelessness and fear regarding the future;
- excessive dependence on external evaluation and peers’ opinions rather than on their own judgments;
- perceiving failures as evidence of complete personal incompetence.

Such a psychological state weakens adolescents’ emotional stability and increases the level of distress. Research shows that adolescents’ self-esteem has a direct impact on their emotional stability (Brannam, 2012; Orr, 1995). Failure to understand, accept, and value oneself leads to the deepening of internal conflicts and reduces the ability to cope with life difficulties. As a result, favorable conditions are created for the emergence of suicidal thoughts and the development of destructive behavior.

The Concept of Suicidal Tendencies and Their Psychological Foundations.

Suicidal tendency is defined as an individual’s thoughts about ending one’s life, planning such actions, or being psychologically prepared to carry them out. It is not a phenomenon that arises suddenly; rather, it represents a complex psychological process formed as a result of long-term accumulated emotional distress, internal conflicts, personal crises, and social difficulties. Suicidal tendencies are often accompanied by profound emotional states such as hopelessness, loss of meaning in life, loneliness, helplessness, and feelings of being unnecessary or unwanted. These conditions are particularly pronounced in adolescents due to the incomplete stability of their psyche and the ongoing formation of their self-concept. The American psychologist E. Shneidman identified “psychological pain” (psychache) as the main cause of suicide. According to him, under conditions of unbearable internal suffering, a person may perceive suicide as the only way to escape life’s

difficulties. This pain often arises from feelings of humiliation, lack of love and support, self-hatred, and loss of hope (Shneidman, 1993).

According to T. Joiner's interpersonal theory of suicide, two main psychological factors contribute to the formation of suicidal intent:

1. feeling oneself to be unnecessary or a burden to society;
2. social isolation, loneliness, and the breakdown of emotional connections with others (Joiner, 2005).

The scholar argues that when these two factors persist over a long period, an individual's motivation to live weakens and the perception of oneself as a burden develops. Such a perception may lead to the stabilization of suicidal thoughts. Both of these factors are directly related to the content of self-concept. Adolescents' social isolation and lack of self-confidence increase the likelihood of suicidal ideation (King & Merchant, 2008; Meta-analysis, 2019). Low self-esteem, failure to perceive one's personal value, and the formation of a negative self-image distance individuals from the social environment and intensify feelings of loneliness. In addition, the inability to find one's place in society and the perception of being useless to others contribute to the deepening of psychological pain.

The Relationship Between Self-Concept and Suicidal Tendencies. Numerous national and international studies confirm that there is a close psychological relationship between self-concept and suicidal behavior. An adolescent's attitude toward oneself, the level of perceived personal value, and confidence in the future determine how he or she reacts to life difficulties. When the image of the "self" is formed negatively, any failure may be perceived as a severe psychological blow.

Low self-esteem is manifested through the following characteristics:

- perceiving oneself as "weak," "unsuccessful," or "incapable";
- denying one's personal value and constantly comparing oneself with others;
- increased feelings of guilt and shame and the emergence of self-directed aggression.

These psychological states weaken an individual's internal resources and reduce the ability to cope with life difficulties. As a result, the likelihood of suicidal thoughts increases significantly, and in some cases such thoughts may develop into actual actions. Low self-esteem has been found to be associated with high levels of depression, hopelessness, and suicidal ideation among adolescents (Orr, King & Seigel, 1995). According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), one of the main risk factors for suicide among adolescents is identity crisis and impaired self-esteem (WHO, 2014). This indicates that suicidal behavior depends not only on social conditions but primarily on the individual's internal psychological structure.

Adolescents with a distorted self-concept tend to:

- perceive difficulties not as temporary obstacles but as life tragedies;

- fail to see alternative ways of solving problems and believe that there is no way out of a crisis;

- consider suicide as the only way to stop emotional pain;
- withdraw from others and conceal their inner distress.

In such situations, adolescents often feel ashamed to ask for help and try to solve their problems alone, which further aggravates their psychological condition.

In contrast, adolescents with a positive self-concept:

- are more resilient to difficulties and perceive them as temporary phenomena;
- feel their own value and have confidence in their abilities;
- are not afraid to seek help from psychologists, teachers, and parents;
- look to the future with hope and maintain their life goals.

For such individuals, even in stressful situations, the motivation to preserve life prevails, and the likelihood of suicidal thoughts is significantly lower. The level of self-concept development is one of the key psychological factors determining adolescents' resistance to suicidal risk. This demonstrates the decisive role of psychological and pedagogical interventions aimed at developing self-concept in suicide prevention. Studies indicate a statistically significant relationship between self-esteem and suicidal behavior, highlighting the importance of strengthening self-worth to prevent suicidal actions among adolescents (Soto-Sanz et al., 2019).

Prevention and Psychological Support Strategies. Reducing suicidal tendencies among adolescents requires comprehensive and systematic psychological and pedagogical interventions. Preventive measures in this area should be aimed at strengthening self-concept, enhancing emotional stability, and supporting adaptation to the social environment. In this regard, the following directions are particularly important:

1. *Development of self-esteem.* It is necessary to strengthen adolescents' self-confidence through trainings, reflective exercises, creative tasks, and the organization of situations of success. Identifying adolescents' strengths and recognizing their personal achievements increases their sense of self-worth and contributes to the formation of a positive self-image.

2. *Formation of emotional intelligence.* Teaching skills of recognizing, expressing, and regulating emotions enables adolescents to avoid accumulating internal distress and to release it in constructive ways. The ability to verbalize emotions, regulate oneself in stressful situations, and resolve conflicts peacefully are important indicators of psychological stability.

3. *Creating a social support environment.* Establishing trusting, open, and supportive relationships with school psychologists, class teachers, and parents helps adolescents avoid feelings of loneliness. Developing a culture of seeking help in difficult situations and creating an atmosphere of understanding and acceptance play a decisive role in preventing suicidal thoughts.

4. *Early diagnosis.* Timely identification of depressive symptoms, social withdrawal, sudden behavioral changes, aggression, or isolation makes it possible to prevent dangerous situations. Psychological screening, observation, and interviews, as well as individual work with students at risk, are essential.

Conclusion. Adolescents' self-concept is a fundamental foundation of their psychological well-being and an important indicator of personal development. The negative formation of the self-image, low self-esteem, lack of a sense of personal value, and social isolation weaken adolescents' inner stability and directly contribute to the emergence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors. The findings of the study demonstrate that the level of self-concept plays a decisive role in the increase or decrease of suicidal tendencies. Therefore, suicide prevention should not be limited to medical or social measures alone but should primarily focus on supporting the psychological development of adolescents and fostering their sense of self-worth. Strengthening the role of psychological services in educational institutions, implementing programs aimed at developing self-esteem, cultivating a culture of emotional support, and establishing systematic cooperation with parents can significantly improve adolescents' psychological well-being. Thus, educating a young generation that is able to value itself, perceive the meaning of life, regard difficulties as temporary phenomena, and look to the future with confidence is an important task not only for the education system but for society as a whole. Such individuals constitute a reliable foundation for sustainable social development, social security, and spiritual well-being.

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THE INTERRELATIONSHIP OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of an empirical study examining the relationship between the level of development of cognitive processes and the psychological well-being of primary school children. The study involved 90 fourth-grade students, divided into experimental and control groups. Correlation analysis revealed statistically significant positive associations between cognitive indicators and components of psychological well-being in the control group. The results indicate that the positive relationship between cognitive development and psychological well-being is mediated by favorable conditions within the educational environment. Based on the research findings, a psycho-pedagogical support program aimed at fostering the psychological well-being of primary school children has been developed.*

Keywords: *primary school children, cognitive processes, psychological well-being, correlation analysis, educational environment, developmental program.*

Introduction

Primary school age is recognized as a sensitive period for the development of key cognitive functions and the formation of the foundations of an individual's psychological well-being [5]. The studies by V. M. Postavnev and I. V. Postavneva emphasize the importance of early primary school age in mastering the fundamentals of academic activity and successful school adaptation [1]; [2]. In contemporary psychology, the nature of the mutual influence between these two domains of child development is actively debated. Theoretical analysis [3]; [6] suggests a positive correlation between the level of psychological well-being and measures

of cognitive abilities, as well as the significant role of the psychological climate within the learning group in optimizing cognitive functioning [3]; [6]. In the context of the stated problem, studies examining the relationship between specific cognitive functions and psychological well-being are of interest. For example, the research by E. V. Pyatnitskaya and Yu. A. Bolotnikova demonstrates a significant correlation between the development of thinking, attention stability, and the level of psychological well-being in primary school children, thereby substantiating the relevance of further investigation of this issue [4]. The aim of this study was to empirically investigate the nature of the relationship between cognitive processes and psychological well-being in primary school-aged children.

Methods

The study was conducted at Rumyantsevskaya Secondary School in the Moscow Region. The sample comprised 90 fourth-grade students (mean age 10 years), randomly divided into an experimental group (EEG, $n = 45$) and a control group (CG, $n = 45$), balanced by gender. A set of validated instruments was employed to assess the cognitive domain: the Bourdon-Anfimov correction test for attention evaluation; A. R. Luria's '10 Words' method (memory); Y. I. Kulagina and V. N. Kalyutsky's 'Simple Analogies' (logical reasoning); N. L. Belopolskaya's 'Exclusion of the Irrelevant' (analytical thinking); and B. D. Karvasarsky's 'Study of Thinking Speed.' The level of psychological well-being was assessed using the Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWB-c), adapted for children aged 8–12 years, comprising six subscales: environmental mastery, personal growth, purpose in life, self-acceptance, autonomy, and positive relations with others. Data processing was performed using statistical methods within the IBM SPSS Statistics software. To test hypotheses regarding relationships, the nonparametric Spearman rank correlation coefficient was employed.

Results and Discussion

The initial comparative analysis demonstrated that students in the experimental group exhibited statistically lower mean scores on all scales of psychological well-being. The integral score in the EEG was 124.9 (SD = 12.6), whereas in the control group it was 142.8 (SD = 11.5). This result indicates a priori less favorable psychological profiles among children in the experimental sample. Correlation analysis revealed fundamental differences in the nature of relationships between the groups. Statistically significant moderate positive correlations were found in the control group between cognitive indicators and well-being components. The most pronounced relationships were observed between success in cognitive test performance and aspects such as personal growth and the overall integral well-being indicator. For example, attention was significantly correlated with personal growth ($r=0.38$, $p<0.01$) and the integral

score ($r=0.36$, $p<0.01$). Similar stable correlations were identified for memory, logical, and analytical thinking. In the experimental group, correlations between all cognitive indicators and the PWB-c scales were weak (correlation coefficients r ranging from 0.06 to 0.22) and statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

The obtained results partially confirm the proposed hypotheses. Indeed, under conditions characterized by a higher baseline level of psychological well-being (control group), there is a stable positive correlation between the development of cognitive functions and the child's personal-social well-being. This enables cognitive abilities to be regarded as a significant resource for self-development, adaptation, and the establishment of harmonious social relationships within a supportive environment. However, in the group with initially low well-being indicators (EEG), this pattern is not observed. It can be assumed that under less favorable socio-psychological conditions (possibly related to the characteristics of the family or educational environment), the child's cognitive achievements no longer directly translate into subjective well-being. External stressors, as well as deficits in support and motivation, which can inhibit the positive impact of cognitive skills on psychological well-being, come to the forefront. Thus, cognitive resources realize their potential for personal development only when a favorable socio-psychological context is present.

Conclusion

The conducted study allows the following conclusions to be drawn.

1. The level of development of basic cognitive processes (attention, memory, thinking) is statistically significantly positively correlated with indicators of psychological well-being in primary school children; however, this relationship is not universal.
2. The nature and strength of the observed interrelationships are significantly mediated by the conditions of the educational and social environment. Under favorable conditions, cognitive development functions as a factor of personal growth and social adaptation, whereas in unfavorable conditions this relationship weakens or disappears.
3. Targeted psycho-pedagogical interventions are necessary to support psychological well-being and to realize children's cognitive potential. Based on the obtained data, a program for the development of psychological well-being has been developed, consisting of 12 thematic sessions aimed at fostering emotional intelligence, self-regulation skills, constructive communication, and positive self-esteem. The implementation of such programs in the educational process can contribute to creating an environment that not only ensures conditions for the sustainable psychological well-being of each child but also supports cognitive development.

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**THE POTENTIAL OF THE LEGACY OF THE CLASSICS
OF RUSSIAN PEDAGOGY IN MODELING THE CONTENT
OF THE SOCIO-INFORMATIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE
PRESCHOOL EDUCATION TEACHERS**

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***Annotation.** The article highlights the problem of the formation of social and informational competence among the future preschool education teachers. Based on the analysis of the Russian classical pedagogical heritage, a number of aspects have been identified that have made it possible to clarify the definition of socio-informational competence in relation to the future preschool education teachers and to outline ways to model its content.*

***Keywords:** socio-informational competence, legacy of the classics of Russian pedagogy, the future preschool education teachers, pupils.*

The relevance of the formation of socio-informational competence among the future preschool education teachers is determined by several key factors. Firstly, there is a rapid informatization of society, which involves children from an early age. Secondly, there is an increase in teacher requirements: the Federal State Educational Standard for Higher Education assumes the use of information and communication technologies in educational activities in the development of children, in communication with colleagues and parents, in professional development, etc. Thirdly, at preschool age, the foundations of information culture, critical thinking and the ability to evaluate information are laid, which requires appropriate professional and personal abilities from the teacher. Fourthly, the actualization of the social role importance of the teacher as the first professional educator in the life of a preschooler and a role model who is able to protect him from the negative influence of the information environment and adequately fulfill the mission assigned by society.

The problem of the social competence formation among future and practicing specialists is reflected in the works of such researchers as: N. N. Bedenko, A. N. Vasilyeva, A. A. Demchuk, L. S. Karimova, V. N. Kelasyev, M. V. Kirilina, S. N. Krasnokutskaya, N. T. Lavskaya, G. P. Mosyagina, I. L. Pervova, E. N. Rodina, Yu. V. Slesareva, A. V. Spirina, E. N. Chekushkina, I. V. Chernousova, and others. Such researchers as Yu. I. Askerko, O. V. Baranova, V. V. Vyazankova, M. V. Goryachova, O. N. Griban, A. G. Zhuyeva, V. O. Zinchenko, A. N. Popov, F. K. Tubeeva were engaged in solving the problem of forming information competence among future specialists. An analysis of the works on the problem of the formation of socio-informational competence of the future specialists has shown that the dissertations of T. A. Chekalina and D. V. Gulyakin are represented in the scientific field.

Based on the analysis of the above studies, it was determined that the socio-informational competence of the future specialists is an integrated personal and professional quality, including the skills to effectively receive, analyze, use and manage information in various social and professional settings based on the legal and moral norms of modern society.

To clarify the definition of “socio-informational competence” in relation to future preschool education teachers and modeling its content, let us turn to the classical pedagogical heritage, in particular, the purpose of our article is to analyze the ideas of the classics of Russian pedagogy and their use in solving this problem.

Let us turn to the legacy of K. D. Ushinsky, the founder of Russian pedagogy, who repeatedly emphasized in his works the importance of a teacher playing a social role and saw his purpose in the development of society, carried out by collecting inexhaustible spiritual treasures for the younger generation; preparing the minds of pupils; scattering the right ideas among them; indicating a reasonable goal and means to achieve it. The scientist wrote: “The most difficult and inglorious share in the mass of human labors is the best share, the greatest share” [7, p. 12]. Striving to fulfill his teaching mission with dignity, K. D. Ushinsky, at the age of twenty-one, made notes in a diary in which he prescribed tasks for each day, which, in our opinion, are aimed at improving his level of social and informational competence. Here are a few such entries: reading is for the mind; studying; visiting the library; visiting (apparently, K. D. Ushinsky visited people with whom it was interesting and useful for him to communicate); filling out a journal (diary), which is essentially a reflexive activity. Thanks to the recordings made (information processing and storage), subsequent generations of teachers have the opportunity to get acquainted with the personality of the future founder of Russian pedagogical science; his thoughts, position on many issues related to pedagogical activity, which enables future educators to embark on the path of comprehending the pedagogical mission and fulfilling a social function.

K. D. Ushinsky, reflecting, admits in his diary that he has negative qualities and characteristics that he has to work on. To do this, the scientist offers his own recipe

for self-education, which, in our opinion, can be used in the development of a future teacher's reflexive culture as a component of socio-informational competence. Here are some tips from the mentioned recipe: stay calm; be direct in words and deeds; think about your actions; do not be boastful; do not waste useless time, regularly report to yourself for your actions, etc.

In the course of our research, we have revealed that one of the indicators of socio-informational competence is the ability to receive, analyze and use various kinds of information in professional activities. In the pedagogical field, pedagogical literature is important, containing scientific knowledge and information, the use of which will significantly improve the quality of professional activity of the educator. In this regard, the article by K. D. Ushinsky "On the benefits of pedagogical literature" is valuable for our research. The scientist focuses on a number of its potential opportunities: introduces educators to the "noble circle of thinkers"; gives access to the ideas and experience of generations of teachers, practitioners and theorists; helps to realize the scale and responsibility of the profession; gives meaning and value to pedagogical activity; promotes the formation of the right requirements for education; directs attention to subtle, unobvious aspects of child development which are easily overlooked in everyday practice; promotes building partnerships with colleagues, developing reflection; sets guidelines for professional development; in general, it promotes the teacher's entry into the professional pedagogical community [8].

The use of various knowledge and information by a teacher in his professional activity involves studying the characteristics of a pupil in order to build positive relationships with him, selecting appropriate pedagogical tools to achieve the best results in his development. So, the key idea of K. D. Ushinsky's work is "Man as an object of education. The experience of pedagogical anthropology" is a simulation of the parenting process based on a deep and comprehensive knowledge of the child's nature, his characteristics, needs, age and psychological characteristics. To do this, the teacher must draw knowledge from various sciences related to humans (philosophy, physiology, psychology, logic, etc.) [6].

During our research, it was determined that one of the components of socio-informational competence is the ability to communicate, effectively interact and collaborate with people, and work in a team. In this regard, the experience of Alexander Makarenko is valuable to us, who emphasized that a team of teachers united on the basis of common values, principles, goals, requirements and approaches to pupils can achieve results in education. Then the communication of the members of the teaching staff will be constructive and aimed at solving common tasks of education and upbringing of children and youth. A. S. Makarenko attached special importance to such a form of teacher's work as observing the life of each pupil in order to have an idea of the characteristics of his character, aspirations, doubts, weaknesses and strengths, so that he could skillfully build a conversation with him, give advice

and help him cope with age-related crisis problems, guide him along the path of personality development. The scientist recommended that teachers make entries in the diary of their work, which should not have the character of an official document. In fact, this is the process of collecting and analyzing important information that a teacher, based on his pedagogical skills, will use in his professional activities.

A. S. Makarenko attached great importance to the conversation with the pupil and believed that its skillful use as a method of education does not turn this process into moralization, on the contrary, it sets up a friendly teacher-child relationship and enables the pupil to realize and accept moral norms and life attitudes. That is, in fact, the teacher must master the art of conducting conversations not only with colleagues, but also with children. For this, according to A. S. Makarenko, a teacher must master a number of special knowledge and skills: to know what to say to a child in certain situations, to set a voice, to master facial expressions, the ability to give a certain expression to a face; to be able to walk, joke, organize, read on a human face; in general, to behave in such a way that his every movement educates. As the scientist wrote: "I became a real master only when I learned to say "come here" with 15–20 shades, when I learned to give 20 nuances in the setting of the face, figure, voice" [1, p. 145].

V. A. Sukhomlinsky paid considerable attention to the issues of teacher training, the essence of professional activity, improving its effectiveness, as well as analyzing qualities and characteristics attractive to children. The pedagogical legacy of the scientist contains many recommendations on the formation and development of social and informational competence of a teacher, although this term was not used by him in his works. V. A. Sukhomlinsky's long-term observations of the activities of the teaching staff, which he led, confirmed that the pupils are attracted to the personality of the teacher by the harmonious unity of ideals, principles, views, beliefs, moral and ethical positions and actions, which are components of social competence. According to V. A. Sukhomlinsky, a real teacher is someone who goes to his students with bright ideas and beliefs, who is able to inspire children with a desire to learn, reflect and perform worthy deeds with his word and thought. A truly educated and spiritual teacher is one who leads his students to the pinnacle of morality, becomes a guide into the complex world of social relations, and helps them find truthful answers to their questions [2]. The scientist wrote that the teacher prepares for a good lesson all his life: in order to give pupils a spark of knowledge, he needs to absorb a whole sea of light (work "Conversation with a young school principal" [3].

In order for the teacher's preparing for good lessons, V. A. Sukhomlinsky recommended, especially for a novice educator, to accumulate intellectual wealth by replenishing his personal library with books and studying them in depth. The scientist advised making three main sections in the library: on the problems of taught science; on human problems; on issues of the human soul, especially for

children. V. A. Sukhomlinsky noted that every book read by a teacher should enter his educational workshop as a new subtle tool (the work “One Hundred tips for a teacher”) [4]. Thus, the scientist emphasized the importance of the informational component of socio-informational competence in the work of a teacher as a means of professional and personal development and successful professional activity.

V. A. Sukhomlinsky argued that a teacher should not only know science and master its teaching methods, but also possess a number of personal qualities (social competence). First of all, it is important for the teacher to deeply understand the child’s soul, to be able to create an atmosphere of trust and mutual understanding with the pupil, to become a mentor and friend for him. The most important professional quality of a teacher should be sincere and wise love for children, on the basis of which he is able to see the personality in each child, understand individual characteristics, interests, needs and show faith in the development of his potential inherent in nature. Empathy, according to V. A. Sukhomlinsky, should also be mastered by a teacher: be able to put yourself in the child’s place, understand his feelings and experiences, be sensitive to children’s problems and support them in difficult moments. According to V. A. Sukhomlinsky, in order to effectively perform a social function, a teacher needs to master the ability to create, rally and lead a team of students. He should be able to create an atmosphere of friendship, mutual assistance and cooperation in a group of children; be able to prevent and resolve conflicts. And, of course, in order to lead a team, a teacher must master communication skills: be able to express their thoughts clearly and clearly, listen and hear children, and have a conversation. The scientist wrote that touching a child’s heart should be gentle. Of particular importance in the professional activity of V. A. Sukhomlinsky emphasized cooperation with the pupil’s family, which undoubtedly requires the teacher to have a high level of communication culture with family members in order to involve them in the life of the children’s collective and achieve the best results in solving educational tasks [4; 5].

So, the analysis of the legacy of classical teachers made it possible to identify a number of conditions for successful professional activity of a teacher, which, in our opinion, can be used in clarifying the concept of socio-informational competence of a future preschool teacher and to outline ways to solve this problem in modern conditions of higher education institutions. The conditions for successful professional activity of an educator include: continuous development of personal qualities based on a traditional spiritual and moral value system; regular reflexive activity; reading literature and observing your students, which allows you to increase your intellectual level, expand your knowledge of a person as a subject of education, find effective pedagogical tools for each pupil and anticipate the results of their actions; mastering the art of communication and cooperation with all participants in the educational process; mastering organizational and managerial skills.

Thus, we will define the socio-informational competence of a future preschool teacher as a component of professional competence, an integrated dynamic education that includes a system of socio-pedagogical and socio-psychological knowledge, values, personal qualities, skills for mobile information acquisition, analysis, and effective use in social and professional settings based on legal and professional standards, moral standards of modern society and professional community, providing high-quality pedagogical service, taking into account the peculiarities of the development of preschool children.

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ON THE ISSUE OF DISCURSIVE SPACE IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation. *The article highlights the issues of «intercultural communication», which is one of the basic elements not only in philosophy, but also in pedagogy and psychology, which expands the study of the conceptsphere of the language personality of communicants in the realities of the discursive space of the multicultural world. Intercultural communication is a set of theoretical knowledge and practical skills that allow it to effectively use its mental, physical, and personal qualities to effectively solve communication problems in a foreign language environment.*

Keywords: *culture, discourse, intercultural communication, multicultural world, communicants, linguoculturolog.*

The radical changes in the life of modern Russian society, the degree of its development, the processes of globalization and integration, the constant expansion of the spheres of international and interethnic communication clearly show that the further development of mankind is possible only in the context of a dialogue between representatives of different national, cultural and religious communities who are able to understand and accept another culture as equivalent to their native culture. The modern world is characterized by a tendency to expand and deepen international contacts in various spheres of economic, socio-political, social and cultural life. This determines the need to address the problems of intercultural communication. It should be noted that when there is a mutual interest of representatives of different cultures in each other, communicants are not familiar enough with representatives of another culture, with the peculiarities of the communicative behavior of representatives of another linguistic and cultural community. In this regard, scientific research is becoming particularly relevant, which is focused a) on finding ways to increase the effectiveness of studying the world and culture of people who speak a particular language; b) on overcoming the cultural barrier created by the national peculiarities of the cultures of communicants; c) on

teaching the dialogue of cultures (G. M. Andreeva, V. V. Vorobyov, D. V. Gudkov, I. B. Ignatova, M. V. Clarin, N. V. Kuzmina, E. P. Orlova, Yu. E. Prokhorov, S. M. Andreeva, L. F. Svoikina, V. P. Furmanova, L. I. Kharchenkova, A. M. Andreeva etc.), i.e. on the formation of intercultural communication of tolerant personality of communicants. Intercultural communication at the present stage of integration of educational systems is considered as the leading personal and professional characteristic of a modern specialist, including a foreign one. Being an integrative concept in its essence, intercultural communication has become a source of interaction and relationship between individuals and representatives of various socio-cultural communities (B. G. Ananyev, Z. A. Vasilyeva, V. V. Vorobyov, I. A. Zimnaya, I. B. Ignatova, V. S. Ilyina, V. V. Krasnykh, E. S. Kubryakova, S. M. Andreeva etc.). Intercultural communication enriching national cultures is an ambiguous phenomenon. It can contribute to the creation of a secondary linguistic personality of communicants, removing the «friend-foe» contradiction, but it can also be an instrument of cultural expansion, oppressing another culture. Therefore, any communication between representatives of different peoples and cultures requires special knowledge and skills [4]. The process of forming intercultural communication involves, first of all, the analysis of the concept of «culture». The origin of the term «culture» has been considered in the works of many domestic and foreign authors (Ts. Arzakanyan, S. A. Artanovsky, M. Weber, E. Giddens, M. S. Kagan, A. F. Losev, Yu. M. Lotman, E. S. Markarian, N. S. Rozov, etc.). Initially, this term meant «cultivation and processing lands». Later, in Ancient Rome, culture meant that which was created by man, not by nature (A. P. Sadokhin). In the Philosophical Encyclopedia, culture is defined as «a specific way of organizing and developing life, represented in the products of material and spiritual labor, in a system of social norms and institutions, in spiritual values, in the totality of people's relations to nature, to each other and to themselves» [7, p. 292]. Based on this definition, it can be said that the core of culture is human activity which is determined by a system of various relationships and inherent values. The word «culture» appeared in Russian in the middle of the 19th century. For the first time the term is found in N. Kirillov's Pocket Dictionary of Foreign Words. V. I. Dahl gives two definitions of this concept.: 1) processing and care, cultivation, cultivation; 2) education, mental and moral [1, p.217]. D. N. Ushakov interprets this concept as «a set of human achievements in the subordination of nature, technology, education, and the social order» [6]. In modern humanities, the concept of «culture» is one of the fundamental ones. Naturally, it is central to intercultural communication. This concept, like no other, has many semantic shades and is used in different contexts. Such phrases as «culture of behavior», «culture of communication», «culture of feelings», etc. are already familiar to us. In common usage, the term «culture» serves as an evaluative concept and

expresses a certain set of personality traits of a person, which it would be more accurate to call not culture, but culture. Modern research on the definitions of culture has shown a huge, increasing interest in this concept. Thus, according to the calculations of American cultural anthropologists A. Kroeber and K. Klakhon, from 1871 to 1919, seven definitions of culture were given by various sciences, from 1920 to 1950 their number increased to 150. Kroeber and Klakhon divided all these definitions into 6 classes (types):

1. Descriptive definitions that interpret culture as the sum of all human activities, customs, and beliefs.

2. Historical definitions that connect culture with traditions and the social heritage of society.

3. Normative definitions that consider culture as a set of norms and rules that organize human behavior.

4. Psychological definitions, according to which culture is a set of forms of acquired behavior that arise as a result of adaptation and cultural adaptation of a person to the surrounding living conditions [10].

5. Structural definitions that represent culture in the form of various kinds of models or a single system of interrelated phenomena.

6. Genetic definitions based on the understanding of culture as a result of the adaptation of human groups to their environment.

This diversity of definitions, interpretations, and interpretations is due to the fact that culture is an extremely complex and multifaceted phenomenon that expresses all aspects of human existence. It includes everything that is created by the human mind and hands. In this regard, culture is studied by a number of sciences: semiotics, sociology, history, anthropology, axiology, linguistics, ethnology, etc. Each of these sciences identifies one of its sides or one of its parts as the subject of its study, approaches its study with its own methods and methods, while formulating its own understanding and definition of culture. In everyday life, the concept of «culture» is used in at least three meanings. Firstly, culture refers to a separate sphere of society's life, which exists in the form of a system of institutions and organizations engaged in the production and dissemination of spiritual values (societies, clubs, theaters, museums, etc.). Secondly, culture refers to a set of values and norms inherent in a large social group, community, people, or nations (elite culture, Russian culture, youth culture, etc.). Thirdly, culture is interpreted as an expression of a high level of human achievement in any activity (culture of everyday life, a cultured person in the sense of «well-mannered and educated», etc.). Very often, ideas about culture are often reduced to its identification with artistic culture (art) or with the education and upbringing of a person. However, the most widespread everyday meaning of the concept of «culture» is its understanding as a set of material objects, objects, ideas, images created by man throughout his history. In this interpretation, culture

appears as the sum of all the achievements of mankind, as a «second nature» created by man himself, forming the human world itself, unlike wild nature. This is precisely the understanding of culture that was formulated by Kroeber and Klakhon, who believed that culture consists of expressed and hidden patterns of thinking and behavior that are a specific, isolating achievement of human communities, embodied in symbols through which they are perceived and transmitted from person to person and from generation to generation. It should be noted that there are more than 500 definitions of this term in the scientific literature, meaning such generally accepted concepts as creative abilities of a person, understanding of works of art, knowledge and mastery of a foreign language, morality, aesthetic education, etc. Due to the variety of definitions, a number of scientists consider it necessary to classify the concept of «culture»:

— culture as an artificial world created by society, i.e. a set of material and spiritual values that are the cause and condition of society's existence (M. Weber, E. Giddens, N. S. Rozov, P. A. Sorokin, etc.);

— culture as a social organism developing according to its own laws (values, norms and rules, needs (N. Danilevsky, A. Toynbee, O. Spengler, etc.);

— culture as a way of transmitting social experience in the form of information contained in cultural texts, customs, traditions, etc. (R. Brislin, K. Levi-Strauss, A. F. Losev, Yu. M. Lotman, etc.);

— culture as a set of qualities formed in the process of obtaining educational experience (R. V. Brislin, G. Hofstede, etc.).

The most commonly used concept is culture as a set of material, spiritual and social values created by man throughout his history. It should be noted that the basis of the existence of the modern world is the diversity of cultures that are in constant interrelation and interaction, i.e. there is a process of integration of cultures of different ethnic groups. At the same time, the language is the carrier of culture. The role of the interaction of language and culture in the communication process has been the subject of research by many scientists since the 19th century. and to the present (S. A. Artanovsky, F. Boas, G. A. Brutyan, D. Vico, I. Herder, V. Humboldt, I. B. Ignatova, S. M. Andreeva, E. S. Markarian, E. Sepir, S. G. Ter — Minasova, B. Whorf, etc.).

Cultural anthropology considers culture as a product of people's joint life activity, a system of coordinated ways of their collective existence, ordered norms and rules for meeting group and individual needs, etc. It must be said that long-term cohabitation of groups of people in the same territory, their collective economic activities, defense against attacks form their common worldview, a unified way of life, manner communication, clothing style, cooking specifics, etc. And as a result of these processes, there is an independent cultural system, which is commonly called the ethnic culture of a given people, the core of which is a set of «rules of the game» adopted in the process of their collective existence. Unlike human

biological properties, they are not inherited genetically, but are absorbed only by learning. For this reason, it becomes impossible to have a single universal culture that unites all people on Earth. Thus, despite its obvious reality, culture appears to be an abstract concept in a sense, because in reality it exists only in the form of many cultures of different eras and regions, and within these epochs — in the form of cultures of individual countries and peoples, which are also commonly referred to as local and ethnic cultures [2]. The presence of local cultures is a natural form of existence of the entire human culture as a whole. Due to the interaction of local and ethnic cultures, a communication system arises, various styles and types of behavior, value orientations are supported, and their ethnic identity is preserved. This communication proceeds both through mutual clarification of relations, strife, conflicts, and through mutual adaptation and understanding of the cultural identity of neighbors. As a rule, the nature of intercultural contacts is determined by the degree of proximity and kinship of the interacting cultures. The fact is that some of the local cultures are similar to each other due to their genetic kinship and the similarity of the conditions of their origin. Other cultures differ from each other as much as the living conditions of the peoples who gave rise to these cultures differ. Each culture embodies a specific experience of the social practice of a particular historical community. And this experience gives each culture unique features, defines its uniqueness. The uniqueness of any culture is completed in the cultural picture of the world, which is gradually formed in the process of the emergence and existence of the culture itself. The cultural picture of the world is the result of the fact that in different cultures people perceive, feel and experience the world in their own way and thereby create their own unique image of the world, an idea of the world, called the «picture of the world». The cultural picture of the world is a set of rational knowledge and ideas about the values, norms, mores, and mentality of one's own culture and the cultures of other nations. This knowledge and understanding gives the culture of each nation an identity, which makes it possible to distinguish one culture from another. When representatives of two different cultures begin to communicate, we are talking about intercultural communication, the positive result of which depends on the degree and depth of mutual understanding between the participants of communication belonging to different national cultures. It should be said that the very concept of intercultural communication is ambiguously understood in the scientific literature. American scientists G. Treiger and E. Hall understand intercultural communication as an ideal goal that a person strives for in the process of effective adaptation to the world around them. This was one of the first interpretations of the concept of «intercultural communication». According to V. P. Furmanova, intercultural communication is considered as a dialogue of cultures, which is «a way of universal communication that encompasses the exchange of information and cultural values in the context of interethnic communication»

[6, p.38]. Based on the psychological positions of B. G. Ananyev, L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev, A. A. Leontiev, S. L. Rubinstein, and others, V. P. Furmanova identified the following main characteristics of intercultural communication: 1) the interaction of cultures that takes place in a certain space and time, in which culture is considered as a generic concept, cultural contacts take on various forms and find their expression in contact, mutual relations and dialogue.; 2) the interaction of cultures, in the process of which they enter into a dialogue and their actualization takes place, which consists in the manifestation of the universal and specific of each culture as a system; 3) the interaction of cultures, which receives its exteriorization through language and verbal content, creating a specific picture of the world [8].

With this approach, intercultural communication is considered as one of the components of the general culture of the linguistic personality of communicants, which is a set of theoretical knowledge and practical skills that allow her to effectively use her mental, physical, and personal qualities to effectively solve communication problems in a foreign cultural language environment. From our point of view, this definition reflects the essence of intercultural communication, which is formed by communicants. The process of forming intercultural communication also requires taking into account the abilities and characteristics of a person that determine the creation and perception of speech utterances (dialogical, monologue) in Russian, in which a person reveals his communicative abilities and properties [8]. Summing up the above, it is necessary to say that intercultural communication at the present stage of integration of educational systems is considered as the leading personal and professional characteristic of a modern specialist, including a foreign one. Being an integrative concept in its essence, intercultural communication is a source of transformation of the interaction and relationship of an individual with representatives of various socio-cultural communities. The interaction of three important components is traced in its content.: a) language as a means of cognitive and educational activity of a communicant's personality; b) culture that conveys the features of socio-historical conditions using language as a special semiotic unit; c) personality formed in the course of educational and social activities (G. N. Bogin, V. V. Vorobyov, I. A. Zimnaya, I. B. Ignatova, Yu. N. Karaulov, E. S. Kubryakova, S. M. Andreeva, L. F. Svoikina, and others). Thus, intercultural communication should be considered as a multifunctional phenomenon, including, firstly, knowledge of norms, principles, requirements of general humanistic ethics, the ability to translate them into the plane of intercultural relations; secondly, the education of specific qualities; the ability to empathy, empathy and self-esteem (G. N. Volkov, Z. G. Hasanov, T. N. Petrova and others); all these are extralinguistic parameters that determine the choice and implementation of a particular type of discourse. The very characteristics of discourse (the desire for cooperation, the reliability of information, the consistency of

utterance, clarity in wording, informativeness) determine discursive competence, the formation of which is one of the goals of learning.

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FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE: GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN ROBOTICS EDUCATION USING THE EXAMPLE OF ALL-RUSSIAN CHILDREN'S CENTER "ORLYONOK"»

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis and systematization of pedagogical experience in applying game technologies in the educational process of the Children's Innovation Center of Aviation and Cosmonautics (DICAIK) at the All-Russian Children's Center "Orlyonok." The research is based on theoretical provisions of modern pedagogy and methods of game-based learning, supported by practical developments. Special attention is given to the specifics of using game technologies to create an optimal educational environment, unleash students' creative potential, and develop skills for collective interaction, which, in turn, contributes to improved subject-specific outcomes in robotics education.*

Keywords: *game technologies, pedagogical activity, "Orlyonok" All-Russian Children's Center, educational process, robotics, STEM education, project-based activity.*

Introduction

The integration of game technologies into the educational process, particularly in rapidly developing fields such as robotics, addresses a critical need for engaging and effective teaching methodologies. In the contemporary educational landscape, maintaining student interest and ensuring a deep understanding of complex technical disciplines is increasingly challenging. In this context, game-based approaches serve as a tool for improving subject-specific outcomes and stimulating cognitive interest. The relevance of this research is underscored by the growing demand for specialists in STEM education and the recognized potential of gamification to transform technical learning.

The purpose of this article is to systematize the practical experience of applying game technologies at the “Orlyonok” All-Russian Children’s Center. Based on an analysis of additional general development educational programs (hereinafter — programs) implemented during 2023–2025, factors contributing to the effectiveness of game-based methods in the pedagogical process have been identified, and their potential for achieving educational and upbringing goals has been demonstrated. The paper describes specific games and their organizational methods, as applied in working with children of various age categories.

Game technologies represent an integral component of modern pedagogical approaches. According to the nature of the pedagogical process, games can be classified into the following groups: a) educational, training, control, and generalizing; b) cognitive, upbringing, developmental; c) reproductive, productive, creative; d) communicative, diagnostic, career-guidance, psychotechnical. Within the framework of PROGRAMS implementation at DICAİK, “Orlyonok,” the following types of games are applied:

- Business games;
- Simulation games;
- Role-playing games;
- Board games.

Examples of how each of these game types is used in technically oriented classes will be presented below.

Business Game

Successful experience in applying the business game format was gained during the implementation of the PROGRAMS “Engineering Profile Squad.” Within this program, teenagers learn about the automation of production processes through robotics. In the second session, they are tasked with generating ideas for an automated production line, which will subsequently be assembled by a group (16 people). For this purpose, work is organized in mini-groups (4 people each). The business game is conducted in several stages.

Stage 1: “Brainstorming.” Each mini-group generates an idea for an automated production line within 10 minutes, using the brainstorming methodology. At this stage, a key competence of a design engineer — “Idea Generation” — is acquired.

Stage 2: “Presentation of Mini-Group Work Results.” This stage involves presentations by mini-groups. Each mini-group briefly presents its idea for an automated line, describing:

- The main process with its working result;
- 4 auxiliary processes that will lead to the desired outcome;
- Robots that can be developed from the constructor set to simulate all necessary processes.

Stage 3: “Group Discussion, Argumentative Statements, Open Voting.” At this stage, active participation in the discussion and formulation of ideas takes place. A common concept for the automated line is formed for the entire group, the result of which is presented in the form of a final table detailing the processes.

At the second and third stages, a design engineer’s competence, “Argumentative Selection of Optimal Solutions,” is acquired.

Stage 4: “Development of Technical Specifications for the Automated Line.” This stage involves active participation in the formation of technical specifications and the adjustment of the table with a detailed description of all processes.

Following this business game, the assembly of robots necessary for the line begins. Each mini-group constructs and programs one robot, which performs a specific functional load in the overall automation of the chosen production process.

Generating an idea for a project in the business game format offers several advantages and positively influences the outcome for several reasons:

1. A business game, unlike a traditional pedagogical assignment, provides participants with a platform for independent idea generation and analysis of various solutions. This promotes deep immersion in design and engineering tasks, as well as stimulates creative thinking, allowing for the development of unique and innovative solutions for automated production lines.

2. Providing students with the opportunity to independently choose the direction of a project significantly increases their engagement and responsibility for the final outcome. Guided by their own ideas and interests, students become more actively involved in the process of assembling and programming robots, as they are implementing their own vision.

3. During the business game, participants acquire skills in group work, exchanging opinions, argumentatively defending their own ideas, and finding compromises, which are an integral part of real engineering activity. Unlike situations where an educator offers a ready-made project, this method contributes to the formation of students’ communicative competencies and the ability to work in a team to achieve a common goal. The skills acquired through such game-based activities will be significant in both the professional and daily lives of students.

Simulation Game

The entire educational program “Engineering Profile Squad” is implemented in a simulation game format. The following game elements of a simulative nature can be briefly highlighted.

Pre-game preparation and project immersion:

1. Introduction and game objectives. Students are presented with the goals and objectives of the simulation game, as well as the context in which the game activity

will unfold. A storyline is introduced, involving the creation of an assembly line at a manufacturing enterprise.

2. Basic training. Participants become familiar with the theoretical foundations of robotics, automated systems, principles of production line operation, and the construction sets used.

3. Role distribution. Each participant receives a role in accordance with the simulation model (engineer, designer, operator, project manager, etc.), which contributes to the acquisition of various competencies necessary for an engineering profession.

Game process:

1. Project concept. Participants develop the concept of an automated line (in the business game format mentioned previously), defining the requirements and capabilities of the constructor set used for its creation.

2. Design. Mini-groups design their own variants of the automated line, distributing tasks and creating prototypes of individual modules.

3. Strategic planning and management. Participants plan work stages and allocate resources, simulating real production processes.

4. Assembly and testing. Participants assemble models of robot modules for the line, conducting their testing and acquiring, in a game-based format, the competencies necessary for a design engineer.

5. Optimization and adjustment. In case of discrepancies with requirements or defects, problem identification and elimination are carried out, along with the optimization of production processes on the line.

6. Presentation and analytics. Teams present the results of their projects, analyze successful solutions and possible errors, and evaluate the efficiency of the line's operation and the nature of their collective interaction within the group.

Reflection and analysis:

1. Discussion and reflection. An analysis of the game process and results is conducted, discussing role strategies, adopted decisions, and behavior in non-standard situations.

2. Feedback and evaluation. Participants and educators provide mutual feedback, evaluating each other's contribution to the overall project.

3. Formation of knowledge, skills, and practical abilities. Participants transform the experience gained during the game into stable knowledge and skills applicable to real projects.

The simulation game format allows participants of the engineering profile squad not only to theoretically study the principles of automated lines and robots but also to practically master the process of their creation from scratch, ensuring full

immersion in a professional environment and the development of comprehensive skills useful for a future engineering career.

Role-Playing Games

The process of role-playing games is most vividly implemented in the PROGRAMS “Robots Guarding the Ecology of the Sea.”

The fourteen-hour PROGRAMS “Robots Guarding the Ecology of the Sea” is a competition of group scientific projects, developed at the intersection of актуальные fields: ecology and robotics. Over 14 academic hours, students study the environmental problems of the Black Sea, determine which of them could be solved with the help of modern robots. Then teams, using educational constructor kits, assemble and program a robot to solve the posed problem.

During the implementation of this project, two key aspects stand out. Firstly, students work in teams, which requires assistance in defining roles and guiding each participant in their research. Secondly, the overall teamwork on the project is organized in such a way that team members can prepare their part of the report for project defense and master the skill of assembling and programming robots.

Within the project, the following roles are defined:

— Chief Researcher — responsible for investigating the environmental problem.

— Chief Designer — coordinates the group’s work on robot assembly.

— Chief Programmer — coordinates the group’s work on robot programming.

— Technician — coordinates the group’s work on the testing ground during robot demonstration.

Each role has its specific place in the overall report during project defense. Organizing the work for preparation for defense promotes the continuity of the robot assembly process. For example, while the chief researcher studies the problem and prepares their slide for the project presentation, the rest of the team is engaged in assembling and programming the robot. Then interaction with the chief designers takes place, while the scientific consultant can participate in the assembly. Thus, specialization does not hinder the acquisition of necessary competencies, and the skill of assembling and programming is mastered by all participants equally.

During project defense, each participant presents according to their chosen role, which ensures everyone’s involvement and contributes to the formation of a sense of significance of their own contribution to achieving the overall result.

Board Games

Educators of additional education at DICAİK, “Orlyonok,” use board games in robotics classes to enhance understanding and reinforce learning material through the practical application of theoretical knowledge in a playful manner. Below is

a description of the experience using two types of board games: “Robolotto” and “Robo-Puzzle: 7 Worlds of Robots.”

“Robolotto”

Game Goal: To be the first to collect all EV3 constructor parts and types of gears used in robotics on one’s game card.

Game Set (developed by DICAİK educator E. L. Putrenok) includes:

- Game cards with a random distribution of images of EV3 constructor parts and types of gears. Each card contains 8 elements (tires, wheels, gears, motors, etc.).
- Separate token cards, on which the correct names of the same parts, components, and gears as on the main cards are depicted and signed.
- Descriptions of parts and gears that can be used as teaching material or for discussion after the game.

The game facilitates rapid acquisition and retention of various EV3 robot components and the principles of mechanism operation, making learning interactive and engaging. Experience has shown that for students to learn the names of constructor parts in a traditional format, they would need to dedicate 10–15 minutes in each of 7 sessions to pass a final test. Using the “Robolotto” game for memorizing part names requires only a brief explanation of the principle and a 10-minute “warm-up” at the beginning of the first two sessions for students to fully grasp the part names.

“Robo-Puzzle: 7 Worlds of Robots”

Game Goal: To familiarize children with the classification of robots.

This game set includes 7 puzzles, each dedicated to a specific type of robot: industrial robots, research robots, social robots, combat robots, medical robots, domestic robots, bionic robots.

This game is the first round of the “PRO-Robots Board Game Tournament” cycle but can also be used independently. This development by E. L. Putrenok, an additional education educator at DICAİK, “Orlyonok,” won 3rd place at the II All-Russian Board Game Competition in 2023.

Throughout the period 2022–2025, the application of game technologies in the educational programs of the “Orlyonok” All-Russian Children’s Center demonstrated significant and measurable results, confirming their effectiveness in improving academic performance in the field of robotics.

Within the PROGRAMS “Robots Guarding the Ecology of the Black Sea,” over 20 scientific project competitions were organized, involving about 250 students. The program received high praise from participants and took 3rd place in the nomination “Best Program in the Field of Environmental Education, implemented in 2022 in organizations for children’s recreation and rehabilitation” at the X All-Russian Open

Competition of Programs and Methodological Materials of Children's Recreation and Rehabilitation Organizations.

The board game "7 Worlds of Robots" was regularly used in introductory sessions ("educational samples") to immerse participants in the field of robotics. Over a two-year period, more than 150 such sessions were conducted, with over 1750 people participating. Approximately one-third of these sessions included the use of the "7 Worlds of Robots" game. Statistical analysis of survey data and practical task performance evaluations revealed that students who played "7 Worlds of Robots" demonstrated, on average, 7% better subject-specific results compared to those who did not use the game. This underscores the game's effectiveness in improving the understanding and practical application of robotics concepts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we would like to present generalized findings on the significance of game technologies for enhancing the quality of pedagogical activity.

Game technologies contribute to increased student motivation and engagement, transforming the learning process into an exciting and interactive activity. This is particularly crucial in technical disciplines where practical application and a deep understanding of complex concepts are critically important.

The integration of game technologies into the educational process should be carried out considering the age and individual characteristics of students. The choice of games should be based on the specifics of the discipline being mastered. For example, for robotics, it is recommended to use games that develop logical and critical thinking, facilitate comprehension, and reinforce skills in programming, assembly, and design.

Furthermore, continued research into the impact of game technologies on the development of specific skills in robotics and programming is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of various types of games in facilitating the mastery of complex course aspects and their influence on long-term retention of material.

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RESTORATION OF STATEHOOD OF THE REPRESSED PEOPLES

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Abstract. *The text examines the process of restoring statehood to the repressed peoples of Southern Russia (Chechens, Ingush, Balkars, Karachays, Kalmyks) in the post-war period. The key stages of rehabilitation are analyzed: from the initial relaxation of the special settlement regime in 1953–1955, prior to the adoption in 1956–1957, of decisions concerning the restoration of their national autonomies. The political prerequisites for rehabilitation are outlined, including the condemnation of the cult of personality at the 20th CPSU Congress and the role of closed reports by the USSR leadership. The principal normative legal acts (resolutions of the CPSU Central Committee, decrees of the USSR Supreme Soviet) initiating the return of peoples to their historical territories are presented. The challenges of implementing rehabilitation are considered separately: resistance from regional authorities, issues with resettling former territories, and shortages of resources for accommodating returning families. Half-measures were evident — despite the restoration of autonomies, political charges against the peoples were not lifted.*

Keywords: *deportation, rehabilitation, special settlers, national autonomy, North Caucasus, 20th Congress of the CPSU, restorative justice.*

During the ‘thaw’ period following the death of I. V. Stalin, the socio-political situation in the USSR changed, positively impacting the status of the repressed peoples. State bodies began developing new approaches to resolving this issue, arguing that the grounds for the deportations had lost their relevance.

In April 1953, a group of high-ranking officials (M. Suslov, P. Pospelov, K. Gorshenin, A. Shelepin, A. Gorkin) prepared an analytical note for G. M. Malenkov. It proposed creating an expert group to assess the advisability of maintaining legal restrictions concerning the repressed peoples.

Restrictions were imposed by the resolutions of the USSR Council of People’s Commissars on January 8, 1945, and the USSR Council of Ministers on November 24, 1948. The note stated that within 10 years after the resettlement of Germans,

Karachays, Chechens, Ingush, Balkars, Kalmyks, and Crimean Tatars, most of them found employment (in enterprises, state farms, and collective farms) but still faced strict restrictions on movement. The authors concluded that the need for the previous restrictions had ceased [1]. In 1954–1955, the Council of Ministers of the USSR and the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR adopted a series of normative legal acts abolishing certain restrictions on special settlers. Although the government measures were limited in scope, living conditions improved for certain categories: in 1955, they began to be issued passports and were conscripted into military service, which facilitated political integration [2, p.36].

After the visit of the FRG Chancellor K. A decree was issued in the USSR lifting restrictions on Russian Germans. This triggered a wave of appeals from other deported peoples seeking a similar lifting of the special regime.

The 20th Congress of the CPSU (February 1956) was decisive for the fate of the repressed peoples. Before its opening, the CPSU Central Committee Presidium approved a closed report by N. S. Khrushchev's 'On the cult of personality and its consequences' [3, p.89].

The report was based on materials about Stalin's crimes, prepared by a commission headed by the CPSU Central Committee secretary, academician P. N. Pospelov. The draft was circulated among members of the CPSU Central Committee Presidium for comments. A copy with corrections (provisionally called the 'Suslov copy') has been preserved, which was reviewed by at least three people. Among the annotations is a note before the section on the Leningrad affair: 'Violations of the national rights of peoples in 1943–1944: Karachays, Kalmyks, Ingush, and Chechens' [4, p. 111].

On February 25, during a closed session of the congress, Khrushchev read the report for four hours. He emphasized that Stalin held a monopoly on making key decisions and, for the first time, officially named him as the culprit of mass repressions.

The report shocked the participants of the congress. This predetermined the subsequent steps towards the liberation and rehabilitation of millions of people, removing the stigma of 'enemies of the people' from them.

The document also addressed the issue of the deportations of the peoples of the Caucasus. For the first time, the highest official of the country characterized the actions of Stalin and his entourage as genocide against entire peoples. It was also recognized that official propaganda created a distorted picture of reality.

The report also addressed specific issues, including Stalin's role during the war and the deportation of Caucasian peoples from their historic territories. For the first time, the highest official of the country assessed the actions of Stalin and his entourage as genocide against entire peoples. It was also acknowledged that official propaganda often portrayed a picture far from reality.

N. S. Khrushchev described the deportation of the Karachays, Kalmyks, Balkars, Chechens, and Ingush as a 'gross violation of the national policy of the Soviet state.'

He specifically emphasized the mass, indiscriminate nature of the deportation and refuted the argument of military necessity for such measures: by the time of the deportations, the turning point in the war had already been achieved in favor of the USSR.

The 20th Congress of the CPSU, condemning the practices of the cult of personality period, laid the foundation for the rehabilitation of repressed peoples. The Congress resolved to eliminate the legal and economic consequences tied to the forced relocation of people and to develop mechanisms for their return to their historical territories.

To make informed decisions, a comprehensive study of the conditions in the special settlement areas where the repressed peoples lived, as well as in the republics planned for their return, was required.

September 15, 1956. Head of the CPSU Central Committee Department for Party Organs in the Union Republics, E. Gromov reported to the Central Committee that the party and Soviet bodies of the Kabardino ASSR considered the return of the Balkars to the republic feasible.

In the memorandum of the Central Committee inspector S. Kolesnikov, who was handling the issue of restoring the autonomy of the Balkar people, outlined the position of the regional party committee bureau (early September 1956): the bureau members supported the return of the Balkars to the republic, but opposed restoring their national autonomy and the former name — Kabardino-Balkar ASSR [5, p. 114]. At the same time, an initiative group of Balkars sent appeals to the central authorities demanding the restoration of national autonomy in the form of the Kabardino-Balkarian ASSR as the only historically just solution. These proposals were taken into account during the subsequent national-state organization of the Balkar people.

The authorities of Dagestan, North Ossetia, and Stavropol Krai opposed the revision of borders in the North Caucasus. At the CPSU Central Committee meeting, leaders of regional party and Soviet organs generally agreed on the necessity of restoring Chechen-Ingush autonomy but proposed placing it in another region — far from the North Caucasus. However, they understood that such a decision was practically unfeasible: relocating the Chechens and Ingush to a different area would require the use of force.

Ultimately, the decision was made to restore autonomy on the historical territory of Chechen-Ingushetia, taking into account the interests of neighboring regions [6, p. 6].

October 16, 1956. A group of specialists from party and central Soviet departments prepared for A. I. Mikoyan the draft resolution of the CPSU Central Committee, summarizing the submitted proposals. On November 24, 1956, the draft was reviewed at a meeting of the Presidium of the CPSU Central Committee. On the same day, the CPSU Central Committee approved the resolution “On the restoration of the national autonomy of the Kalmyk, Karachay, Balkar, Chechen, and Ingush peoples.” The document condemned deportation as an act of arbitrariness

and lawlessness; · it emphasized that the mass expulsion of peoples was not dictated by military necessity and was a manifestation of the cult of personality; · it acknowledged that previously adopted measures were insufficient for the full rehabilitation of repressed peoples and the restoration of their equality; · it proclaimed the necessity of restoring the national autonomy of the specified peoples and ensuring their return to their historical territories.

Specifically on the Balkar question, it was stated: to transform the Kabardin ASSR into the Kabardino-Balkar ASSR within the RSFSR [7].

Thus, an important step was taken in the initiated process of rehabilitating the repressed peoples toward restoring the historically established ethnic map of the North Caucasus.

The leading role of the CPSU in public life — which the party not only declared but also consistently implemented — was also evident in the sphere of national relations. Impulses originating from the party were promptly implemented by both state and non-state bodies. The resolution of the CPSU Central Committee was binding on all authorities of the USSR and the RSFSR: it was adopted for strict enforcement, with adherence to all legislative procedures and a thorough examination of the local situation.

Measures for the creation of autonomous regions and republics, as well as for the return and resettlement of the Balkar, Karachay, and Kalmyk peoples, were planned for completion in 1957–1958. The population of the Ingush and Chechens was significantly larger, and the terms for their return were stipulated separately.

The CPSU Central Committee's resolution marked an important step toward rectifying the injustice against the repressed peoples: it provided for the restoration of their national autonomy and the establishment of necessary conditions for national and cultural revival [8]. Following its adoption, the rehabilitation process noticeably accelerated.

At the same time, the speaker did not address the Crimean Tatars, Turkic Meskhetians, and several other repressed peoples. Nevertheless, public condemnation of the mass repressions against the North Caucasian ethnic groups was highly significant: it prompted measures aimed at restoring justice.

Key steps taken by the Soviet government concerning the repressed peoples:

March 13, 1956. — a resolution that, for the first time, allowed certain special settlers to return to their native regions; · April and June 1956. — decrees by the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR lifting restrictions on special resettlement for the Kalmyks, Balkars, Chechens, Ingush, Karachays, and their family members.

At the same time, the decrees did not imply the full restoration of rights: · the return of property confiscated during the deportation was not provided for; a ban on residing in the places of initial exile remained in force.

Despite these limitations, people returned en masse to the Caucasus, driven by the desire to reclaim their homeland. In 1956, approximately 30,000 Chechens and Ingush and more than 4,500 Balkars returned; tens of thousands of Kalmyks and Karachays also returned. Local authorities were not always willing or ready to accept them everywhere, but the arrivals — mostly representatives of the former party and Soviet nomenclature, veterans of the Great Patriotic War, fighters for Soviet power, members of the intelligentsia, and simply desperate people wishing to live in their homeland — refused to leave the North Caucasus [9, p.12].

The persistence of the repressed peoples significantly influenced the prompt adoption of official decisions to restore their abolished statehood.

In the spring of 1956. Ninety-seven commissions were established under the Supreme Soviet of the USSR and the Presidium of the CPSU Central Committee to investigate the repressions. A government commission led by A. I. Mikoyan examined the accusations against the ‘punished peoples’ and summarized proposals submitted by individual citizens and collectives.

The deported peoples sent their representatives to Moscow to secure a meeting with the country’s leadership to discuss rehabilitation and the return to their historical territories. In the summer of 1956. Meetings took place: · N. S. Khrushchev received a delegation of Karachays; · A. I. Mikoyan conducted negotiations with representatives of the Chechens and Ingush; · L. I. Brezhnev met with a delegation of Balkars.

The negotiations addressed the prospects for the peoples’ return to the North Caucasus.

During the summer–autumn of 1956, in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, several commissions dispatched from Moscow operated to study the situation on the ground. The composition included staff from the CPSU Central Committee apparatus, the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, and the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

One of the commissions organized by the CPSU Central Committee investigated the living conditions of former special settlers (Balkars, Karachays, Chechens, and Ingush). Its conclusions stated that overall, the former special settlers did not face serious employment problems, although most of them were engaged in agriculture. The national culture of these peoples did not develop during the years of settlement but, on the contrary, declined; After the 20th Congress of the CPSU, the desire to return to the historical territories sharply intensified; Many persistently demanded the restoration of national autonomy. Proposals concerning the republics where they are currently located are met with a very negative attitude [5, p. 112]. The situation was complicated by the fact that territories previously inhabited by the deported peoples were densely populated by settlers from other regions. In some cases, those returning had to reclaim practically empty areas — destroyed settlements that had remained uninhabited since the deportations. Given these circumstances, attempts were made to persuade the Chechens and Ingush to agree to the creation of an autonomous

republic with its center in the city of Chimkent. The leadership of Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan, by contrast, demonstrated readiness to grant autonomy to the Balkars and Karachays. Party leaders of the Altai, Tyumen, and Novosibirsk regions opposed the return of the Kalmyks to their historical homeland. Their objections were driven by concerns about labor shortages in agriculture and several industrial sectors. The desire to keep the deported peoples in places of forced settlement was partly supported by central leadership. However, the firm determination of the people to return to their homeland proved stronger. As a result, work was carried out within the central authorities to develop legislative mechanisms: · restoration of national autonomy; · regulation of resettlement issues.

The main decisions in this area were made during the period 1957–1960. Decisions of the CPSU Central Committee were granted constitutional status in decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on January 9, 1957. The following decrees were issued: «On the transformation of the Kabardian ASSR into the Kabardino-Balkarian ASSR»; · “On the Restoration of the Chechen-Ingush ASSR within the RSFSR”; · “On the Formation of the Kalmyk Autonomous Oblast within the RSFSR”; · “On the Transformation of the Circassian Autonomous Oblast into the Karachay-Cherkess Autonomous Oblast” [1 0].

On the same day, the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the RSFSR adopted the relevant normative acts. February 11, 1957. These documents came into force, marking the beginning of the planned return of the deported peoples to their historical territories.

These decrees were of great importance for the Balkar, Karachay, Kalmyk, Chechen, and Ingush peoples: they ended the thirteen-year period of forced exile and opened the path to revival. At the same time, the documents’ texts lacked a legal and political assessment of the decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR from 1943–1944 concerning the deportations.

January 25, 1957. The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the USSR issued an order ‘On the right of residence and registration of Kalmyks, Balkars, Karachays, Chechens, Ingush, and their family members in their former places of residence.’

Specialized resettlement and labor recruitment departments were established to coordinate resettlement, placement, and employment.

In 1957–1959. The majority of Balkars returned to their homeland, but not all: according to the 1959 census, 34,100 Balkars lived in the republic out of the ethnic group’s 42,400 (9, p.31). In 1957–1959, returned · 20,514 Karachay families (73,442 people); 18,158 Kalmyk families (72,665 people). By 1959, Chechens and Ingush made up 41 % of the population of the Chechen-Ingush ASSR (11, p.190).

The return of the repressed peoples to their homeland was a significant event in the history of the USSR. It reflected the new leadership’s commitment to rectifying the errors of national policy and normalizing interethnic relations. N. S. Khrushchev

tasked all government bodies with giving priority to the rehabilitation of the deported peoples.

For their successful adaptation, it was necessary to resolve a complex of socio-economic, political, and interethnic problems. These tasks were addressed simultaneously at both the union and republican levels, as only coordinated actions could ensure a positive outcome.

The government and economic bodies of the RSFSR and the restored republics undertook extensive work to return the repressed peoples of the North Caucasus. The main directions of the authorities' activities were determined by the population's needs in housing, social infrastructure, and the production base of collective and state farms in 1957–1958. The Council of Ministers of the RSFSR adopted a series of resolutions on financing the program for the return and assistance of deported peoples. The documents defined the nature of rehabilitation measures covering various spheres of life. Within the framework of support for settlers, the following were provided: loans for construction of housing; financing of home repairs; funds for the purchase of livestock; support for education and healthcare.

For the creation of collective farms and state farms, loans were allocated through the Russian office of the Agricultural Bank. However, a significant portion of the allocated funds was misused. The reason was the absence, in the decrees of the Council of Ministers of the RSFSR, of clear obligations to monitor the expenditure of funds on the economic and domestic organization of the returning peoples.

Despite difficulties, the first years after returning to the homeland were marked by a general upsurge. People gradually settled down: education, healthcare, and cultural institutions were being restored. Representatives of the repressed peoples were incorporated into the work of state and party bodies. Literature and the press revived, and scientific activities were being established. By 1960, most of the primary tasks related to returning to their homeland had been resolved.

The attitudes of local authorities and the population toward the return of former special settlers varied. In Kabardino-Balkaria, Kalmykia, and Karachay-Cherkessia, the central government adhered to the main principles of state national policy, which facilitated a smoother integration process.

The restoration of nation-state entities in the North Caucasus was an important step in the rehabilitation of the deported peoples. The re-establishment of autonomies provided the foundation for the revival of ethnic groups and stimulated the development of their economies, cultures, and education systems.

At the same time, the state acts of 1956–1957 were of a limited nature. The political charges that served as the basis for the deportations were not officially lifted, leaving the rehabilitation process incomplete. From the mid-1960s, the rehabilitation process of the deported peoples was effectively suspended. Problems in the sphere of interethnic relations did not receive proper attention from the country's leadership

for a long time. Existing contradictions were concealed by official rhetoric about the friendship and brotherhood of the peoples of the USSR.

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, Russia underwent radical political changes culminating in the collapse of the Soviet system. The democratization course adopted during this period activated the process of rehabilitation of repressed peoples.

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POETRY OF RUSSIAN MODERN STYLE AND MUSIC

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the issue of the synthesis of the arts, which is so characteristic of the work of representatives of Russian modernism at various stages of its evolution. It highlights the original combination of tradition and innovation in the musical realization of the Silver Age poetics; and substantiates the reasons for the asynchrony in the developmental trajectories of poetic and musical arts in 20th-century Russian culture.*

Keywords: *Russian modernism, Silver Age, symbolism, syllabic music, alliteration, assonance, sound painting.*

Radical in its approach to life and art, modernism of the first decades of the twentieth century — in literature and dramatic theater, painting, and sculpture — sought to soar above reality, aiming to create something higher that transcended the limits of visible and audible space, stepping beyond the boundaries of the familiar, visible, and tangible... And could it have been otherwise in the visual arts — with the advent of photography, or on the dramatic stage — with the newborn cinematograph and its successes? Is any sculptural composition capable of competing with a museum wax figure in imitating nature? It should be noted that, at the turn of the century, vernisages and museums of this kind spread across the world with astonishing rapidity...

Music, in the contest between reality and invention, ‘stood apart’: being inherently non-specific and abstruse by nature, it was always meant to lie beyond the bounds of prose and direct everyday experience; She breathed symbolism and enigmas, mysticism and eternal ambiguity in every epoch. “Music begins where the word is powerless,” — this was reiterated at various times and in different forms by figures of the arts, from Heinrich Heine to Claude Debussy. Music as an art has no real interpretation and “expresses nothing except itself,” asserted I. Stravinsky, one of the heralds of musical modernism. 1)

It is unsurprising that during the Silver Age, alongside literature, it flourished luxuriantly and vividly, distinguished by originality and boldness of exploration;

At times, it ‘dominated’ among the other arts, for example, in ballet: the musical masterpieces of the renowned ‘Russian Seasons’ of S. Diaghilev guided the endeavors of decorators and innovations of choreographers, embodied in the artistry of outstanding male and female dancers. The ideas of the genius A. Scriabin — the standard-bearer among composers of the Silver Age — enabled the unification of music, word, and movement with a color score (it is known that the musical text of the poem **Prometheus**, 1909, included a line Luce).

Music was linked to literature of the first third of the century not only through semantic and aesthetic foundations but also through the very character of verbal expression — in words or sounds. Fragmentation and discontinuity of structures were evident both here and there — in contrast to the former linearity and strict logical coherence of the narrative. Extended, ‘ring-shaped’ melodies yielded to micro-thematism and an overall mosaic-like composition. The coloristic and refined timbral qualities of vocal compositions highlighted the specificity of modernist poetry, where the musicality of alliteration and assonance defined the meaning of what was expressed more than the conceptual verbal sequence. The melodic of the verse and the poetics of the melos merged into an inseparable unity, with each stylistic branch of literary modernism finding a response in the compositional sphere: the symbolism of A. Blok and Andrey Bely, and above all, K. Balmont, found a parallel in the explorations of A. Scriabin and his follower I. Vyshnegradsky; The dialogue of the futurists was embodied in the pair V. Mayakovsky — S. Prokofiev; the ideas of acmeism were close to both the experienced and authoritative A. Lyadov and the young I. Stravinsky (‘*Petrushka*,’ ‘*The Rite of Spring*,’ 1910s), who later gravitated toward imagism — in ‘*The Wedding*’ (1923), metaphorically reproducing the peasant wedding ritual in a hut with four pianos placed in the corners (as required by the author’s instructions).

Music, as an art, is both national and international simultaneously; the more ‘Russian’ it appeared on the world’s stages, the more it was liked and highly valued. It was established, blossomed, and took shape in the leading genres of the Golden 19th century, but during those years it barely penetrated beyond the Fatherland; it became known worldwide, simultaneously — in Europe and America — during the subsequent Silver Age. The brilliant emergence of Russian music undermined the perennial literature-centric concept of national culture; poetry, as in the past, no longer led the melody by the hand (once obedient, it was now ready to ‘buck’ with counter-accents, rhythms, and meter), and the narrative or play no longer dictated the structure of musical dramaturgy. The relationship between the senior and junior branches of native art was replaced during the era of modernism by parity between the verbal and musical spheres; Despite the wealth of prominent names in the literary world, among them there are few equals: in terms of superstar status — Sergei Rachmaninoff or Igor Stravinsky; in the magnitude of innovative

ideas — Alexander Scriabin; in popularity among audiences of all ages — Sergei Prokofiev; in demand on the contemporary theatrical stage — Alexander Glazunov, Nikolai Tcherepnin, and Boris Asafyev; in sacred circles — Sergei Taneyev and Alexander Gretchaninov, etc.

The Silver Age designated composer names not of the foremost, but of the literary echelon. Corresponding to him was also the circle of performing musicians, ranging from Leonid Sobinov and Fyodor Chaliapin to Vladimir Sofronitsky; in the ballet world, those years shone with a scattering of talents that astonished the world: Anna Pavlova, Mathilde Kschessinska, Tamara Karsavina, their partners, and choreographers Vaslav Nijinsky, Mikhail Fokin, Leonid Myasin, and others. French by origin, ballet in its homeland lost its strong standing, having shifted at the turn of the century into operetta and other entertainment genres — variety theatre and revue; it was precisely the Russian school and Russian music that preserved ballet as a full-fledged genre within the sphere of high art, eventually displacing the aging opera in its dynamic development. However, unlike the previous century, during those years she seldom referred to contemporary literary themes.

At the same time, modernist literature, as was later revealed, was destined to a ‘double life’ in music, and this phenomenon was associated not with fantastic projects and artists’ designs, but rather with the dramatic realities of a rapidly changing world.

It has long been observed that literary and musical paths, intertwining and intersecting, formed characteristic poetico-composer pairs peculiar to the Russian school. Already during the formation of the national school, in the Catherine era, the posters of the first domestic operas listed: A. Ablesimov — M. Sokolovsky, Ya. Knyazhnin — V. Pashkevich, N. Lvov — E. Fomin, etc. — playwright and musician, more arranger than composer, since the librettist directly indicated which number and from which collection of ‘folk songs with voices,’ widely published at that time, should be used as musical material in a new reinterpretation. At the dawn of the Romantic era, duets of equals came to prominence — tandems of renowned leaders in their fields: V. Zhukovsky and A. Verstovsky, who managed to set the poet’s ballads to music as organically as no one else did; the congenial duet of A. Pushkin and M. Glinka, unsurpassed not only in chamber vocal lyricism but also manifesting itself in opera (‘Ruslan and Lyudmila’); The tandem of M. Lermontov and A. Dargomyzhsky (romances), limited in quantity but exceptional in the depth of music’s immersion in the passionate and bitter words of the poet; N. Nekrasov and M. Mussorgsky, the natural school, the peasant accent in musical speech; the series can be easily extended...

The confident procession of pairs came to an end, and the ranks merged during the revolutionary years, which redirected the stylistics, content, and purpose of domestic art. The widespread emigration, which laid bare the St. Petersburg musical

world and was quite active in other regions, interrupted the development of the emerging creative partnerships (mentioned above); Prokofiev left Russia in 1918; six months earlier, Rachmaninoff had left. In 1920, Vyshnegradsky departed for Paris. Stravinsky, who had been shuttling between his homeland and abroad since the early 1910s, definitively chose the latter in 1914. In the 1920s, A. Glazunov left Petersburg and the conservatory entrusted to him. At that time was also taken the significant source of the future abundant flow of the Russian émigré.

In poetic-musical tandems, writers were usually the senior contemporaries of composers, who lagged behind them in age by approximately one generation. Thus, the composers born in the 1900s and coming of age in the 1920s and 1930s were expected to set to music the poems of A. Akhmatova, M. Tsvetaeva, B. Pasternak, O. Mandelstam, V. Mayakovsky, and their contemporaries; Fate, however, prepared for them other paths, far removed from the former ideals. That is why, for the most part, it was not the pre-revolutionary composers but those who came many years later — those who shaped the era of the Soviet cultural renaissance of the 1960s-1990s — who turned to literary modernism. Thus, within the musical sphere, the poetry and prose of the early twentieth century received a twofold response: swift and succinct from contemporaries, and later, rich and multifaceted from their artistic ‘grandchildren.’

The new era sought to understand and hear what had been expressed not merely half a century ago, but was born in a different world, entirely distinct from the Soviet epoch, yet still imprinted in the native word *мир* of the enigmatic Russian soul. Now, the poet and the composer were separated in history not by 5–7 years, but by fifty to seventy — the same span, but with zeros added...

The stylistic delta of Russian modernism at the beginning of the century revealed a multicolored musical cluster of directions — from late, or more precisely, ‘belated’ romanticism (S. Rachmaninoff and N. Medtner), academism (A. Glazunov), symbolism (A. Scriabin), and the Russian impressionism close to it in manner of writing (partly A. Lyadov, as well as A. Arensky)—to the futuristic experiments of the young S. Prokofiev and the modernist experiments of I. Stravinsky. This lush ‘bouquet’ was cut down at once and tightly bound by ideological shackles for many years.

Soviet composers, closely linked with socialist realism (during the central period of the century), marched precisely in step with contemporary poets; texts and music were often created synchronously, especially during the wartime era, which was rich in masterpieces of the song genre. The famous «Katyusha» by M. Blanter, set to verses by M. Isakovsky, united the efforts of contemporaneous authors. In the first days of the war, the poem *The Sacred War* signed by V. Lebedev-Kumach was published in newspapers; literally a few days later, a song of the same title by A. Alexandrov appeared. The poet A. Fatyanov, whose verses were set to music in hit melodies by V. Solovyov-Sedoy, was twelve years

younger than the composer. Often, musicians composed their songs even before the texts appeared; I. Dunaevsky, incidentally, acted this way more than once: his 'Wide is My Native Land...' was given a subtext a year and a half after its creation. Others followed his example.

Composers of the new era, born between the 1930s and 1950s, on the contrary, tended to maintain distance; they were less drawn to topicality and publicism than their senior colleagues, preferring distant predecessors to poets of their own generation. Around the names of A. Blok, S. Yesenin, A. Akhmatova, B. Pasternak, O. Mandelstam, V. Bryusov, Z. Gippius, and others, a dense musical field has emerged, moving Soviet poets of the last decades of the twentieth century to the periphery of the musical process, closer to mass culture. The modernism of the Silver Age was rejuvenated, came into contact with the musical avant-garde and the New Folklore Wave, and was perceived as entirely consonant with the current *fin de siècle*, interpreted differently — more thoroughly and vividly than at the beginning of the century. Along the paths of convergence between Russian poetry and music in the 20th century, two successive yet largely distinct periods emerged: the initial, direct INCARNATION of modernist literature in the music of contemporaries, and a future RETURN to the source, separated by decades.

The FIRST STAGE (1900–1920) possessed a significant and crucial advantage: it involved trusting, often friendly communication between composers and their contemporary poets, meaning that the semantic and philosophical foundation of the art was unified, and concerns for its future were equally urgent. The salvation of national music, as had been the case before, was perceived by many as lying in the strong embrace of literature. The undisputed leader of musical symbolism and an innovator — a pioneer of ideas, many of which remain unrealized even today — A. Scriabin, in his unique oeuvre, most vividly captured the artistic world of the Silver Age; however, no direct embodiment of literary texts is present in his legacy. The composer's domain was instrumental music (symphonies, sonatas, piano miniatures, etc.). Presumably, he was the only figure of the Russian school who did not undergo extensive study of romance (or choral) music. His exploration in vocal lyricism remained limited to a single piece: the romance 'I Would Like With a Beautiful Dream,' composed at the age of 19 to his own text. A poem by the composer himself forms the basis of the finale of the six-movement First Symphony with chorus (1900); his poetic voice also appears in the texts of the «Preliminary Action»; This is where the direct literary-musical parallels in Scriabin's legacy end. At the same time, the titles of his miniatures — «Strangeness», «Gloomy Flame», «Dreams», «Fragility», «Winged Poem», «Nuances», «Poem of Longing» — attest to a close affinity with poetry; Above all, the very world of the composer's music — mutable, elusive, impetuous, and anxious — as well as the gradual replacement of melodies with brief, aphoristic motifs, and of

complete musical ideas with hints and certain mysterious signs, attests to creative paths closely aligned with literary symbolism.

The Skryabinists, direct continuators of his ideas (the most prominent among them being I. Vyshnegradsky), were primarily associated with circles of the Russian Diaspora. One would think that it was precisely they — educated, free, talented, and often connected with the literary émigré milieu — who could embody Silver Age poetry adequately and multifariously, having received it firsthand; yet, different sentiments prevailed here. THERE, in the abandoned Russia, art seemed to matter no longer — and for a long time! HERE, in Paris, London, Warsaw, Berlin, San Francisco, and other émigré centers, the primary goal was preserving the accumulated heritage and passing the baton to future generations of musicians. To seek unexplored paths on unstable ground, transplanting the Russian word to the West — few were capable of this, and the initial attempts to compose music to the poetry of symbolist poets (in the pre-emigration period), as a rule, did not endure. Arthur Lourié, who was passionate in his youth about Vyacheslav Ivanov, Anna Akhmatova, Vladimir Mayakovsky, and A. Blok, abandoned the desire to set their works to music when he emigrated to Europe (and later, to America) in 1922. The realization of ideas for creating new instruments, and thus new methods of music recording, captivated Nikolai Obukhov and the aforementioned Ivan Vyshnegradsky; The tragic fate of yet another Skryabin follower (who remained in Russia), Nikolai Roslavets, led to the loss of many of his compositions. The Russian émigré Alexander Grechaninov (who left in 1925) created the vocal cycle **Twilight** (1913), which included poetry by A. Blok and K. Balmont; Abroad, his attention was primarily drawn to sacred genres: ‘I find consolation in composing sacred music...’.

THE SECOND PHASE (the last third of the 20th — early 21st century) naturally lost in music the sensation of the feverish pulse characteristic of the era torn by contradictions at the turn of the century. It was not so much the prophetic dimension of the literary word, nor its philosophical essence, but above all the unique sonic aura that particularly captivated musicians who grew up during the period of the ‘monochromatic’ mass song — initially children’s, then pioneer, followed by youth and student songs. During the period of the «Soviet musical renaissance» (as the era of the 1960s-1990s was termed in musicology), modernist poetry captivated with its exquisite sound painting, the subtlest hues, and intricate rhythmic patterns. A poem being read is the same music, the same refined melos long forgotten in social struggles; in the light beating of rhythms, sounds, and nuances, it closely approaches eighth notes, sixteenth notes, harmonies, and counterpoints. It was precisely the musicality — and above all, the musicality — of modernist poetry that attracted contemporary composers far more than the meaning of the words themselves, philosophical depth, or conceptual nuances. Compared to the stylistics

of early 20th-century interpreters, the priority of the ‘music within poetry’ has been clearly and precisely established.

‘It is so natural... there exists the mystery of poetry in its purest form.’ Phonic play, not reducible to a logical sequence. I fear deciphering the mystery... I do not know, perhaps I will face some accusations from literary scholars, but when I compose music to the poetry of my beloved poets... from our ‘Silver Age,’ — the sound always matters more to me than the meaning of individual words,” said one of the contemporary St. Petersburg composers who masterfully realized the Blok-style verse. 2) “You know, when my composition went on tour abroad — to Germany and Switzerland — the audience was given booklets with translations of the poems. But no one looked inside; I am convinced that in genuine vocal music the ‘bird language’ is crucial: the most subtle intonational inflections, rhythmic flexibility, cantilena of vowels, the fragmentation of clicking, rustling, and ringing consonants... Everything is determined by the music of the verse, the poetry of the melody, and not by the literal meaning of the text.” 3) They do not read but listen, as to a song, with a refined inner ear, to the poetry of modernist poets and other musicians of our time. Distinctive series of accents, The asymmetry and aperiodicity of their texts are reflected in the variable micrometers of vocal lines, polyrhythms and syncopations, and the irregularity of phrases and musical sentences in white verse. Syllabic poetry, which captivated Blok and his contemporaries, transformed into ‘syllabic music’, frequently found in contemporary compositional practice.

Modernist poetry, more than any other, offered a boundless field stretching to the horizon for exploration. Compared to the first stage, poetic preferences among musicians changed; Replacing the ‘king’ of the Silver Age favored by their predecessors — K. Balmont — was the undisputed leader in terms of the number of musical settings, Alexander Blok, along with Anna Akhmatova, Marina Tsvetaeva, and Boris Pasternak. The focus of interests and compositional preferences, as well as the artistic ideas themselves, noticeably shifted over the years, especially since the 21st century has provided a quite convincing response to the main, pressing questions faced by Silver Age artists. Let us turn to the characterization of individual stylistic currents of modernist poetry and their embodiment in music.

SYMBOLISM, represented in literature and distinctly marked in music by the four “B”s: Blok, Bryusov, Bunin, Balmont, as well as conditionally affiliated with them Andrey Bely, whose pseudonym begins rather with “A” than with “B” (although his real surname is Bugayev), resonated in the works of their contemporary composers with an unconditional priority accorded to Konstantin Balmont. The exquisitely exalted language of V. Bryusov attracted the attention of both the late romantic Nikolai Metner and the composers deeply rooted in the early Soviet era — Nikolai Myaskovsky and Sergei Prokofiev. A. Blok’s poetry was even more frequently embodied in music — albeit in the works of composers well known but

considered by twenty-first-century standards as secondary rather than of the ‘first rank’: Sergey Vasilenko, Boris Goltz, Alexander Gretchaninov, Myaskovsky himself, and Alexander Cherepnin. I. Bunin attracted the attention of the unequivocal genius — Sergey Rachmaninov, albeit only once; Balmont far outpaced everyone... Indeed, his own original poems were supported by skillful translations of foreign classics, often turning into romances and songs. It was Balmont who, in terms of musical demand, approached such frequently set Russian poets of the elegiac 19th century as A. Fet, F. Tyutchev, and even A. Pushkin himself. (Among the interpreters of Balmont’s poetry were creators from all artistic levels: the rationally minded Boris Asafiev, who combined the professions of musicologist and composer; the enthusiastic Antoniý Arensky; the simple and heartfelt Alexander Gretchaninov; the symphonist and master of large-scale genres Nikolay Myaskovsky; the scholar-polyphonist Sergey Taneyev; the lyricist with a genuinely Russian musical soul Sergey Rachmaninov; the classic of opera and ballet theater Sergey Prokofiev, who was rather indifferent to genres of chamber-vocal lyric; and Nikolay Cherepnin — overall, more than one hundred and fifty authors among 20th-century literary figures, simply a record!). The musical essence of Balmont’s poetry was never questioned by anyone, and the art of sounds always remained intimate and close to him.

FUTURISM — in many respects the polar opposite of symbolism — as a literary modernist movement in the creative duo ‘poet-composer’ was perfectly embodied in the tandem Vladimir Mayakovsky — Sergey Prokofiev. Their birth dates were separated by approximately two years. Both began their careers in pre-revolutionary Russia; both, in their youth, gained scandalous fame and an image as subverters of established norms. In their mature years, both the poet and the musician lived abroad for extended periods. Neither probably imagined that, in time, both would be declared ‘classics of the Soviet era.’ ‘To the chairman of the globe from the music section — the chairman of the globe from the poetry section, Prokofiev to Mayakovsky,’ read the dedicatory inscription to the composer, made by the poet in March 1918 on his poetry collection. In this ‘pair of chairmen,’ Prokofiev was clearly the subordinate both initially and subsequently. Bold and daring in his youth, inclined toward provocation, with a percussive approach to the piano and sharp rhythmic accents, the composer in his music was close to Mayakovsky’s direct, ‘chopped’ verse.

At the turning point of epochs in music, as in other arts, a characteristic tendency towards primitivism, simplicity, and purity becomes noticeable — a desire to erase from the musical ‘slate’ the multi-layered chords and complex counterpoints, freeing up space — though for what, as yet, remains unclear... but necessarily new themes, ideas, and images. In parallel to the precise — spare, graphic word of AKMEISM and the spot-on metaphor of IMAGISM, the music of the new era strives to shed professional armor, years of accumulated mastery, revealing the

essence... The composer closest to these movements, Igor Stravinsky, in fact had no such 'armor': he did not graduate from conservatories, began serious musical study hopelessly late — in his early twenties — and his musical education consisted of brief and irregular private lessons with N. Rimsky-Korsakov, which were more consultations than systematic 'studies'. Acmeism, whose proponents preferred to view the world directly and reproduce it as it is, was reflected in Stravinsky's early ballets, especially in **Petrushka**. The ideas of literary imagism were embodied in the interpretation of another ballet by the composer — **The Wedding**, which completed the composer's 'Russian period'. He repeatedly emphasized the parallels of his poetic intentions: 'My task was to create... something like a poem expressed in the language of music.'⁴) In his view, the musical and poetic word share the same foundation: the regularly accented meter of a musical composition corresponds to poetic meter, and repetitions in music, as well as corresponding cadences, serve as rhymes. On numerous occasions in his memoirs, Stravinsky stressed that his music is articulated through poetry. Thus, comparing his work **The Rake's Progress** with Schoenberg's **Expectation**, Stravinsky pointed out that the former is an 'opera in verse', while the latter is an 'opera in prose'.⁵) As it turned out, many others later followed the same musical path.

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PUBLIC ART IN THE DIGITAL ERA: INTERACTIVITY, PLACEMAKING, AND THE CONSTRUCTION OF SOCIAL IDENTITY

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Abstract. *The proliferation of digital technologies is fundamentally reshaping the forms and functions of public art. This paper examines recent digital public art initiatives across selected European and Chinese cities to explore how interactive art enhances public participation, redefines urban spatial experience, and contributes to the formation of social identity within multicultural environments. Findings suggest that digital public art not only expands artistic expression but also acts as a cultural catalyst, connecting individuals, communities, and urban landscapes. Its participatory nature offers new possibilities for the democratization and revitalization of public spaces.*

Keywords: *Digital Public Art; Public Participation; Placemaking; Social Identity; Interactive Art*

Introduction

Traditionally, public art has played a vital role in urban culture, often materializing as static installations such as sculptures and murals. In the contemporary digital age, however, public art is evolving toward greater interactivity, dynamism, and participatory engagement [1]. Europe, as a leader in both the theory and practice of public art, has witnessed the emergence of numerous projects that integrate digital media in cities like Berlin and Barcelona. These initiatives not only transform the visual and experiential fabric of urban environments but also redefine public interaction with art. This study investigates, through comparative case analysis, how digital public art facilitates public involvement, strengthens a sense of place, and supports the construction of social identity, offering theoretical and practical insights for the ongoing evolution of the field.

Research Methods

This research employs a mixed-method approach combining case study analysis with theoretical reflection. Six representative digital public art projects from Europe (e.g., the Netherlands’ “Light Cube,” the United Kingdom’s “The Wave”) and China (e.g., Shanghai’s “Digital Dunhuang,” Shenzhen’s “Light and Shadow Art Festival”) serve as primary cases. Methods include literature review, participatory observation, and semi-structured interviews with audiences and practitioners. The analytical framework integrates participatory art theory [2], placemaking theory [3], and social identity theory [4].

Results

1. Interactivity Deepens Public Engagement

Through the use of sensors, projections, augmented reality, and other interactive technologies, digital public art shifts audiences from passive spectators to co-creators. For example, “Light Cube” employs motion-sensing interfaces, enabling visitors to influence light patterns and narratives, thereby enhancing immersion and personal connection [5].

2. Reconceptualizing Place Through Art

By layering digital visuals, sound, and interactive elements onto physical locations, such projects imbue public spaces with renewed cultural and emotional resonance. “The Wave,” for instance, transforms a historical building façade into a dynamic storytelling medium, bridging past heritage with contemporary expression [6].

3. Fostering Social Identity in Multicultural Contexts

Digital public art often serves as a platform for cross-cultural dialogue and collective meaning-making. Shanghai’s “Digital Dunhuang” exhibition uses VR to make ancient murals accessible, fostering a shared sense of cultural heritage and identity among diverse audiences [7].

Discussion

The expansion of digital public art signals a convergence of artistic practice, technological innovation, and social engagement. While its interactive qualities can enhance aesthetic experience and civic learning [8], challenges remain — including technological dependency, sustainability concerns, and issues of digital inclusion. Moving forward, practitioners and policymakers should prioritize contextual relevance, technological accessibility, and meaningful community co-creation to ensure that such art remains substantive and socially impactful rather than merely technologically ornamental.

Conclusion

Digital public art represents a significant evolution in how art interacts with public life. By leveraging technology to encourage participation, it strengthens

connections between people and places and supports the formation of layered social identities. For artists, curators, and urban planners, the task ahead lies in thoughtfully integrating technological tools with artistic vision and social intentionality, guiding public art toward more inclusive, engaged, and culturally resonant futures.

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BAIKAL IS SO DIFFERENT IN THE VISUAL ARTS

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Abstract. *This article examines a natural object, Lake Baikal, which is depicted in landscape works by local artists in different ways: sometimes calm, sometimes stormy and rebellious. People living on its shores as an ancient deity who influences their entire lives perceive Baikal, as a living, spiritual being. Therefore, the works of the artists represent the lake very differently, unlike each other. This study is based on the paintings of the artist P. S. Panarin «Baikal», 1976 (it is located in the Regional budgetary institution «The State Art Museum of the Altai Territory») and the «Baikal Wave», 1959 (it is located in the «Chelyabinsk State Museum of Fine Arts», a regional state-funded cultural institution).*

Keywords: *natural landscape, Lake Baikal, wave, Eastern Siberia, landscape painters.*

The image of Lake Baikal does not lose its relevance, since when referring to the nature of his native land, the artist, in fact, refers to himself, to his origins and roots. Baikal is a very iconic and recognizable unique natural object. Artists can endlessly be inspired and draw on themes for creativity in the image of Baikal, which appears as a living, spiritual being with its own character, manners and mood. A meeting with Lake Baikal changes a person forever, leaving a deep mark on his soul. In modern, mostly digital reality, contemplation and depiction of nature fades into the background in the individual's worldview. Computers, smartphones, various fashionable gadgets, digital platforms replace everything for a modern person and there is no need to go to nature or go to a museum. However, it is communication with nature that maintains the balance of the past, present and future in a person, preserving his connection with his ancestors and roots. Despite

the rapidly developing modern world, the experience of previous generations is necessary for people to live a full life now and the lives of future generations. Lake Baikal is such a natural object that combines the past, present and future. That why he does not leave the paintings of artists, presenting himself all the time in a new artistic image for himself. «Nowadays Lake Baikal is an inexhaustible source of inspiration for artists. The masters paint its nature, inhabitants, inhabitants of its shores, their everyday life is depicted on canvases, as well as the severity and unpredictability of its elements» (Pokatsky V. A., 2020, p. 240).

The purpose of this article is to consider the paintings by the artist P. S. Panarin «Baikal» and «Baikal wave», made in the genre of natural landscape in the context of creating an artistic image of such a different Baikal.

In accordance with the set goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

— to provide an overview of the scientific literature on the topic under consideration;

— define the methodology of the present study;

— to present a brief historical and geographical sketch of Lake Baikal;

— to define the genre of the natural landscape, to consider its features;

— in the context of defining the genre of natural landscape, consider the paintings by the artist P. S. Panarin «Baikal», 1976 and «Baikal Wave», 1959, presenting such a different Baikal in painting.

Wherever you have to meet Baikal landscapes, they are always recognizable due to the popularity of this place. The depiction of Baikal places and attractions differs from work to work due to the individuality and artistic talent of the artist who rearranged them.

This work has a scientific novelty as it presents an image of such a different Lake Baikal by one artist, representing the diversity and versatility of his talent and the uniqueness of the Baikal landscapes.

From a practical point of view, this research can be used in further scientific and pedagogical activities as methodological material.

During the preparation of this article, the following literature was selected and studied:

— the work of senior lecture A. V. Bekisheva «Landscape in painting by trans-Baikal artists of the second half of the twentieth century» tells about specific artists living in the Trans-Baikal Territory and painting Baikal, their works created during the specified time period;

— the scientific article by Gurlenova L. V. «The realistic image of nature in modern regional painting» is devoted to the peculiarities of depicting the natural landscape of individual localities and regions;

— the work of the Candidate of cultural Studies Lyashenko E. S. «Trans-Baikal painting of the XVIII — early XXI century: problems of periodization»

tells about the trends in the development of fine art (including) landscape painting in the specified period of time;

— the scientific publication of E. S. Manzyreva, Candidate of Cultural Studies, «The image of Eastern Siberia and its reflection in regional artistic culture» is devoted to the description of the artistic image of the Baikal region created in the culture and art of this area;

— V. A. Pokatsky's article «The nature of the Baikal region in the work of Leopold Nemirovsky» tells about the work of a single artist, describes his creative path and the fate of the created works of art;

— the work of art critic T. G. Lareva «The history of fine art of the Baikal region of the XX — early XXI century» gives an idea of the types and genres of fine art in the region as a whole.

«Baikal-fairy tale lakes». Collection. Book 1 presents the legend of the origin of Lake Baikal, which is an important component in describing the image of this natural object.

The indicated scientific and specialized literature helps to fully reveal and understand the subject of this study «Such a different Baikal in the visual arts» and acts as its methodology.

The present study was conducted using:

— empirical research methods: observations, comparisons, descriptions. Having determined the initial data — the image of Lake Baikal in fine art, a description and comparative analysis of the landscape works of the artist P. S. Panarin in the context of this study is carried out;

— methods of theoretical research (induction, deduction, comparative analysis, analogy). The methods of induction (from the particular to the general) and deduction (from the general to the particular) in this study are interrelated, since from identifying the characteristic features and artistic features of the image of Lake Baikal in a particular painting, a general description of this natural object in the visual arts is given, and, — on the contrary. In defining and describing the features of a particular work, there is a comparative analysis and analogy, with the help of which the signs of the created artistic image are emphasized and highlighted;

— methods of generalization and systematization, which are used in this case in order to summarize the data obtained as a result of a comparative analysis of works of art in order to identify the characteristic artistic features of the artistic image of Lake Baikal in the landscape works of the artist P. S. Panarin in the context of the designated the me.

In addition, the above-mentioned scientific and specialized literature can also be used as a research methodology.

Lake Baikal is the deepest freshwater lake on earth. It is located on the territory of Eastern Siberia. More than three hundred small streams and rivers flow into the

lake, but only one flows out — the Angara. The bottom of Lake Baikal in one place is more than a kilometer below the level of the World Ocean. The lake is located in a kind of natural excavation formed by mountain ranges, mountains and hills. There are about thirty islands on the lake, and the largest of them is Olkhon Island, located in the western part of Lake Baikal. The age of the lake is still a scientific debate. It is generally assumed that it corresponds to a figure of more than 25 million years. This fact makes this natural site unique, as freshwater lakes mostly live no more than 15 thousand years. Then they are bogged down (Lyashenko E. S., 2023). The peoples living along the shores of the lake have many legends and legends about the origin of the lake. Here is one of them:

«About Baikal...

In ancient times, a dense forest grew in the place where Lake Baikal is now. There were so many birds and animals in this forest that it was difficult for a person to pass. Among the birds, one stood out, it was the size of a large sturgeon. Her wings were huge and strong, if she hit a tree, it would fall to the ground by its roots, and if she hit a rock, the rock would fly apart. People were afraid of that bird and could not kill it in any way, because when it flew, such hot rays came from it that the hunters fell dead. However, one man was born among the people. He grew rapidly. Soon he grew up to be a hero and was not afraid of any force. The people went to him to ask him to save everyone from trouble and kill that firebird. The hero obeyed. I made a bow out of a hundred trees, carved an arrow out of two hundred woods, and went hunting. Soon, the ground shook. That bird fell from a well-aimed shot, the fire started so that the sky is hot. The people dispersed from this taiga to the mountains and saw columns of water breaking through the flames. So the sea in that place became. When the earth and taiga were burning, the people shouted: «Baikal, Baikal!» When the sea became, the name Baikal has been preserved from century to century. Either the fire was called Baikal by the big people, or that bird was so called, or maybe this word meant «a lot of water»... People just remembered that this place is called Baikal» (Baikal-fairy tale lakes, 1989, p. 235).

Landscape as a separate genre of fine art is an image of nature or its individual elements and objects. It has called a natural or classical landscape. It has a deep history of origin and development. The image of nature accompanies visual art throughout the entire period of its existence. The landscape is present both in the earliest paintings and in modern installations. Nature is the source, the basis of life on earth, it accompanies man everywhere (Gurlenova L. V., 2013). In the landscape, the artist acts as a researcher, he does not copy the world around him, but subjectively passes it through himself, and transmits his impressions, thoughts, experiences, emotions and feelings to the viewer in the picture. It is in the landscape that the abilities and peculiarities of the artist's talent are more evident in the ability to convey the state of the surrounding world and its changes. Landscape

painter as an intermediary between the human world and the natural world. The main theme of his image is the views of nature and natural objects not created by man. This type of landscape is the main one and dates back several hundred years in its history. «The initial factor influencing the formation of the image of any region is the surrounding nature. In this aspect, the East Siberian region, with its variety of geographical and climatic manifestations, is unique. Taiga and steppes, mountain ranges and plateaus, abundance of rivers and the pearl of the region — Lake Baikal, these things are most often found in paintings or literary sketches» (Manzyreva E. S., 2017, p. 34).

Fig. 1. P. S. Panarin «Baikal», 1976. Source of literature: goskatalog.ru

Consider the work of the artist P. S. Panarin «Baikal», 1976 (fig. 1):

The composition of the work has a horizontal shape. In the foreground, the calm water surface of Lake Baikal is depicted, where a boat is depicted near the very line of intersection with the shoreline, heading towards the viewer. The coast is a line of land in the form of hills and natural irregularities. The shore along which the boat runs, located closest, is brighter and more saturated in color. Further, on, the earth seems to be in a haze, here the colors are already dimmer, with a predominance of blue and lilac shades. Judging by the greenery painted by the artist in the foreground, it is a clear sunny summer day. The sky is blue with white clouds. The waters of Lake Baikal seem to be motionless and heavy. The painting exudes peace and tranquility. The artist's work is done in the style of realism, as all objects correspond to their size and scale, the color scheme of the landscape is close to the natural.

A completely different Baikal is represented in the work «Baikal Wave», 1959 (fig. 2), by the artist P. S. Panarin.

The composition of the work also has a horizontal position. In the work, the bend of a large wave is immediately presented in the foreground, which occupies

almost the entire workspace. Baikal is shown not calm, but seething with waves. Looking at the work creates a feeling of anxiety and tension. The water is shown to be a dense dark green color with brown hues. In the distance, in the background, you can see a strip of blue shore and a dark, heavy sky approaching the surface of the lake, almost touching the latter. The artist shows a harsh natural environment, a lake at the time of an approaching storm. The work, like the previous one, is executed in the style of realism, since the size and scale of the depicted elements correspond to reality and the color scheme of the landscape is close to the natural one.

Fig. 2. P. S. Panarin «Baikal Wave», 1959. Source of literature: goskatalog.ru

Such a different Baikal was represented in the works of the artist P.S. Panarin. «The landscape is a kind of reflection of reality through the prism of the artist's vision, his monologue about what he saw. What matters here is the color and the mood it creates; the captured objective world that the author includes in the format of the painting; as well as the narrative and plot of the image» (Bekisheva A. V., 2020, p. 39).

If we consider in general the works of the artist P. S. Panarin devoted to the image of such a Baikal, we can state that:

- the presented works of the artist belong to the genre of natural landscape;
- the artist's works depict Lake Baikal;
- the presented works of the artist depict Lake Baikal in different states: calm and agitated;

- the presented works of the artist have signs of the style or realism;
- the presented works of the artist have a rectangular composition, which sets a certain dynamic associated with the plot of the works — to show the breadth and immensity of Lake Baikal;
- all the artist's works have their own unique artistic image of Lake Baikal, depending on the individuality and personality of the artist himself (Lareva T. G., 2015).
Thus, in the course of the conducted research:
 - a review of the scientific literature on the topic was presented;
 - the methodology of the present study has been determined;
 - a brief historical and geographical sketch of Lake Baikal was presented;
 - the definition of the genre of natural landscape was given, its features were considered;
- in the context of defining the genre of the natural landscape, the paintings by the artist P. S. Panarin «Baikal», 1976 and «Baikal Wave», 1959, presenting such a different Baikal in painting, were considered.

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**ANGLES OF VICTORIA PITIRIMOVA'S REALITY.
ON THE ISSUE OF THE FORMATION
OF THE AUTHOR'S VISUAL VOCABULARY**

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Abstract: *The article discusses aspects evolution of the author's plastic language of the Ural artist Victoria Pitirimova and an attempt is made to analyze he multidisciplinary practices in work on the graphic cycle "Khazar Lexicon".*

Keywords: *Ural region, Victoria Pitirimova, graphic object, graphic biennale, Khazar lexicon.*

Art at all times

resists unambiguity as much as it can.

Alexander Borovsky [1, p. 184]

The Ural-Siberian region, as an area of ecological risk, natural anomalies, and relentless exploration of new spaces, shapes a distinctive character of creative individuality inclined to transgress the boundaries of conventional aesthetic approaches and practices. At the turn of the 1990s and early 2000s, during the emergence of the biennial movement in post-Soviet Russia, contemporary art centers were established in major regional hubs such as Ufa, Yekaterinburg, Nizhny Tagil, Krasnoyarsk, and Novosibirsk, serving as unique platforms for international creative exchange. What motivated the artists of the Urals and Siberia to actively experiment with methods of traditional creative practice in search of a new visual vocabulary? The Chelyabinsk-based artist Victoria Pitirimova became one of the leaders of this movement in the Urals.

It is generally accepted that art can be divided into genres and types, thereby systematizing the diversity of its forms for the sake of our understanding. Of course, it can. Only within the living creative process are all these concepts easily blended and rearranged, generating new modes of visual expression. Victoria Pitirimova is precisely one of those contemporary artists who freely express themselves through

diverse forms of artistic plasticity. She is captivated by experiments with photography and colored glass pressing. She takes an interest in the unpredictable processes of etching and monotype. Her pictorial canvases transform into monumental frescoes, and her graphic cycles into spatial objects. Having received a classical art education, she consistently strives to surpass the confines of academic artistic practice, discovering through experimentation her own methods and regularities for visualizing her concepts.

The impetus for this was the artist's fascination with artistic printing technologies, which allow the author to experiment with textures and engraving techniques. The catalyst for the formation of the authorial plastic language based on this was the work on a cycle inspired by the novel by Serbian writer Milorad Pavić, *The Dictionary of the Khazars*, translated into Russian in the 1990s. Through a thoughtful interpretation of the interplay of meanings in the Serbian author's hypertext, Victoria Pitirimova reveals new methods of variability on the plane and within the spatiality of various media, which later become a defining characteristic of her authorial style.

Figure 1. Pitirimova V. M. "Khazar Lexicon. Red Book" 2002
Paper, etching 84x54 cm

First and foremost, it is essential to underscore the artist's deeply personal interest in decoding the essence of the myth of the 'Khazar debate,' as living in a multiethnic region and bearing the genes of representatives of all three religions, she, through creative experimentation, formulated the codes of her own identity. The process of search extended over a full decade, from 2001 to 2011, expanding and enriching the vocabulary of expression with each passing year.

Figure 2. Pitirimova V. M. "Khazar Lexicon. Yellow Book" 2002
Paper, etching 74x56 cm

One of the principal stylistic features of Pitirimova's authorial lexicon is the ornamental character of her vision. According to her own words, she has 'always been captivated by ornaments, such as those in Bashkir or Kazakh carpets, in the petroglyphs of Altai, or in Kyrgyz felt rugs, where the figures simultaneously serve as the background.' This principle of rhythmic plastic interplay among condensed forms underpins the principal triptych of engravings in the Khazar cycle — "Red Book" (fig. 1), "Green Book" (fig. 2), and "Yellow Book" (fig. 3). Each of the

three “symbols of Faith” — the cross, the crescent, and the six-pointed star — is constructed from the same set of etching matrices but arranged in a new sequence, conforming to the designated shape of the symbol. The plastic interplay of various scenarios combining images, forms, and textures became the artist’s response to the semantic play within the writer’s postmodern text. If Pavic’s primary technique is the static nature of the plot or event combined with a shift in perspective, then Pitirimova employs the opposite principle — the mobility of narrative rhythm within the stasis of predetermined symbols. The combination of panels based on only two geometric shapes — the square and the triangle — with recurring motifs vividly embodies the idea of the essential unity of all spiritual truths amidst the external diversity of their rituals.

Figure 3. Pitirimova V. M. “Khazar Lexicon. Green Book” 2002
Paper, etching 74x56 cm

Artistic thinking is an integral process. The solutions discovered during the initial plastic experiment with the material become, for the reflective artist, a conscious linguistic device that subsequently develops and enriches the lexicon of their self-expression. This pattern is also evident in the work of Victoria Pitirimova. Working with the graphic sign in real space brought the artist into the realm of contextual games involving shifts of visual perspectives within architectural and landscape environments. The figures of the «Catchers» shifted from static

to dynamic positions, placed at different levels — sometimes within the exhibition interior spaces, sometimes in the landscape environment against the sky or trees — interacting at times with the viewer, at others with light sources, and still others with air movement (Fig. 5). Such fundamental interactivity of the artistic concept endowed V. Pitirimova's project with affinities to the postmodern character of M. Pavic's novel, creating a semiotic field where, as in our dreams, known information is recoded into new texts and meanings. The artist herself perceives a correspondence between the novel and her cycle of works in the context of overlapping and interweaving forms and connections. 'In Pavic's work, events take place within a once-designated, immutable life space of the Khazars, but the components within it change; in my "Khazar Lexicon," the plastic components remain constant, though they are each time situated in different spatial circumstances.' Thus, the hypertext of the novel generates the hyperspace of the graphic series, constructed as a virtual puzzle of multidirectional semantic connections, a multitude of visual contexts, and the variability of metaphorical interpretations.

Figure 4. Landscape installation "Dream Catchers. Flight". Ural region. 2006.

The logic behind the further de-sealing of the semantic structure of the novel's text provoked the artist's interest in mastering space as a total text and applying graphic techniques within non-graphic technologies. This refers to her experiments with glass textures, mirror reflections in the 'reverse kaleidoscope,' and the interplay of photomontage combining positive and negative images in frames

of her own jumps as ‘attempts at flight.’ The world, in such mirrored refraction, indeed resembled a whimsical ornament. This is how the artist herself describes this experience: «I wanted to transform optical effects into graphic space. To achieve this, I suspended a kaleidoscope in various exposures so it could be rotated in all directions, observing inside the refractions of objects as graphical mirror reflections. An interesting effect emerged then — it was not the mirrored lens that was being turned, but the reality around it. I even attempted to create something like an animation: I glued fragments of engravings onto a cardboard circle and rotated it in front of the mirrored lens. The result was amusing, dynamic graphics. A game in cinema.” [5] The playful aspect was dominant in this case, as the viewer was granted complete freedom to manipulate the object and interpret the optical effects. Experiments with glass pressing and the inlaying of wire “texts” into it further developed the concepts of mirage-like dreams and the magic of disappearing texts (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Fragment of the exhibition of the Personal exhibition of Victoria Pitirimova “Perspectives of Reality”, 2016. Chelyabinsk, Chelyabinsk State Museum of Fine Arts.

As a result of the artist’s profound immersion in the process of visually decoding the codes of the “Khazar Lexicon,” she was able to establish her own lexical vocabulary. It possesses its own morphology of form creation, transforming certain images into others through reflections and combinatorics of printing techniques, the complementarity of different materials and media into new syntactic structures, while the diversity of exhibition presentation methods allows the viewer to derive new meanings from the spatial context of the images each time. New ideas give rise to new modes of expression, yet the unity of the author’s approach remains discernible — a dialogue with the material in search of a new perspective of perception. In this bilateral process, the artist always encounters a novelty of impressions, the discovery of unexpected technical possibilities, a ‘ping-pong of media response,’ according to her own witty remark. ‘For me, art generally arises

from the close interaction of idea, form, and language,' she admitted in our personal conversation.— 'I am especially fascinated by improvisations with the process. Often, it happens that at the beginning of the process I suppose something, and then I arrive at new sensations, ideas, and decisions within the space.' Listening to her commentary, one cannot help but think that her approach to artistic practice embodies the principle of an 'open plot,' almost Pavić-like, with the possibility of various trajectories of movement within it and arbitrary changes of perspective in the optics of perceiving reality. The artist herself becomes part of the process, dissolving within it, just as the Khazar princess vanished in her reflection. Within this approach, the author and the viewer become co-authors, and the artwork envelops them, drawing them into its metaphorical space. Victoria Pitirimova always invites her viewer to 'change the point of view' and to gaze into the exhibition space either through the shifting angle of a rotating mirror kaleidoscope, through glass texts, or from within chiaroscuro vibrations, to be convinced that the primary images and meanings are generated within our consciousness. Contemporary artists seek to focus our attention on the creative potential within ourselves, inviting the viewer to become an active co-author. The entire focus of transforming reality into an artistic phenomenon lies in the perspective from which we view it.

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APPROACHES TO DESIGNING ONLINE TRAINING FOR FUTURE JOURNALISTS IN THE FORM OF PRACTICE-ORIENTED COURSES

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Abstract: *This article examines the main methodological approaches to designing the goals and objectives of practice-oriented courses when organizing online educational activities for future journalists. Based on an analysis of Kazan Federal University's experience in online, practice-oriented training for future journalists, based on collaborative principles of interaction with the regional media system, the author develops a model for organizing online education in the context under study.*

Keywords: *future journalist, journalism education, collaboration, regional media, online education.*

Introduction

The modern system of university training of future journalists is on the way to comprehending and reformatting the goals of the entire educational process with an emphasis on the organization of practical training. It becomes obvious that the training of future journalists is in a state of permanent transformation, which is facilitated by the rapid development of information and computer technologies, as well as the active digitalization of both the educational space and other areas of professional activity, including the media sphere, which, in turn, involves an emphasis on digital tools, the development of which becomes the basis for the development of the content of educational programs and courses. It should also be noted the multifaceted nature of transformation processes in the education of future journalists, the main of which is the influence of multimedia technologies on the creation of the final products of journalistic activity, which leads to the multimedia of journalistic activity. These aspects also have an impact on the processes of educational practice, require responses to the challenges of the profession and the digital world, and actualize the issues of organizing professional education for future journalists in the university format in the context of the search and design

of new forms. One of them, in our opinion, is the network form. This article is devoted to its features and main characteristics.

Methods

To determine the main characteristics of the organization of the network form of education for future journalists, the experience of the Kazan Federal University for 2015–2025 was analyzed, within the framework of the courses developed and conducted by the author for the specified period: “Theory of Mass Media”, “Technology of Journalistic Activity”, “Professional Technologies of Modern Journalism”, “Fundamentals of Art Journalism”, “Introduction to Ethnojournalism”. In total, 10 student groups with a total number of 200 people took part in the study. The study was divided into stages: 2015–2016 — substantiation and theoretical definition of the features of the organization of network training for future journalists within the framework of special modules of the disciplines read (creativity modules); 2017–2023 — development and design of methodological justification for network formats integrated into the programs of the courses taught as creative laboratories and creative workshops, development of content, diagnostic materials, tasks, etc.; 2024–2025 — determination of the main outcomes of network learning.

Results

When developing and evaluating new formats for organizing the educational activities of future journalists, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the educational environment is also becoming digital. In 2020, Russia launched the state information system “Modern Digital Educational Environment”, which is designed to provide universities with digital platforms. This environment acts as an aggregator of online courses from different platforms and universities, which are hosted on the sites of educational organizations that create and support these courses, as a single point of access to the resources of different providers [13]. Thus, the digital educational environment is based on the use of various digital technologies and resources in the educational process as means of learning, providing ample opportunities for the implementation of versatile communicative and effective relationships, shifting the focus of attention to the interaction of subjects acting in different roles. The most complete definition, in our opinion, of the digital educational environment is given by O. N. Shilova, who proposes to understand it as “a complex of relations in educational activities mediated by the use of digital technologies and digital educational resources, contributing to the implementation by the subjects of the educational process of opportunities to master culture, ways of self-realization, building social relations aimed at the formation of responsible digital behavior of a citizen modern society.” [14, p. 40]. Researchers classify the types of digital education, distinguishing textual information among them

(electronic textbooks, articles); visual information (illustrations, videos); audio information (recording of lectures, audiobooks); interactive models (virtual laboratories, interactives); audio and video information (online lectures, recordings of master classes) [15]. The highlighted features of the digital educational environment of the university allow us to identify the features of digitalization of the education of future journalists: actualization of the processes of self-development of the student; accentuation of personal characteristics of creative energy management (creative potential); special emphasis in this process is placed on the digital foundations of the system of practice-oriented education of future journalists. Based on a certain parity of fundamentality and mobility of educational practices, it should be noted that the digital environment can flexibly combine and quickly respond to changes in the media sphere and the conditions of the future journalist's activities, creating an effective "learning landscape" (V. V. Gatov), including creative spaces that stimulate and motivate creativity [1].

Thus, a kind of educational digital cluster should be formed to combine practice-oriented forms of educational activity of students and fundamental training. The main subject for study in this context is digital content, the ability to work with which brings to life the requirements for future media workers in the field of digital literacy and information technology. The criteria for the formation of professional readiness are now digital culture, digital ethics, digital security [8; 9; 10].

Among the main directions of development of modern media are: the growth of the influence of social networks in the dissemination of information; development of the podcast format in the media space; the spread of formats with interactive characteristics that ensure the interaction of participants in communication processes [4]; development of artificial intelligence and data journalism; strengthening the fight against fakes and disinformation and growing interest in media education. The growing influence of artificial intelligence and neural networks in media practice is also important, which allows us to talk about the need to form competencies in this area among future journalists, and the fan divergence of the audience in social networks allows, for example, K. R. Nigmatullina to assert that there is practically no mass audience in its classical sense now, which forces the journalist to work differently with a local audience, delineated by interests, views, preferences, etc. [7].

In the context of the indicated trend directions for the development of journalism, the most promising form of organizing journalism education programs can be considered a network form through the integration of educational programs (on the basis of joint participation of educational organizations in the development of educational programs and its implementation) and through the use of the resources of a partner organization (when one or more organizations, educational and industrial, participate in network interaction). This makes it possible to improve the quality and effectiveness of personnel training, and even in conditions of limited

resources, to solve the problem of their shortage. An analysis of the experience of universities in such conditions allows us to talk about the sufficient prevalence of network programs, as well as about their significant characteristics: increasing the competitiveness of leading universities, “which have the opportunity to enter new markets”; introduction of tools for modernizing the organization of the educational process based on the understanding of the experience of partners [5, p. 13].

Discussion

The network form of implementation of educational programs is designated in the Federal Law “On Education” as providing an opportunity for students to master an educational program using the resources of several organizations engaged in educational activities [11]. V. A. Zakharova and A. S. Belozerova identify a number of features that allow us to talk about the effectiveness of this form of educational activity: providing the opportunity to solve problems that require joint efforts based on the exchange of experience and knowledge, best practices; concentration of resources; creating conditions for the professional growth of university teachers, improving the quality of education, and quickly responding to changes in the educational environment [3].

A special form in the training of future journalists is the network interaction between the university and the media, which become a partner of the educational process. Thus, the network form of educational activity in the context of training future journalists allows you to integrate the educational space of the university into the system of professional activity — the media sphere, contributes to the approximation of such a form of educational activity as industrial practice to the real conditions of media practice, increasing the academic and practice-oriented mobility of students. All participants in the network form of educational activities receive certain advantages. They are defined in Table 1.

Table 1.
Advantages of the network form of educational activity

Subject	Characteristics of advantages
Educational organization (university)	Improving the quality of education due to the updating of educational programs, taking into account the level and features of resource support for real professional activities, the exchange of experience in training personnel between educational organizations, creating conditions for use in the learning process of modern material, technical and methodological base, convergence of educational programs aimed at training specialists in demand in the labor market.

Employer, representative of media structures, including business	Improving the quality of trained personnel by accumulating the best resources of educational and other organizations with the possibility of monitoring and adjusting the training of specialists.
A student is a future journalist	Increasing the competitiveness of a media market with the possibility of employment on the basis of developed personal qualities, competencies of oral and written communication, adaptive abilities, expanding the boundaries of awareness of existing educational and other resources, own resources, which helps to increase motivation to study, awareness of responsibility for achieving the result.

Thus, the network form of the educational process in the training of future journalists is based on collaboration as mutually beneficial cooperation between media structures (representatives of the media market) and an educational organization — a university, striving to achieve mutually beneficial results. The university is to improve the efficiency and quality of training future journalists, the media structure is to train the personnel that are needed at the moment. The design of the network form of training future journalists at Kazan (Volga Region) Federal University is based on a horizontal structure of interaction — “university — media system of the region”. This makes it possible to ensure the implementation of joint educational and research projects, the joint development and implementation of training course programs, the presentation of the results of activities at forums and conferences, and the provision of career guidance for future journalists (acquaintance with the profession). The most productive type of such activity is laboratories — “Laboratories of Discoveries” and “Laboratories of Creativity”. “Discovery Laboratories” are intended for implementation in junior courses (mainly in the first year). Here the task is professional motivation and orientation in the profession, which is carried out within the framework of the so-called journalistic holidays — on the basis of media organizations, which can be carried out 1–2 times a year and involve training in team building, excursions to the city’s media enterprises, attending master classes organized by practicing journalists. All this makes it possible to create conditions for the implementation of professional tests — practice in real media conditions. “Discovery Labs” include the following stages: theoretical (familiarity with terminology); technological (acquaintance with the methods of professional activity) and creative (creative application of the acquired skills). The Discovery Labs project is implemented in the main educational program (the Practical Media Design module) and in additional educational programs of a career guidance orientation developed by the participants of the network project.

For the effective functioning of the Discovery Laboratories, it is necessary to develop a set of additional educational programs to support the professional training

of students, a bank of methodological cases to support the professional training of future journalists, a package of diagnostic materials to support the professional training of future journalists. Also, one of the most important directions in this context is the design of goals and objectives of educational programs, academic disciplines and courses, which in the modern theory of higher education is considered as a fundamental stage of methodological support of the educational process [2; 6].

“Creativity Laboratories” are designed for senior courses and involve network training in practice-oriented courses. The design of the goals and objectives of educational activities is based on the following provisions.

The design of the goals and objectives of the discipline takes place in the format of competencies, which involves the compilation of a modular structure of the content and a matrix of correspondence of various didactic units (modules, submodules, educational elements) to the competencies, the formation of which ensures the development of the discipline and the choice of innovative teaching technologies.

Based on the approach to the description of tasks in the context of problem situations proposed by L. M. Fridman [12], it is possible to identify the main functions of the tasks of the discipline as an integrative didactic unit of the educational process:

- educational function (formation of the ability to solve professional problems in the relevant types of professional activities and competencies);
- criterion function (diagnostics of the level of competence formation);
- developmental function (development of self-esteem and self-determination in future journalists).

Practice-oriented tasks of training future journalists can be defined as an integrative didactic unit of content, technology and monitoring of the quality of training of future journalists in the educational process of the university, ensuring the effectiveness of the formation of students’ professional competencies. Problem situations that tend to be reflected in the student’s mind and objectified in the sign model, that is, in the information model expressed by special signs, can act as such tasks. For journalism education, such objectification is associated with the textual embodiment of tasks, since the most adequate form of the existence of the problems of journalism is the text. The problem situation must meet the requirements of compliance with the professional type of activity of the future journalist.

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, we can distinguish the main stages of designing the goals and objectives of practice-oriented training of future journalists in the format of network training:

1. Analytical — analysis of the requirements of the media market for specialists and their correlation with the corresponding area of training.

2. Identification of professional competencies that are subject to formation in the process of educational activities.

3. Selection of educational and practical material (media material — media texts and other products of media activity/journalist's activity) for practice-oriented tasks and development of their content.

4. Approbation and refinement of the system of practice-oriented tasks in the conditions of real professional activity in the media system of the region.

5. Implementation of goals and objectives in the content of disciplines in the organization of the network form of educational activities.

Thus, when designing the goals and objectives of practice-oriented training of future journalists in a network format, it is important to focus on the formation of students' competencies that reflect and meet the modern needs of the real media sphere. This is possible with active collaboration between an educational organization and media enterprises interested in training highly qualified personnel. The prospects for studying the problems of network interaction in the course of organizing educational activities should include the comprehension and identification of the patterns of development of various forms of network interaction, as well as the identification of conditions and factors for the effectiveness of forms and models of network interaction.

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MARSHAK'S TRANSLATION HERITAGE (FROM ENGLISH CLASSICAL POETRY)

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Abstract: *This article lists the names of English poets whose works S. Ya. Marshak was fascinated with at various times in his life. He left behind a vast legacy of translations of their poetry in various genres. English poetry for children occupies a special place in the article. It examines folklore motifs and images refracted in the poems of English authors, which always fascinated Marshak the translator.*

Keywords: *children's poetry, folklore, poetic genres, nonsense poetry, fairy tale, tall tale, humor*

Marshak's long-lasting interest in English poetry, initially in book form, then reinforced by his youthful encounter with national folklore and its linguistic practices during his stay in Great Britain from 1912 to 1914, would find further expression in his translation work throughout his career.

The largest-scale "projects" in this field would be his translations of Shakespeare's sonnets and virtually the entire poetic legacy of Burns. At the same time, Marshak also created excellent examples of "selective" translations of other English poets of various eras and movements, from Blake, Coleridge, and Wordsworth to Carroll and Milne.

In one of his letters, Marshak wrote: "I love Byron very much, but I have translated him little... Unfortunately, we have had no luck with Byron. Good translations — translations equal to the original — are few. You can count them on your fingers: translations by Lermontov, Ogarev, Ivan Bunin (the poems "Cain" and "Manfred"), Boris Pasternak, Tatyana Gnedich, V. Levik" (19/1 1963). 1 From

Byron's "Jewish Melodies," Marshak translated the poems "She Walks in All Her Beauty" and "You Cry — They Glow with a Tear..." [1]. Among the translations of texts by Percy Bysshe Shelley (1792–1822), our attention is drawn to the poem "Winter," in which the poet creates metaphorical anthropomorphic images of nature:

*The bird mourned its love,
Alone in the gray forest.
The frozen wind crept between the branches,
The water rustled with ice [2].*

The dates of the first publications of many of S. Marshak's translations of English and Scottish poetry are noteworthy. They range from the 1910s to the early 1960s. Russian-speaking readers were widely introduced to the poetry of foreign authors in "Literaturnaya Gazeta", "Inostrannaya Literatura", "Ogonyok", and even "Krokodil" and "Pioneer".

In his translations of Tennyson (1809–1892) and Browning (1812–1889)—English poets of the post-Romantic period — Marshak also remains true to his interest in the folk tradition in their work ("The Miller's Daughter," "The Eagle" (1947). "The Flutist of Hamelin" is an adaptation of a medieval legend that became a common literary plot).

The same can be said of the translations of poets of the next literary generation: Dante Gabriel Rossetti (1828–1882), an English poet and painter, one of the founders of the Pre-Raphaelite school, and Robert Louis Stevenson (1850–1894)'s "Heather Honey."

From Kipling's creative legacy, S. Marshak translated the author's verses included in his fairy tales. For example, the poem "On the Far Amazon..." is placed at the end of the fairy tale "Where Did the Armadillos Come From." It was also published in Kipling's books under the title "Brazil," and later became a popular bard song. A passion for the clear rhythms of counting rhymes at one time prompted Marshak to translate these perky and whimsical verses by Kipling.

Marshak's poems about steamships sailing to Brazil combine the businesslike routine of a steamship schedule with a romantic dream of distant, unknown lands. The verse rhythm gradually slows, helping one clearly sense how long and far the ships must travel:

*From Liverpool harbor
Always on Thursdays
Ships set sail
To distant shores.
They sail to Brazil, Brazil,
Brazil.
And I want to go to Brazil,
To distant shores! [3].*

Such poems will be most appreciated by a child, for whom poetry begins with clear lines of verse, born with the movement of play. However, the translator also emphasizes the informational and analytical side of the text:

*You will never find in our northern forests
Long-tailed jaguars, armored turtles.
But in sunny Brazil, my Brazil
Such an abundance of unseen beasts [3].*

The presence of refrains gives the verse additional rhythm and semantic completeness, reinforcing the philosophical tone of the poem's ending:

*And in sunny Brazil, my Brazil
Such an abundance of unseen beasts!
Will I ever see Brazil, Brazil, Brazil,
Will I ever see Brazil before my old age? [3].*

Marshak's poems, eagerly accepted by children, are far from superficially imitating folklore. And yet, Marshak learned from the people, creating his proverbs, jokes, teasers, and songs. Marshak preserves these elements of children's play even when he moves from short and simple songs to more complex tales and fables, both in form and content: "If in the glass of the cabin..." is placed at the end of the fairy tale "Where does the whale get such a throat?", "I have six servants..." — at the end of the fairy tale "The Little Elephant" (in R. Kipling's books it was published under the title "A Hundred Thousand Whys"), "The camel's hump, so clumsy..." — after the fairy tale "Why does the camel have a hump", "The cat sings wonderfully by the fire..." at the end of the fairy tale "The Cat Who Walked by Herself", "The Song of Darzi, the Tailor Bird, in Honor of the Brave Mongoose Rikki-Tikki-Tavi".

A special place in Marshak's legacy is occupied by his translations of Edward Lear (1812–1888), an English poet and artist, which he worked on in the last years of his life. In a letter to V. M. Konashevich on May 26, 1961, Marshak wrote: "... I am translating the poems of Edward Lear, the founder of English children's poetry, the first creator of the genre of "nonsense." There is so much whimsy, invention, and spiritual purity in his books. And at the same time, Edward Lear is one of the most musical poets" [4: 23]. Publishing translations of E. Lear in periodicals or separate collections, Marshak often noted the originality of his work. A magnificent master of verse, he combines inexhaustible humor with gentle lyricism in his children's books... His heroes are cheerful and sweet eccentrics of his own creation, talking animals, birds, and things. "Translating Lear is very difficult. It is not easy to convey his varied, flexible rhythm and the melody of his verses, to reproduce in another language the whimsical procession of his images... I worked on translating Lear with the liveliest interest and pleasure. I wanted to convey to readers that cheerful playfulness that constitutes the essence of Edward Lear's poetry" [4: 23].

Lewis Carroll (1832–1898), Professor of Mathematics at Oxford University, continued the tradition of E. Lear. From the fables he told the children of his colleagues, the fairy tale “Alice in Wonderland” and its sequel “Through the Looking-Glass: What Alice Saw There” were later born. Lewis Carroll wrote “A Russian Journal” after his 1867 trip to Russia. S. Marshak’s archive contains several handwritten pages of a prose translation of Alice in Wonderland, as well as an autograph of the first stanza of a poem from the same book, “Do You Hear the Crab’s Voice...”

One of Marshak’s last contacts was with the writer’s contemporary, Alexander Allan Milne (1882–1956). “A. Milne’s ‘Ballad of the King’s Sandwich,’” writes B. Galanov, “sparkles with a cheerful, mischievous joke and at the same time conveys with extraordinary precision and naturalness the lively intonations of all the characters, from the king to the court milkmaid inclusive... it is both good-natured mockery and casual children’s play” [5: 41].

S. Ya. Marshak consistently mastered the entire classics of English children’s poetry, which in one way or another harkens back to the folk tradition, its various genres, images, and motifs.

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THE COLOR CONTINUUM OF I.S. TURGENEV'S "SKETCHES FROM A HUNTER'S ALBUM" CYCLE

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Abstract. *This article examines the color continuum as a holistic and structural system in the "Sketches from a Hunter's Album" cycle (also known as "A Hunter's Sketches"). The text's color organization, extending beyond its descriptive function, becomes a primary mechanism for modeling artistic reality. Through an analysis of the cycle, the formation of associative-semantic fields and binary oppositions, that structure the social space of everyday life and the philosophical space of existence the article explores. Particular attention is paid to the dynamic nature of the color palette, capable of symbolic inversion and transformation. It is argued that the color continuum is a fundamental element of Turgenev's idiosyle, providing a synthesis of concrete imagery and profound symbolism, and serves as a strategic key to understanding the author's worldview.*

Keywords: *color continuum, I. S. Turgenev, "Sketches from a Hunter's Album", Russian classical literature, idiosyle, color category, color symbolism, artistic picture of the world, poetics.*

In recent decades, scholarly attention has increasingly focused on integrative issues within the humanities, centering on the concept of the "Homo creator" (the creative individual) and their unique, authorial worldview. Color, as an integral part of the world, life, and being, represents a powerful medium for shaping consciousness, capable of exerting both psychological and physical influence. Undeniably connected to archetypal symbolism as well as to national and individual models of the world, color is consequently studied from the perspectives of numerous disciplines.

In contemporary literary studies and linguo-stylistics, the color continuum is defined as a holistic, dynamic, and structured system of color designations within a given literary text, cycle, or authorial corpus. Unlike a mere collection of color epithets, the continuum implies systematicity and interconnectedness, where color elements form semantic fields and binary oppositions that structure the artistic worldview. Each element within this system serves a distinct artistic function:

characterological (in portraiture or details of costume), psychological (reflecting emotional states or triggering associative perception), symbolic (white symbolizing light, purity, or death), and plot-forming or compositional (acting as a leitmotif or episode-dominant). The color palette itself may evolve throughout a narrative, mirroring conflict development, a character's internal transformation, or the author's philosophical conception — for instance, in a shift from vivid to muted, mixed tones. Thus, the color continuum stands as one of the fundamental linguistic and semiotic systems modeling artistic reality and the authors vision of the world.

The category of color is fundamental to the national model of the world. It aids in understanding the core components of the Russian cultural code and is essential for identifying the unique idiostyle and worldview of this representative of classical Russian literature. V. V. Nabokov himself noted the depth and diversity of Turgenev's individual manner and his extraordinary gift for perceiving and capturing beauty: "These softly colored, small sketches, which still delight us, are skillfully interspersed in his prose and are more reminiscent of watercolors (*Italics added here and below.* — E.I.) than the rich, dazzling Flemish portraits from the gallery of Gogol's characters. "A Hunter's Sketches" is especially replete with these sparkles of mastery" [3, p. 65]. Like paintings, these works allow each researcher to discern something personal, thereby contributing their own vision to the field of literary scholarship.

The dialogic nature of a literary work shapes this special continuum, wherein "thanks to the implicit expression of color, when it is not directly named but arises in the imagination based on associations, its informational capabilities are significantly expanded, thereby forming microfields and semantic nuances that expand the semantic potential of texts, creating a unique, meaningful space in which the associative fields of the writer and reader interact" [2, p. 24]. Creative consciousness is inherently marked by high associative flexibility, which fosters the generation of new and often unexpected semantic connections. Furthermore, the nature of such associations is shaped by the reader's general outlook, level of linguistic culture, and the broader sociocultural context. By inviting the reader into co-creation — prompting free association while subtly guiding its course — the artist transcends ready-made figurative and linguistic clichés.

"Sketches from a Hunter's Album" (also known as "A Hunter's Sketches") reflects key aspects of Russian life: its daily routines, connection to its native nature, traditions, and customs.

Traditionally, elements associated with everyday life, domestic customs, and material values is perceived as "low" and often carry a negative connotation. In contrast, images of Russian nature and landscape sketches serve as entry points for the author's lyrical digressions or the characters' philosophical reflections, elevating the reader's thoughts. This paper examines how the associative-semantic

fields formed by color in the everyday and existential space of “Sketches from a Hunter’s Album” not only enrich the narrative of the works, but also become a kind of “key” to the hidden meanings of the texts, the author’s position and ideological conception.

From the very first pages, Turgenev presents vignettes from life — a direct and natural account of the everyday scenes he observed in the villages of the Oryol and Kaluga provinces. Through descriptions of rural life and images of peasants, the writer attempts to convince the reader that the serf population is the foundation and spiritual core of the Russian nation.

The first story, “Khor and Kalinich”, begins with a contrast between the Oryol and Kaluga “race” of peasants, which manifests itself not only in their appearance but also in their living conditions. The Oryol serf “lives in wretched little hovels of aspen-wood” [4, p. 9]. Aspen is rarely used in residential construction, as the belief that this tree, like a vampire, drains a person’s energy is too strong. Among the disadvantages of this wood is the rather severe curvature of the trunk, which is often rotten from the inside and shrinks considerably, giving the huts a dilapidated and slanted appearance. Although the text doesn’t directly name the color of the peasant houses, it is implied by the word “aspen”, meaning dark gray or black. This is how an associative-semantic field is formed — poverty, misery, untidiness, uncleanness — which correlates with the characteristics of a typical village for the Oryol province: “is usually situated in the midst of ploughed fields, near a ravine which has been converted into a filthy pond. <...> hut is huddled up against hut, their roofs crudely thatched with rotting straw...” [4, p. 9]. All this leaves an imprint on the appearance of a local peasant, who “is not tall, is bent in figure, sullen and suspicious in his looks” [4, p. 9].

The rent-paying peasant of Kaluga, on the contrary, is “tall, bold, and cheerful in his looks, neat and clean of countenance”, because he “lives in roomy huts of pine-wood” [4, p. 9]. The reader’s imagination conjures log walls of a light yellow, golden color, which creates an atmosphere of well-being, cleanliness, neatness, freshness, and thrift. This idea surfaces several times in the narrative: Kalinych’s apiary is clean, smells of dried herbs, and spring water flowing through it, while in Khor’s house “the table of linden-wood had been lately washed and scrubbed” [4, p. 11], the walls are not plastered with cheap pictures, there are no cockroaches, and kvass is served to guests in a white mug.

The swamp on the edge of which Khor once settled is associated with a complex brown-yellow-green color, or khaki, meaning “dusty, earth-colored”. Swamp color can evoke dual associations: on one hand, it symbolizes danger, stagnation, and a wild place; on the other, it represents confidence and stability. The purest water is found in swamps. Thus, the rationalist Khor chose the optimal location for his “estate”.

Many of Turgenev's stories about peasants are close to the essay genre, therefore, artistic details involving color often serve to characterize the historical and cultural conditions of everyday life. For example, the writer sketches the wretched dwelling of the forester in the story "Biryuk" with a few cursory strokes: "The forester's hut consisted of one room, smoky, low-pitched, and empty, without a shelf-bed or partition. A tattered sheepskin hung on the wall. On the bench lay a single-barrelled gun; in the corner lay a heap of rags; two great pots stood near the oven. A pine splinter was burning on the table flickering up and dying down mournfully. In the very middle of the hut hung a cradle, suspended from the end of a long horizontal pole. <...> I looked round — my heart ached: it's not cheering to go into a peasant's hut at night" [4, pp. 154–155]. This passage functions as an ethnographic description of peasant life, depicting the dreadful Russian everyday life, that the forester's wife could not bear, compelling her to abandon her children and flee with a passing tradesman. The dim light of a torch casts a mournful, dark tint over the surrounding space and the girl's face, characterizing the serfs' hopeless existence.

The color of household items and interior elements also plays a significant role in recreating the atmosphere surrounding Turgenev's characters. Thus, in the story "Two Country Gentlemen" it is no coincidence that attention is paid to the description of Mardariy Apollonich's study: "a bluish-coloured screen covered with pictures cut out of various literary works of past century; a book-case full of musty books, spiders, and black dust" [4, p. 165]. The color of the screens should primarily evoke calm, peace, and harmony. However, the mention of pictures from old "musty" books, the disorder and dirt in the room, gives rise to an entirely different chain of associations. The "old man" — a serf-owner with the telling surname Stegunov (from the verb *stegat'* — "to lash") — orders the beating of peasants for the slightest offense. In his estate, the rules of Peter the Great's Rus' prevail ("Whom he loveth he chasteneth" [4, p. 168]), and thus the bluish color of the screens inevitably brings the bruises that were probably left on the backs of Natalka and Vasya.

The color white, when describing buildings, appears only three times in the entire cycle when describing buildings, and exclusively in reference to churches. This is not only "an iconic touch that contributes to the creation of a unique Central Russian rural landscape, dominated by the church" [1, p. 135], but also a symbol of a different, transformed life. Traditionally, churches are built in the most beautiful, open places, often on hills, so that they remind people from afar of the luminous and the divine. The sight of such a building elevates one above the dark peasant life and reminds one of the eternal.

In discussing the role of color in the existential space of nature in the stories of the cycle, it is important to note that Turgenev maintained a lifelong, profound interest in painting and collecting art throughout his life. Ivan Sergeevich has entered

literary history as a master of landscape descriptions, his style characterized by simplicity, concreteness, the play of light and shadow, and an exquisite color palette.

In the story “Bezhin Meadow” color acquires an additional negative connotation through its association with a shroud — the cloth in which the deceased was wrapped: “I was at once plunged into a disagreeable clinging dampness, exactly as though I had gone down into a cellar; the thick high grass at the bottom of the valley, all drenched with dew, was white like a smooth table-cloth; one felt afraid somehow to walk on it” [4, p. 87]. The lost narrator descends into a narrow valley, subconsciously reminiscent of a damp grave, and is seized by fear. This mortifying association is later realized literally in the story “Kasyan of Fair Springs”: “the coffin covered with a white cloth” [4, p. 106].

Shades of red are instrumental in creating a distinctive atmosphere associated with sunrise and sunset. In the story “The End of Chertopkhanov” the climactic moment of the proud nobleman’s separation from the freedom-loving gypsy is steeped in an ominous, dark red hue: “The sun was sinking on the horizon, and everything was suddenly suffused with purple glow — trees, grass, and earth alike” [4, c. 284]. The evocation of thick, clotted blood seemingly saturating the entire scene fosters in the reader, who is aware of the loaded pistol, a powerful sense of impending tragedy.

Horses played a vital role in both peasant and landowner life, consequently, their descriptions rightfully occupy a prominent place: “racehorses, dapple-grey, raven, and sorrel, with large hindquarters, flowing tails, and shaggy legs, stood in majestic immobility like lions” [4, p. 171]. However, the author does more than simply admire the graceful beauty of these noble animals. At times, a horse’s color proves pivotal in the plot, as, for example, in the story “The End of Chertopkhanov”. The hero is finally convinced that the returned horse is not his beloved Malek-Adel when he grasps a simple truth: over a year “Grey horses get lighter in colour!” [4, p. 307]. The figure of the horse has long been considered a polysemantic symbol. In Turgenev’s work, it functions as a mediator between worlds and essentially “transports” Chertopkhanov to the next world.

Thus, color is first and foremost an inalienable property of nature, an essential attribute of any natural fragment, a characteristic that exists beyond time.

Also of interest are the names of characters and places that implicitly carry chromatic meaning [2]. The study of proper names in this context is crucial, as they always reflect historical facts, cultural norms, foundational values, and traditions inherent to a particular time and people, and are also a primary means of creating an artistic image.

Turgenev dedicated two stories to the landowner Chertopkhanov, whose surname evokes associations with evil spirits, the color black, and the word “cursing”, by invoking the devil — “Cher-top-khanov” [4, p. 267] — as the hero, who

has stuttered since childhood, pronounces it. Indeed, his behavior and mannerisms suggest possession.

The toponymic title of the story “Lebedyan” establishes the main symbol and actualizes the reader’s associative potential. The city’s name derives from “the swan” (*lebed’*) that once inhabited the nearby Lebedyanka River, which is why its coat of arms still depicts a white swan on a blue background. This ornithological symbol is frequently employed in 19th-century discourse to describe the beauty and grace of a horse. In the 19th century, Lebedyan was famous for its horse fairs, one of which is described in the story. The author cleverly plays on a popular folk saying: “The breast of a *swan*, the gait of a *peacock*, the eyes of a *falcon*, the eyebrows of a *sable*” by including several horses with these very names (*Peacock*, *Falcon*, and *Ermine*) among those observed by the narrator. This allusion is made explicit in a description: “The dark-bay shaft-horse stood firmly, its neck arched like a *swan’s*” [4, p. 177].

Traditionally, the swan symbolizes noble qualities: most often love, fidelity, beauty, purity, and is associated with the color white; less often, deception and hypocrisy, since its snow-white plumage conceals its black body. Thus, the white color, implicitly included in the name of the city, enters into opposition with the surname of the steppe horse breeder Mr. Chernobai, who foists on the narrator a “broken-winded” horse [4, p. 180]. The horse trader’s surname (literally, “black storyteller”) directly points to the dark, duplicitous nature of this character. Black is the color of deception, evil deeds (“black deeds”), fraud, and something hidden from view. He doesn’t simply sell; he artfully spins fictions, deceiving buyers with beautiful but deceitful speeches.

Andryusha Belovzorov’s surname also carries negative semantics, constructed on the principle of a deceptive expectation. Superficially, it promises the image of a noble, luminous, open personality (literally, “white gaze”). However, the writer presents the complete opposite: “a stout, broad-shouldered fellow, with a big red face and greasy curly hair” whose “eyes [are] lost among layers of fat and, his cheeks puffed out and tense as drums” [4, p. 190]. While Turgenev typically attributes an attractive appearance to a healthy complexion, a smooth white forehead, white hands, and teeth, here the “white” in Belovzorov’s name signifies not purity, but emptiness, facelessness, and a lack of inner substance; his “gaze” is devoid of insight. The surname thus functions as an ironic commentary on the stark contrast between a beautiful, “speaking” name and the character’s soulless essence, expressing the complete inexpressiveness and spiritual void within him.

As a pictorial and expressive medium, color allows the author to convey his attitude toward the characters more vividly and to construct their psychological portraits.

By employing color to create character portraits, the writer not only vividly depicts their appearance but also delineates essential aspects of their personality and conveys his own attitude toward them. White in clothing typically signifies

neatness and cleanliness. A crucial element in the portrait characterization within the story “The Tryst” is the description of their clothing. Yet, Akulina’s white shirt, typical of a peasant girl’s dress — “Her clean white blouse, buttoned up at the throat and wrists, lay in short soft folds about her figure” [4, p. 236], stands in stark contrast to the tasteless outfit of “the pampered valet of some rich young gentleman”, where even a white shirt appears pretentious and absurd: “The round collar of his white shirt mercilessly propped up his ears and cut his cheeks” [4, p. 237].

It is essential to note the semantic ambivalence of the color white. On one hand, it is the color of purity and chastity. On the other, within Russian culture, it represents death and desolation and is frequently associated with supernatural being: “almost all evil spirits are dressed in white” [1, p. 154]. It is therefore no coincidence that, shortly before his death, Chertopkhanov has a nightmare vision of “a white fox, white as snow, ran to meet him...” [4, p. 296]. Similarly, in the “scary stories” told by the village boys in “Bezhin Meadow” mythical white wolves and a white werewolf lamb appear, while a white dove is perceived as a righteous soul on its way to heaven. The same cultural stratum includes folk beliefs about mermaids — maidens pallid skin, long green hair, and slender arms: “she herself was as bright and as *white* sitting on the branch as some dace or a roach, or like some little carp, so *white* and silvery <...> and her hair was green as hemp” [4, p. 94]. Gavriila calls her “*zel’ye*” (a potion or herb), a term that plays on multiple meanings simultaneously: the green hue of aquatic plants and mermaid hair, a love philtre, and a herbal concoction.

The mortal symbolism of the color white is also manifests in “The Singers”: “When at last Yakov uncovered his face, it was pale as a dead man’s:” [4, p. 216], and in “Chertopkhanov and Nedopyuskin”: “she had died <...> she had had a dream of a *white* figure riding on a bear” [4, p. 271].

Within the figurative system of the “Sketches from a Hunter’s Album” cycle, the color yellow in portraiture conveys the semantics of bodily decay and illness. This symbolism, however, undergoes a profound transformation in the climactic story “A Living Relic”. Lukerya’s portrait is rendered in an iconographic palette of golden-yellow tones, immediately establishing an oxymoronic unity of decay and holiness: “A head utterly withered, of a uniform *coppery* hue — like some very ancient ikon; <...> and from under the kerchief some thin wisps of *yellow* hair <...> two tiny hands of the same *coppery*” [4, p. 316]. This iconographic image stands in direct contrasts to the memory of her former, corporeal beauty: “This mummy, Lukerya — the greatest beauty in ail our household — that tall, plump, *pink-and-white*, singing, laughing, dancing creature!” [4, p. 328] — thereby accentuating the radical metamorphosis she has undergone.

Earthly illness is gradually reinterpreted as a sign of a different, spiritual existence. The “*coppery*” features of her face acquire a sacred dimension in their

details: “her dark lids, fringed with golden eyelashes, closed again, and were still as an ancient statue’s” [4, p. 322]. The culmination of this transformation is the heroine’s dream, built on the key colors of Christian symbolism — blue, white, and gold. In it, the final exchange of earthly attributes for heavenly ones occurs: instead of a wreath of cornflowers, a luminous “crescent moon” crowns her head “like a kokoshnik, and I was all brightness directly and I made the whole field light around” [4, p. 323]. This halo-like glow signifies a meeting not with an earthly bridegroom, but with the Heavenly Bridegroom. Thus, the yellow-gold palette, beginning as the color of diseased flesh, culminates as the color of a transformed spirit, visualizing the central idea of the story — the transition from a perishable physical existence to eternal spiritual life.

Red in “Sketches from a Hunter’s Album” is an invertible color, characterized by its dual effect, performing both a life-affirming and a life-destroying function. A distinctive element of the characters’ portraiture is their red hands and fingers, which often contrast with the rest of their appearance. The hero of “The Hamlet of Schigri Uyezd” remarks with irony upon the combination of red hands with the curls, blue eyes, and absurd diminutive names of the German’s grown-up daughters: “This professor had two daughters, of twenty-seven, such stumpy little things — God bless them! — with such majestic noses, frizzed curls and pale-blue eyes, and *red hands* with white nails. One was called Linchen and the other Minchen” [4, p. 257]. Red, thick fingers adorned with rings, along with a greasy arkhaluk, a faded tie, and unpolished boots, play a significant role in creating the image of Pyotr Petrovich Karataev: “He smelt strongly of tobacco and spirits; on his fat, *red fingers* almost hidden in his sleeves, could be seen silver and Tula rings” [4, p. 222].

A striking detail in the portrait of the vulgar, heartless, and depraved valet from the story “The Tryst” is “the *red crooked fingers*, adorned by gold and silver rings, with turquoise forget-me-nots” [4, p. 237]. The coldness and artificiality of the pale blue stone reveals the young rake’s true attitude toward Akulina. Her bouquet also contains these flowers: “«These are forgetme-nots, and that’s mint. And these I picked for you», she added, taking from under yellow tansy a small bunch of blue corn-flowers, tied up with a thin blade of grass” [4, c. 239]. A contrast is created between the living feelings of the girl, who will remember her lover even without flowers, and Victor’s indifferent promise to remember her.

It is noteworthy to observe the similarity between the characters in two distinct narratives, whose portraits are rendered using an identical chromatic scheme. The burgomaster from the story “The Steward” “was short, broad-shouldered, grey-haired, and thick-set, with a red nose, little *blue* eyes, and a beard of the shape of a fan” [4, p. 128]. “He wore a *blue* coat, girded with a red belt” [4, p. 130]. This is a cunning and cruel man, hypocritically refers to his master as a father while fraudulently enriching himself from his lands and peasants.

Blue color in the description of the characters' clothing, as noted above, symbolizes balance and reliability for Turgenev, thereby inspiring trust. In "Lebedyan" the old man "in along-skirted *blue* coat, <...> of medium height, with white hair, a friendly smile, and fine *blue* eyes" [4, p. 179] inspired such confidence in the narrator through his entire demeanor that he was able to sell a worthless horse to a man who appeared otherwise knowledgeable about such transactions.

The conducted research allows us to assert that the color system within the holistic artistic work functions as an independent semiotic structure, possessing a high degree of semantic autonomy and conceptual significance. Ultimately, the color continuum of "Sketches from a Hunter's Album" emerges as a fundamental component of Turgenev's idiosyncrasy, embodying its aesthetic program. It ensures a synthesis of pictorial concreteness and symbolic depth, objective observation and lyrical experience. The study of this system confirms that the analysis of the text's color organization is not an auxiliary, but a strategic method of literary criticism, providing access to hidden layers of the author's intent and enabling a holistic understanding of the artistic universe of a classic work.

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THE POST-APOCALYPTIC GENRE IN VLADIMIR SOROKIN'S PROSE

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The article discusses the poetics of the modern post-apocalyptic novel, the poetic originality of the second chapter of V. Sorokin's novel "Telluria," and explores the fabulation of V. Sorokin's novel "Telluria," as well as the characteristics of the post-apocalyptic genre and the poetics of postmodernism.

Keywords: *post-apocalypse, Vladimir Sorokin, "Telluria," post-apocalyptic genre poetics, fabulation, and postmodernism.*

Works about a global catastrophe after the apocalypse gained widespread popularity after World War II due to concerns about the use of nuclear weapons, but the post-apocalypse genre actually originated in the 19th century.

The main idea of this genre in literature is that a characteristic feature of post-apocalyptic fiction is the development of a plot in a world (or a limited part of it) with a specific history. In the past of this world, civilization reached a high level of social and technological development, but then the world experienced a global catastrophe that destroyed civilization and most of its wealth.

The most common catastrophes that have destroyed the world include: a third world war involving weapons of mass destruction (nuclear, chemical, or biological), an alien invasion, a machine uprising led by artificial intelligence (robots; see also the problem of controlling artificial intelligence), a pandemic, the fall of an asteroid, the mass appearance of monsters (including those created by humans, from a parallel universe, prehistoric, or from other times, alien, or other), a climate change caused by an impact from another time, a natural disaster (non-living), or other catastrophes. [2].

A typical post-apocalyptic plot usually begins to develop a considerable time after the catastrophe, when its "lethal factors" have ceased to be effective. In one form or another, the reader is usually presented with a summary of the society's history since the catastrophe: immediately after the catastrophe, there is a period of savagery, followed by the survivors concentrating around the remaining sources

of sustenance and the spontaneous formation of various new social structures. By the time the plot begins, this process is usually complete, and a conglomerate of communities has formed in the habitable territory, establishing a more or less stable balance of power.

Post-apocalyptic works do not describe the end of the world, but rather a catastrophe that leads to the end of human civilization. Most people die. The events that follow take place “outside of civilization.” It is these events that are of interest to the reader.

Post-apocalyptic stories are based on mythology and religion. Rebecca Roanhorse’s novel “The Trail of the Lightning” depicts a post-flood Earth. One of the Navajo reservations has managed to survive behind a wall they have strategically built around their settlement, and they are now struggling to survive in a world where even the gods have returned. The novel incorporates Navajo words, characters, demons, and creatures from the tribe’s legends and stories.

Mythological post-apocalypse. For example, in Pavel Mikey’s novel “The World of Worlds,” the world is depicted after the Martians dropped mythobombs on Earth. This weapon was intended to bring Earthlings to submission, but the Earthlings refused to submit to the Martians and their technology.

In literature of this genre, events often take place in large cities or even more significant territorial entities. Typically, these cities are unaffected or minimally affected by the disaster, preserving the “old” way of life that gradually changes under the influence of external factors.

In the description of the setting, there are usually locations such as abandoned or partially destroyed cities, factories, military facilities, underground areas, subways, and vast deserts in place of previously inhabited territories. These territories were previously on land but were flooded by the sea as a result of a disaster. Buildings and man-made structures are located on the seafloor. These locations are sometimes dangerous and sometimes useful, but they are usually just used as a backdrop for the story.

The works feature mutated humans, animals, plants, and entire mutant forests (interesting examples of mutant humans in T. Tolstoy’s “Kys”).

The plot may revolve around the adventures of the characters in the world, particularly the journey of the hero to a place or object that will provide him with a long and prosperous life, allowing him to save his community from destruction, or even help revive the entire civilization. In some cases, the means and technologies that led to the catastrophe may be considered taboo in society, and the tranquility of this pastoral society is disrupted by young rebels who seek to revive the forbidden technology.

Often, apocalyptic literature combines elements of post-apocalyptic literature, depicting the aftermath of a catastrophe and its impact on the lives of survivors.

In some cases, the narrative explores the perception of modern reality through the lens of future generations. This genre often overlaps with cyberpunk in literature.

Telluria is the tenth novel by Vladimir Sorokin. It was published on October 15, 2013, by the Corpus publishing house. It was awarded the second Bolshaya Kniga Prize (2013–2014 season).

Telluria by Vladimir Sorokin is a look at the future of Europe, which, despite the drastic changes in the world and human society, seems very clear and real.

Vladimir Sorokin's post-apocalyptic novel "Telluria" is a dystopia in which Russia, in its current form, has finally ceased to exist. "Telluria" presents the most comprehensive and multifaceted vision of the future world.

The book lacks a coherent plot and is divided into 50 chapters without titles (short novellas), numbered with Roman numerals. The characters in the chapters rarely intersect. The novel is assembled using the collage principle. The novel takes place in the middle of the 21st century, in a territory stretching from the Altai Mountains to Madrid. After a global war with the Wahhabis, Europe has returned to the Middle Ages, and the Knights Templar have taken power. Russia has fragmented into various principalities, some of which have embraced Orthodox communism.

In the genre of post-apocalyptic literature, it is common for the protagonists to inhabit isolated, high-tech, and compact communities that have been formed on the basis of large military bases, scientific towns, orbital stations, or even specially constructed shelters in anticipation of a catastrophe. In Sorokin's novel, there are descriptions of various types of societies, including democratic, totalitarian, and those ruled by radical military leaders, scientists, or controversial political figures. These societies possess the most dangerous technologies that have been preserved from pre-catastrophic times. Typically, these communities maintain a degree of isolation from the outside world.

It is in space that times coexist, and it is through space that different times appear as simultaneous times. The opening of local chronotopes is achieved through the conditional timelessness of space, and the text of "Telluria" itself embodies this chronotope through its structure. [1]. The artistic time of the novel is conventionally set in the "post-" catastrophe era. In other words, the novel is conventionally classified as a post-apocalyptic genre.

The novel "Telluria" is a parody of the search for the meaning of history, developing the idea of the referential illusion of historians, that is, the description of a fictional reality. For this purpose, both fabulation and pastiche are used, and non-overlapping storylines are combined in the novel, and instead of one theme, there are 50 themes, corresponding to the number of chapters in the novel.

One of the central operating locations is Altai. The Altai republic of Telluria is located there. In this republic, magic nails are made from the rare material tellurium, which are in great demand all over the world. This is a powerful drug: if you

hammer such a nail into the head in a strictly defined place, you can experience incomparable pleasure. From now on, the most sought — after profession is a carpenter, who hammers tellurium nails quickly and painlessly. This mythological element of the novel is a direct reference to Ottavio Vannini's painting "Jael and Sisera," which inspired the concept of "Telluria."

"Telluria" is a majestic panorama of ruins. The spaces of the state are full of artifacts of a lost civilization: ruins, stones and boulders, rusty iron, bones, fragments of Russian pottery, and bricks from the wall that once surrounded Muscovy. The novel has two "preliminary novels." Sorokin deliberately refers the reader to "The Day of the Oprichnik" and "The Sugar Kremlin," where the origin of this wall (then still intact) is described in detail.

In modern literature, a mythologeme is often referred to as a mythological motif that has been consciously transferred to the world of modern artistic culture. In "Telluria," there is a mythologeme of "Anglo-Saxon sobriety" and a mythologeme about a higher, developed West, which is revealed in Chapter 2 of the novel.

"See you in my native neo-imperial skull, full of brain fog and Anglo-Saxon sobriety," writes Leo, the protagonist, in a letter to the West in Chapter 2. (Telluria, Chapter 2)

His letter and his homosexuality are an allusion to the Marquis de Custine. The Marquis Astolphe de Custine visited Russia in 1839 and wrote a book about his impressions of Moscow, Yaroslavl, St. Petersburg, and other cities. The Marquis de Custine was a staunch monarchist, a conservative, and a reactionary. He feared democracy in France and the power of the mob. In Russia, Custine hoped to find arguments against the democratic form of government, but he was shocked by the Russian form of autocracy.

Astolphe de Custine's book "Russia in 1839" was banned in Russia by Emperor Nicholas I. To this end, the Marquis's alleged homosexuality was invented. This was due to the book's unflattering portrayal of the emperor and Russian customs. Marquis de Custine wrote, "To live in Russia, it is not enough to conceal your thoughts; you must also be able to pretend. The former is useful, but the latter is necessary." (Custine de Astolphe, "Russia in 1839. Volume 1.")

The book provoked a reaction of rejection in Russia. In Tsarist and Soviet Russia, the full text of Custine's book could only be accessed through French originals that were illegally imported into the country. Some quotes from the book are provocative: "The Russian Empire is a camp-like discipline instead of a government, a state of siege elevated to the status of a normal state of society" (Custine de Astolphe, "Russia in 1839. Volume 1").

Sorokin takes turns stylizing all the significant genres of Russian, European, and American literature. These include epics, folk tales, chivalric romances, socialist-realist industrial novels, Orthodox prayers, communist advertisements,

love plots, reports, and eulogies. The eulogy is a parody in honor of tellurium, a “fragile silver-white metal” that grants all wishes. This technique is consistent throughout the 50 chapters.

Sorokin carefully describes a social system that combines elements of feudalism, communism, and theocracy. Advances in genetics have finally allowed for a physiological division of classes, not only financially and in terms of living standards, but also physiologically. The first class, the upper class of society, consists of tiny individuals. They are the size of a beer bottle. They do not work and possess a paradoxical ability to enslave others. The second class, the middle class, consists of individuals with normal physical characteristics. 3rd class, laborers — stupid and often weak-willed giants who do the most menial work for a pittance. 4th class, service personnel — others (zoomorphs and others).

After the catastrophe, the countries were divided into small republics, orders, and principalities. Social injustice is no longer perceived as a personal offense. However, the only happiness in the future is a tellurium nail. This special metal interacts with the human brain, providing complete and absolute happiness. Insert a tellurium nail into your head and do what you’ve always wanted to do. This is an allegory of the ideology of self-denial, of being in the name of a higher idea, which is a very strong allusion to the communist ideology and the Russian philosophical idea.

This is tellurium, the metalloid that gave the book its name. It is a metaphor for propaganda that can be implanted in anyone, a metaphor for ideology, and a metaphor for the religion of Sufism. People want to use nails made of tellurium metal, and they drive them into their heads. The driven nails are undoubtedly an allusion to the ideology that makes people in Russia happy. Happiness is replaced by a single tellurium nail.

The word “telluria” has another meaning: tellurium (from Latin. tellus — “Earth”) is a device for visual demonstration of the annual motion of the Earth around the Sun and the daily rotation of the Earth around its axis. Also, “tellurium” can be called a mechanical model of the Solar system.

Sorokin, through fascinating allusions, gives messages to our time. In his work, the author not only warns us what awaits us if the world does not change, but also suggests looking at these changes through the eyes of a person from the post-Soviet space.

We can also mention the energetic and repeatedly realized genre of dystopia by writers. This genre is also interesting to Vladimir Sorokin. The ideas of dystopia, the “dark future,” can be used in the genre of post-apocalypse. Dystopia is characterized by the presence of an undesirable society (community, influential group of individuals), dehumanization, and other features of decline, collapse, and disintegration of society, a totalitarian form of government, and an environmental catastrophe. Dystopia addresses real-life issues in politics, religion, technology, and economics.

The main feature of the poetics of V. Sorokin's novels is fabulation. This term comes from psychology and refers to the blending of fiction and reality in speech and memory. The postmodern writer specifically emphasizes free fiction and pure creativity. If we consider the poetics of novels using fabulation as a process of unfolding metaphors (V. Humboldt, G. Shpet, and A. F. Losev) and absurdity as a result of the logical method of *reductio ad absurdum*, then fabulation is a conditional truth. Any artistic reality described in the world of the novel becomes more tangible than the history of world politics. "My sweet, most venerable boy (My sweet, most venerable boy), here I am in Muscovy. Everything happened faster and easier than usual. However, they say it is much easier to enter this state than to leave it." (Telluria, Chapter 2)

The second main feature of Sorokin's work is intertextuality. He perceives the existing world as a text, and the inclusion of one work in another is inevitable (the principle of the matryoshka doll), as the artist in postmodernism is merely a carrier of a vast dictionary from which he draws information. In Sorokin's texts, intertextuality manifests itself at various levels: semantic, stylistic, and direct quotation.

In Sorokin's new, secular apocalyptic mythologem, one can observe the stylistic features of postmodernism. The material for this is the "serial" plots of the apocalypse. Post-apocalypse makes the most extensive use of postmodern concepts of imaginary nostalgia for the past.

The novel "Telluria" is a mixture of alternative history and social fiction in the style of postmodernism.

Post-apocalypse embodies two aspects of postmodernism: a sense of time without a future or a past. The narrative in post-apocalyptic literature is based on myths, archetypes, and timeless stories, and the characters' stories are presented as individual "quests" within a larger narrative. Post-apocalypse is a softened role-playing game with already established and well-known mythologems, which does not require becoming an "initiate."

The fictional world is always bleak: in Telluria, we find ourselves in a developed city where feudalism reigns. Religious orders flourish, and there is a heavy and bloody war against the Mujahideen invaders, who have taken over much of Europe and Asia. The Chinese have purchased the Moscow region and established a foothold in Eastern Russia. New crusades are taking place, but they are led by robots rather than humans. In this new world, small-scale industries and manufactories thrive. A change in the production regime has led to a different consumption regime.

The world of the novel has the effect of a reality that claims to be a game, and the world of Telluria is a role-playing "universe" with many different conflicts and detailed settings.

Post-apocalyptic fiction is one of the components of the eschatological discourse, which reflects the collective fear of the future. Depictions of the destruction

of humanity can be found in all developed mythologies (Ragnarök, the Apocalypse, the Flood, etc.). In the early 21st century, post-apocalyptic themes have become increasingly relevant to society and writers, leading to the development of the post-apocalyptic genre in science fiction and literature.

“Telluria” is a dystopia, but not a military one, but a satirical one: political phobias, ideological manias, and the absurdity of our era. In this diverse world, there are totalitarianism, Chineseization, Stalinism, Islamization, bioterrorism, and Orthodox communism.

In a 2018 interview, V. Sorokin said that he had a feeling that “a giant was dying, and its name was the Whole Picture of the World.” (3) The world of post-apocalypse is a patchwork of colors, loosely connected by a storyline, which is one of the main techniques of postmodernism.

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METHODS OF RENDERING ENGLISH VOWEL SOUNDS IN WRITING

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the problem of graphic spelling of English vowel sounds (monophthongs, diphthongs and diphthongoids) in educational activities of pedagogical workers in English classes at educational institutions in the Russian Federation. The authors identify the main ways of graphic spelling of the phonemes, namely letters, combinations of letters and punctuation marks and letters used in the formation of the sounds in question.*

Key words: *diphthongoids, diphthongs, educational activities, English, graphic spelling, monophthongs, pedagogical worker.*

In 2012, the Russian Legislature adopted *Federal Act “About Education in the Russian Federation”* [8]. Under the Act, none but educational institutions, organizations carrying out education and individual entrepreneurs are entitled to render educational activities [8. Article 21]. The Act stipulates that individual entrepreneurs render educational activities directly or indirectly by employing pedagogical workers [8. Article 32]. The educational activities of individual entrepreneurs within the framework of teaching English cover a very diverse target audience that includes pre-school children, students of secondary and higher educational institutions, individuals, representatives of legal entities.

The year of 2015 initiated our research which was planned that same year, done in 2015–2025 and approved in 2025 at *In. Yaz. — Foreign Languages, Interpretation and Translation Center*. In English classes, we observed the students experience phonetic and spelling problems while learning English words containing one and the same letter or a combination of the same letters pronounced

differently in definite cases, e.g. the vowel letter *a* in the following words: *after* — [a:], *age* — [eɪ], *ago* — [ə], *all* — [o:], *ant* — [æ], *Bologna* — [jə], *climate* — [ɪ], *parent* — [ɛə], *watch* — [ɔ]; the combination of vowel and consonant letters *our*: *sour* — [sauə], *tumour* — [ə], *courtesy* — [ʒ:], *concourse* — [o:], *tour* — [uə]; the combination of consonant letters *ch*, e.g. *chef* — [ʃ], *chess* — [tʃ], *chorus* — [k], *sandwich* — [dʒ].

The relevance of the research work arose in the background of insufficient coverage of the declared topic in the educational process carried out by individual entrepreneurs in the Russian Federation. The introductory [10], introductory and phonetic courses [6], English phonetics [15] and phonology manuals [14], [20] at that time did not allow us to find irrefragable answers to all questions of the students regarding the multiple ways of graphical spelling of vowel and consonant phonemes. That demand prompted us to study the problem thoroughly.

The material of the research work consisted of various texts taken for our consideration from pieces of literature, periodicals, the Internet. We also dealt with business correspondence, films, advertising; explanatory [5], [7], [17] and on-line dictionaries [11], [12], [13]; guides to contemporary English pronunciation [16], [18], [19]. We examined the parts of speech and their transformations regarding tense, voice, number, case, degree, mood categories. It seemed natural for us to view abbreviations, acronyms, interjections and loan words, paying particular attention to such toponyms [3] as the names of cities, continents, countries, days of the week, months, nationalities, people's names, patronymics and sur-names, rivers, salads, social networks, seas, stars, states, wines, etc. In this article, we endeavour to compile and systematize the ways of graphical spelling of 2 diphthongoids, 10 monophthongs and 8 diphthongs [2], [4], [6] omitting other 12 vowel consonant sounds [9], [10].

Vowel sound [i:] can be represented by vowel letters *e* (*genius* ['dʒi: nəs]), *i* (*fatigue* [fə'ti: g]), by consonant letters *b* (*BBC* [bi: bi: 'si:]), *c* (*CNN* [si: en'en]), *d* (*PhD* [pi: eɪf'di:]), *g* (*NGO* [endʒi: 'əv]), *p* (*PA* [pi: 'ei]), *t* (*t-shirt* ['ti: fə: t]), *v* (*VIP* [vi: ai'pi:]), *z* (*Zz* [zi:]), by French letter *i* (*naïve* [nai' i: v] or [na: 'i: v] or *naive* [na: 'i: v]), and by groups of letters *ae* (*algae* ['ældʒi:]), *ea* (*grease* [gri: s]), *ee* (*seethe* [si: ð]), *eh* (*vehicle* ['vi: ɪkl]), *ei* (*protein* ['prəʊti: n]), *eo* (*people* ['pi: pl]), *ey* (*key* [ki:]), *ie* (*retrieve* [ri'tri: v]), *oe* (*Phoenix* ['fi: nks]), *uay* (*quay* ['ki:]). Sound [i:] can be put in the opening (*eat* [i: t]), central (*scheme* [ski: m]) and ending (*payee* [pei' i:]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral position. Diphthongoid [i:] is represented by three vowel letters (*e*, *i*, *ï*), by eight consonant letters (*b*, *c*, *d*, *g*, *p*, *t*, *v*, *z*) and by 10 groups of letters (*ae*, *ea*, *ee*, *eh*, *ei*, *eo*, *ey*, *ie*, *oe*, *uay*). In nine cases, this phoneme is made in graphic spelling by groups of vowel letters (*ae*, *ea*, *ee*, *ei*, *eo*, *ey*, *ie*, *oe*, *uay*) and in one case by a group of a vowel and consonant letters (*eh*).

Vowel sound [u:] can be represented by vowel letters *o* (*tomb* [tu: m]), *u* (*ruth* [ru: θ]), by consonant letters *q* (*IQ* [ai'kju:]), *w* (*WC dAblju: 'si:ʃ*) and by groups of letters *eau* (*beauty* ['bju: ti]), *eu* (*pharmaceutical* [fa: mə'sju: tikəl]), *eu* or *oeu* (*maneuver* or *manoeuver* [mə'nu: və]), *ew* (*screw* [skru:]), *heu* (*rheum* [ru: m]), *hou* (*ghoul* [gu: l]), *iew* (*review* [ri'vju:]), *oe* (*canoe* [kə'nu:]), *oo* (*maroon* [mə'ru: n]), *ou* (*acoustics* [ə'ku: stiks]), *ough* (*through* [θru:]), *ue* (*rue* [ru:]), *ueue* (*queue* [kju:]), *ui* (*bruise* [bru: z]), *wo* (*two* [tu:]). Sound [u:] can be put in the opening (*Oops* [u: ps]), central (*shrewd* [fru: d]) and ending (*bamboo* [bæm'bu:]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral position. Diphthongoid [u:] is represented by two vowel letters (*o*, *u*), two consonant letters (*q*, *w*) and by 16 groups of letters (*eau*, *eu*, *eu*, *ew*, *heu*, *hou*, *iew*, *oe*, *oeu*, *oo*, *ou*, *ough*, *ue*, *ueue*, *ui*, *wo*). In ten cases, this phoneme is made in graphic spelling by groups of vowel letters (*eau*, *eu*, *eu*, *oe*, *oeu*, *oo*, *ou*, *ue*, *ueue*, *ui*) and in six cases by groups of vowel and consonant letters (*ew*, *heu*, *hou*, *iew*, *ough*, *wo*).

Vowel sound [ʌ] can be represented by English letters *o* (e.g., *dozen* ['dʌzn]), *u* (*thus* [ðʌs]), *w* (*WTO* [dʌblju: ti: 'əʊ]) and by groups of letters *oe* (*does* [dʌz]), *oo* (*blood* [blʌd]), *ou* (*double* ['dʌbl]), *uh* (*uh-huh* [ʌ'hʌ]) or [ʊ'hʊ]). Sound [ʌ] can be put in the opening (*oven* ['ʌvn] or ['ʌvən]) and central (*flood* [flʌd]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral and ending position of lexical units. Monophthong [ʌ] is represented by two vowel letters (*o*, *u*), one consonant letter (*w*), three groups of vowel letters (*oe*, *oo*, *ou*). In one case, this phoneme is made in graphic spelling by a group of a vowel and consonant letters (*uh*).

Vowel sound [a:] can be represented by letters *a* (*disater* [diz'a: stə]), *e* (*ensemble* [a: n'sa: mbl]), *r* (*R&D* [a:(r)ən'di:]), and by groups of letters *ah* (*Ah* [a:]), *al* (*almond* ['a: mænd]), *ar* (*arc* [a: k]), *are* (*aren't* ['a: nt]), *arre* (*bizarre* [bi'za:]), *au* (*laugh* [la: f]), *ear* (*hearth* [ha: θ]), *er* (*sergeant* ['sa: dʒənt]), *ir* (*memoir* [mem'wa:]), *oi* (*turquoise* ['tə: kwa: z]), *ois* (*bourgeois* ['buəʒwa:]), *uar* (*guard* [ga: d]). Sound [a:] can be put in the neutral (*Ah* [a:]), opening (*ask* [a: sk]), central (*barley* ['ba: li]) and ending (*spa* [spa:]) position of lexical units. Monophthong [a:] is represented by two vowel letters (*a*, *e*), one consonant letter (*r*) and 12 groups of letters (*Ah*, *al*, *ar*, *are*, *arre*, *au*, *ear*, *er*, *ir*, *oi*, *ois*, *uar*). In two cases, this phoneme is made in graphic spelling by groups of vowel letters (*au*, *oi*), in ten cases by groups of vowel and consonant letters (*Ah*, *al*, *ar*, *are*, *arre*, *ear*, *er*, *ir*, *ois*, *uar*).

Vowel sound [ɪ] can be represented by letters *a* (*image* ['ɪmɪdʒ]), *e* (*depart* [di'pa: t]), *e* or *i* (*enquire/inquire* [ɪn'kwɪə]), *i* (*inlet* ['ɪnlet]), *o* (*women* ['wɪmɪn]), *u* (*busy* ['bɪzi]), *y* (*hymn* [hɪm]), by French letter *é* (*protégé* ['prɔtʒeɪ]) and by groups of the letters *ae* (*palaeontology* [pælɪɔn'tɔlədʒɪ]), *ai* (*fountain* ['fauntɪn]), *ay* (*Friday* ['fraɪdi]), *ea* (*Guinea* ['ɡɪni]), *ee* (*yankee* ['jæŋki]), *ehea* (*forehead* ['fɔrɪd]), *ei* (*forfeit* ['fo: fit]), *eig* (*sovereign* ['sovərɪn]), *eo* (*pigeon* ['pɪdʒɪn] or ['pɪdʒən]), *ey* (*kidney* ['kɪdni]), *ia* (*marriage* ['mæɪrɪdʒ]), *ie* (*kerchief* ['kə: tʃɪf]),

ui (*guild* [gɪld]), *wi* (*Greenwich* ['grɪndʒ]). Sound [ɪ] can be put in the opening (*ink* [ɪŋk]), central (*climate* ['klaɪmɪt]) and ending (*plenty* ['plenti]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral position.

Vowel sound [ɔ] can be represented by letters *a* (*wrath* [rɔθ]), *e* (*entrepreneur* [ɛntrəprə'nə:] or [a: ntrəprə'nə:]), *o* (*inoculate* [ɪ'nɔkjuleɪt]) and by groups of letters *ach* (*yacht* [jɔt]), *au* (*sausage* ['sɔsɪdʒ]), *ea* (*Sean* [ʃɔn]), *ho* (*honest* ['ɔnɪst]), *oh* (*John* [dʒɔn]), *ou* (*lough* [lɔh]), *ow* (*knowledge* ['nɔlɪdʒ]). Sound [ɔ] can be put in the opening (*onto* ['ɔntu:]) and central (*pond* [pɔnd]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral and ending position of lexical units.

Vowel sound [o:] can be represented by letters *a* (*gall* [go: l]), *o* (*sanatorium* [sænə'to: rɪəm]) and by groups of letters *al* (*stalk* [sto: k]), *aor* (*extraordinary* [ɪks'tro: dənəri]), *ar* (*swarm* [swo: m]), *au* (*taunt* [to: nt]), *au* (*naught* [no: t]), *aw* (*thaw* [θo:]), *awe* (*awesome* ['o: səm]), *hau* (*haut* or *haute* [o: t]), *oa* (*broad* [bro: d]), *oar* (*hoard* [ho: d]), *oor* (*floor* [flo:]), *or* (*enforce* [ɪn'fo: s]), *ore* (*pore* [po:]), *orps* (*corps* [ko:]), *ort* (*rapport* [ræ'po:]), *ough* (*ought* [o: t]), *our* (*four* [fo:]), *wor* (*sword* [so: d]). Sound [o:] can be put in the neutral (*or* [o:]), opening (*all* [o: l]), central (*walk* [wo: k]) and ending (*door* [do:]) position of lexical units.

Vowel sound [ʊ] can be represented by letters *o* (*bosom* ['bʊzəm]), *u* (*bull* [bʊl]) and by groups of letters *oo* (*nook* [nʊk]), *ou* (*haute couture* [əʊtkʊ'tjʊə]), *oul* (*should* [ʃʊd]). Sound [ʊ] can be put in the opening (*Ugh* [ʊh]) and central (*butcher* ['bʊtʃə]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral and ending position of lexical units.

Vowel sound [æ] can be represented by letters *a* (*acrid* ['ækɪd]), *i* (*meringue* [mæ'ræŋ]) and by groups of letters *ai* (*plait* [plæɪ]), *a'a* (*ma'am* [mæm]), *ua* (*guarantee* [gærən'ti:]). Sound [æ] can be put in the opening (*act* [ækt]), central (*pad* [pæd]) and ending (*Nah* or *Nahh* [næ]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral position.

Vowel sound [e] can be represented by letters *a* (*ate* [et] or [eit]), *e* (*peril* ['perəl]), *u* (*bury* ['berɪ]), *f* (*FOB* [efəʊ'bi:]), *l* (*LTD* [elti:'di:]), *m* (*BMW* [bi: em'dAbɪju:]), *n* (*NGO* [endʒi:'əv:]), *s* (*SOS* [esəʊ'es]), *x* (*x-ray* ['eksreɪ]), *z* (*ZT* [zed'ti:]), by French letter *é* (*apéritif* [ə'perəti: f]) and by groups of letters *ai* (*said* [sed]), *ea* (*pleather* ['pledə]), *eg* (*phlegm* [flem]), *ei* (*leisure* ['leɪʒə]), *eo* (*jeopardize* ['dʒepə'daɪz]), *ie* (*friend* [frend]), *ue* (*baguette* [bæ'get]). Sound [e] can be put in the opening (*embassy* ['embəsi]) and central (*twenty* ['twenti]) position of words. One does not meet it in the neutral and ending position of lexical units.

Vowel sound [ə:] can be represented by groups of letters *ieu* (*milieu* ['mi:ljə:]), *ear* (*pearl* [pə: l]), *eor* (*George* [dʒə: dʒ]), *er* (*tertiary* ['tə: ʃəri]), *ere* (*were* [wə:]), *err* (*inferred* [ɪn'fə: d]), *eur* (*amateur* ['æmətə:] or ['æmətə]), *ir* (*dirge* [dɜ: dʒ]), *olo* (*colonel* ['kə: nəl]), *or* (*attorney* [ə'tə: ni]), *our* (*courtesy* ['kə: təsi]), *ur* (*nocturnal* [nɔk'tə: nəl]). Sound [ə:] can be put in the neutral (*Er* [ə:]),

opening (*earnest* [ˈəː nɪst]), central (*hurt* [ˈhəː t]) and ending (*infer* [ɪnˈfəː]) position of lexical units.

Vowel sound [ə] can be represented by letters *a* (*abrupt* [əˈbrʌpt]), *e* (*fraudulent* [ˈfroː djələnt]), *i* (*principal* [ˈprɪnsəpl]), *o* (*custody* [ˈkʌstədi]), *u* (*focus* [ˈfəʊkəs]) and by groups of letters *ai* (*villain* [ˈvɪlən]), *ar* (*leopard* [ˈlepəd]), *ay* (*always* [ˈoː lwəz] or [ˈoː lweɪz]), *ea* (*sergeant* [ˈsaː dʒənt]), *eo* (*sturgeon* [ˈstəː dʒən]), *eou* (*outrageous* [autˈreɪdʒəs]), *er* (*southern* [ˈsʌðən]), *er* or *re* (*fibre* or *fiber* [ˈfɪəbə]), *eu* (*pasteurize* [ˈpæstʃəraɪz]), *eur* (*chauffeur* [ˈʃəʊfə] or [ˈʃəʊfəː]), *gh* (*Edinburgh* [ˈedɪnb(ə)rə]), *hu* (*sorghum* [ˈsoː gəm]), *ia* (*initial* [ɪˈnɪʃəl]), *ie* (*sufficient* [səˈfɪʃənt]), *io* (*tension* [ˈtenʃən]), *iou* (*vicious* [ˈvɪʃəs]), *iour* (*saviour* [ˈseɪvɪə]), *iu* (*premium* [ˈpriː mjəm] or [ˈpriː miəm]), *oar* (*cupboard* [ˈkʌbəd]), *oi* (*tortoise* [ˈtoː təs]), *or* (*tailor* [ˈteɪlə]), *ou* (*ominous* [ˈɒmɪnəs]), *ough* (*thorough* [ˈθʌrə]), *o(u)r* (*vigour* or *vigor* [ˈvɪgə]), *re* (*macabre* [məˈkaː bə] or [məˈkaː br]), *ue* (*guerilla* [gəˈrɪlə]), *uer* (*lacquer* [ˈlækə]), *uor* (*liquor* [ˈlɪkə]), *ur* (*surmountable* [səˈmaʊntəbl]), *ure* (*torture* [ˈtoː tʃə]), *wer* (*answer* [ˈaː nsə]), by a combination of the apostrophe (‘), a consonant and a vowel letters (*re* (*we’re* [ˈwiːə]), a vowel letter and the apostrophe *o’* (*o’clock* [əˈklɒk]). Sound [ə] can be put in the opening (*about* [əˈbaʊt]), central (*tenant* [ˈtenənt]), central and ending simultaneously (*opera* [ˈɒpərə]) and ending (*clever* [ˈklevə]) position of lexical units. One does not meet it in the neutral position. Monophthong [ə] is represented by five letters (*a*, *e*, *i*, *o*, *u*), by 30 groups of letters (*ai*, *ar*, *ay*, *ea*, *eo*, *eou*, *er*, *eu*, *eur*, *gh*, *hu*, *ia*, *ie*, *io*, *iou*, *iour*, *iu*, *oar*, *oi*, *or*, *ou*, *ough*, *o(u)r*, *re*, *ue*, *uer*, *uor*, *ur*, *ure*, *wer*), by one group of consonant letters (*gh*), by one combination of a punctuation sign (the apostrophe), a consonant and a vowel letters (*re*) and by one combination of a vowel letter and a punctuation sign (the apostrophe) (*o’*). In 14 cases, this phoneme is made in graphic spelling by groups of vowel letters (*ai*, *ay*, *ea*, *eo*, *eou*, *eu*, *ia*, *ie*, *io*, *iou*, *iu*, *oi*, *ou*, *ue*), in 15 cases by a group of vowel and consonant letters (*ar*, *er*, *eur*, *hu*, *iour*, *oar*, *or*, *ough*, *o(u)r*, *re*, *uer*, *uor*, *ur*, *ure*, *wer*), in one case by a group of consonant letters (*gh*).

The vowel sound [aʊ] can be represented by combinations of English letters *au* (e.g. *Saudi Arabia* — [sɑʊdɪˈreɪbiə]), *ou* (*tousle* — [ˈtaʊzl] or [ˈtaʊzəl]), *ough* (*plough* — [plau]), *ow* (*scowl* — [skaul]). The sound [aʊ] can be placed in the zero (*Ow* — [aʊ]), initial (*out* — [aʊt]), middle (*house* — [haʊs]) and final (*brow* — [braʊ]) position of words. The diphthong [aʊ] is represented by four combinations of letters (*au*, *ou*, *ough*, *ow*). In two cases, this phoneme is formed in graphic spelling by combinations of vowel letters (*au*, *ou*) and in two cases — by combinations of vowel and consonant letters (*ough*, *ow*).

The vowel sound [ɔɪ] can be represented by combinations of letters *oi* (*moist* — [mɔɪst]), *ois* (*Illinois* — [ɪlɪˈnɔɪ]), *oy* (*deploy* — [dɪˈplɔɪ]). The sound [ɔɪ] can be placed in the initial (*oyster* — [ˈɔɪstə]), middle (*avoid* — [əˈvɔɪd]) and final

(*destroy* — [di'strɔɪ]) position of words. The diphthong [ɔɪ] is represented by three combinations of letters (*oi, ois, oy*). In two cases, this phoneme is formed in graphic spelling by combinations of vowel letters (*oi, oy*) and in one case — by a combination of vowel and consonant letters (*ois*).

The vowel sound [ɪə] can be represented by the letter *e* (*query* — [ˈkwɪəri]) and by combinations of letters *ea* (*ideal* — [ai'diəl]), *ear* (*sear* — [sɪə]), *eer* (*veneer* — [vi'niə] or [və'niə]), *eir* (*weird* — [wiəd]), *eo* (*theory* — [ˈθiəri]), *eou* (*hideous* — [ˈhidiəs]), *ere* (*adhere* — [əd'hiə]), *eu* (*linoleum* — [li'nəʊliəm]), *hea* (*gonorrhoea* — [gɒnə'riə]), *ia* (*guardian* — [ˈga:diən]), *iar* (*peculiar* — [pi'kju:liə]), *ie* (*nutrient* — [ˈnju:triənt]), *ier* (*pierce* — [piəs]), *io* (*oblivion* — [əb'liviən]), *ior* (*warrior* — [ˈwɔriə]), *iou* (*tedious* — [ˈti:diəs]), *ir* (*souvenir* — [su:və'niə]), *iu* (*premium* — [ˈpri:miəm]), *ya* (*Libya* — [ˈlibiə]). The sound [iə] can be placed in the zero (*ear* — [ɪə]), initial (*earshot* — [ˈɪʃɔt]), middle (*material* — [mə'tiəriəl]) and final (*fear* — [fiə]) position of words.

The vowel sound [əʊ] can be represented by the letter *o* (*rodent* — [ˈrəʊdnt] or [ˈrəʊdənt]) and by combinations of letters *ooh* (*pharaoh* — [ˈfɛərəʊ]), *au* (*sauté* — [ˈsəʊteɪ]), *eau* (*plateau* — [ˈplætəʊ]), *eou* (*Seoul* — [səʊl]), *ew* (*sew* — [səʊ]), *hau* (*haute couture* — [əʊtkə'tuə], [əʊtkə'tjuə] or [əʊtku:'tjuə]), *ho* (*Rhode Island* — [rəʊd'aɪlənd]), *'ho* (*table d'hôte* — [ta:bl'dəʊt] or [ta:bəl'dəʊt]), *oa* (*float* — [fləʊt]), *oe* (*foe* — [fəʊ]), *ol* (*folk* — [fəʊk]), *oo* (*brooch* — [brəʊtʃ]), *ou* (*soul* — [səʊl]), *ough* (*dough* — [dəʊ]), *ow* (*mellow* — [ˈmeləʊ]), *owe* (*owe* — [əʊ]). The sound [əʊ] can be placed in the zero (*Oh* — [əʊ]), initial (*own* — [əʊn]), middle (*note* — [nəʊt]) and final (*polo* — [ˈpəʊləʊ]) position of words.

The vowel sound [aɪ] can be represented by the letters *i* (*grime* — [ɡraɪ]), *y* (*ply* — [plai]) and by combinations of letters *ei* (*skein* — [skai]), *eiġh* (*height* — [haɪ]), *ey* (*geyser* — [ˈɡaɪzə]), *eye* (*eye* — [aɪ]), *ie* (*tie* — [taɪ]), *ig* (*benign* — [bi'nai]), *igh* (*knight* — [naɪ]), *ui* (*disguise* — [dis'gaɪz]), *uy* (*buy* — [baɪ]), *ye* (*bye* — [baɪ]). The sound [aɪ] can be placed in the zero (*I* — [aɪ]), initial (*either* — [ˈaɪðə]), middle (*neither* — [ˈnaɪðə]) and final (*verify* — [ˈverɪfaɪ]) position of words.

The vowel sound [ʊə] can be represented by the letter *u* (*rural* — [ˈrʊəl] or [ˈrʊərəl]) and by combinations of letters *ewer* (*skewer* — [ˈskjuə]), *oor* (*moor* — [mʊə] or [mo:]), *our* (*dour* — [dʊə]), *ua* (*septuagenarian* — [septʃʊədʒi'neəriən]), *uar* (*Stuart* — [ˈstjuət]), *ue* (*fuel* — [fjuəl]), *ueur* (*liqueur* — [li'kjuə]), *uou* (*sumptuous* — [ˈsʌmptʃʊəs] or [ˈsʌmptʃʊəs]), *ure* (*obscure* — [ɒbs'kjuə]). The sound [ʊə] can be placed in the middle (*gourmet* — [ˈɡʊəmeɪ]) and final (*poor* — [pʊə]) position of words.

The vowel sound [ɛə] can be represented by the letters *a* (*pharaoh* — [ˈfɛərəʊ]), *e* (*wisteria* — [wis'tɛəriə]) and by combinations of letters *ae* (*aerodynamics* — [ɛərədaɪ'næmiks]), *ai* (*dairy* — [ˈdeəri]), *air* (*fair* — [fɛə]), *aire* (*questionnaire* — [kwɛstʃənɛə]), *are* (*welfare* — [ˈwɛlfɛə]), *ayor* (*mayor* — [meə]),

ear (forebear — [ˈfo: beə]), eir (their — [ðeə]), er (conciierge — [kɒnsiˈeəʒ]), ere (therefore — [ˈðeəfo:]). The sound [eə] can be placed in the zero (air — [eə]), initial (area — [ˈeəriə]), middle (whereas — [weəˈræz]) and final (where — [weə]) position of words.

The vowel sound [eɪ] can be represented by the vowel letters *a* (slate — [sleɪt]) and *e* (elite — [eɪˈli: t]), by the consonant letters *h* (PhD — [pi: eɪtʰdi:]), *j* (J.F Kennedy — [dʒeɪfˈkenedi]) and *k* (KGB — [keɪdʒi:ˈbi:]), by the French letter *é* (protégé — [ˈprɒtʒeɪ]) and by combinations of letters *ae* (Gaelic — [ˈgeɪlk]), *ag* (champagne — [ʃæmˈpeɪn]), *ai* (maim — [meɪm]), *aig* (campaign — [kæmˈpeɪn]), *aigh* (straight — [streɪt]), *ay* (relay — [ri:ˈleɪ]), *ea* (steak — [steɪk]), *ee* or *ée* (matinee — [ˈmætiːneɪ]), *entrée* — [ˈɒntreɪ] or [ˈa: ntreɪ]), *ei* (abseil — [ˈæbseɪl]), *eig* (reign — [reɪn]), *eight* (freight — [freɪt]), *er* (foyer — [ˈfɔɪeɪ]), *et* (gourmet — [ˈgəʊmeɪ]), *ey* (fey — [feɪ]), *oa* (gaol — [dʒeɪl]), *uet* (bouquet — [buˈkeɪ]). The sound [eɪ] can be placed in the zero (Eh — [eɪ]), initial (eight — [eɪt]), middle (tame — [teɪm]) and final (bay — [beɪ]) position of words.

The research allowed us to work out and prepare for publishing a guide-book of drills containing lists of words formed by means of ABC letters and their combinations used to denote the English sounds. The results of the scientific analysis persuade us that the presented material can be effective in the educational process rendered by teachers at educational institutions, organizations carrying out education and by individual entrepreneurs when explaining the articulation of English phonemes via graphic spelling of letters and their combinations to students. Demonstrating the data of the study to learners can facilitate their understanding the problem of English alphabet letter combinations representing the sounds used in the formation of lexical units [1] while practicing the pronunciation [19]. We assume that the ways of graphic spelling of the phonemes presented by us are not exhaustive because it is impossible to cover the whole spectrum of English language due to its constant development.

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ABOUT THE RUSSIANNES OF RUSSIAN MUSIC

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the phenomenon of Russianness of Russian music. It is noted that in order to talk about the Russianness of Russian music, it is necessary to first determine what Russianness is. It is emphasized that this can only be done by a person who is a native speaker of Russianness and who on this basis can be called a Russian person. It is indicated that the Russian person is Orthodox and for him Russianness is the Radiance of the Power and Glory of God.*

According to the understanding of the Russian person of Russianness is explained that the Russianness of Russian music is predetermined by the action of ancient Russian Orthodox singing — znamennoe penie, which shone with the Light of Russian music. Three bright flashes (glows) of this radiance are indicated, which have consistently appeared in three types of Russian music: secular, ecclesiastical and secular-ecclesiastical.

In conclusion, the role of bell ringing in Russian music is emphasized. It is claimed that the bell sound used in Russian music is the most vivid illumination of znamennoe penie, which means it is the most powerful expression of the Russianness of Russian music.

Keywords: *Russianness, Russian person, Russian music, znamennoe penie, bell ringing, God, Orthodoxy.*

Today, the conversation about Russianness, including the Russianness of Russian music, is extremely relevant. Unfortunately, Russianness irritates many people these days (why? — this is a separate topic, which, of course, is not currently possible to discuss). Let's ask the question: *what is Russianness?*

At first glance, it seems that the answer to this question lies on the surface: Russianness is a certain property, quality of nationality: by nationality, Russian is a native speaker of Russianness. But it's not that simple. A huge number of Russians by nationality, especially nowadays, are not native speakers of Russianness,

and, conversely, some non-Russians by nationality: French, Germans, Brazilians are native speakers of Russianness. *So, what is Russianness?*

It seems that the answer to this question can be given precisely by someone *who is a native speaker of Russianness*, and who on this basis can rightfully be called a *Russian — Russian person* (we introduce a new category: “Russian person”, that is, we give the Russian person an ontological status). *Who is a Russian person and how does he understand Russianness?*

The features of the Russian man were clearly marked by the saints of Russia: Sergius of Radonezh, Nil Sorsky, Maxim the Greek (by the way, Maxim the Greek is a Greek by nationality). They were formulated especially vividly and concisely by St. Nil Sorsky in his “Rule of Skete Life”. Here they are:

- escape from the outside to the inside;
- non-possessiveness;
- purity of thought;
- love for one’s neighbor;
- the thirst for meeting God (the idea of salvation) [13].

Obviously, the Russian person — a religious person is *Homo religious*, and since he is a Russian person, it means that his homeland, in a literal, physical, or spiritual sense, is Russia, in which the dominant religion is Orthodoxy, he is *an Orthodox person*.

The fact that a Russian person is Orthodox, many prominent Russians, writers, and scientists claimed to be Russian. For example, F. M. Dostoevsky emphasized: “The Russian people are all about Orthodoxy and its idea. That’s all he has in him, and he doesn’t need to, because Orthodoxy is everything... Those who do not understand Orthodoxy will never understand anything among the people. Moreover, he cannot love the Russian people, but will love them only the way he would like to see them” [5, p. 64]. And once he even identified: “What is Orthodox is Russian” [4, p. 173].

Thus, for a Russian person, Russianness is connected with Orthodoxy. *But what is Orthodoxy for a Russian person?* (this is a very serious question, because Orthodoxy is practiced not only by Russians, but also by other peoples: Serbs, Greeks, Romanians, Ethiopians, not to mention Georgians, Moldovans, Belarussians and Ukrainians).

So, the question is, what is Orthodoxy for a Russian person? — extremely important (and, I must say, extremely difficult. It is no coincidence that even religious scholars have different answers to it). Let’s try to offer our own answer. In our country, it develops according to the principle of the *crescendo* used in music:

We believe that *Orthodoxy for the Russian people is the Power of God* (the Christian God, in the unity of His three Hypostases: God the Father, God the Son and God the Holy Spirit), which surpasses the power of the earth (nature), which, in particular, is expressed in the ability of God to cast death (“... death corrects

death”). And since in the minds of the ancient Russian people the impulses of the earth were connected with the behavior of pagan gods — Perun, Veles and others, it is not surprising that Prince Vladimir, who led Russia to Orthodoxy, expressed the superiority of the Power of God over the power of the earth by erecting a temple on the hill where the altar of Perun was previously located in honor of his heavenly patron saint St. Basil the Great.

For a Russian, the Power of God is also the Glory of God. It is significant that in the prayer “Our Father” — the main prayer not only of Christians, but also of Jews (among Jews it is called *Avinu Malkenu*), and Muslims (Muslims call it *Al-Fatiha*), it is in its Orthodox version that the prayer ends with the words:

[For] Thine is the kingdom, and the power,
and the glory forever and ever. Amen.

(These final words of prayer are certainly Praise and Doxology to the Creator!)

Finally, *for a Russian person believe that God’s Power and Glory are contained in the Light of God* (the Uncreated Tabor Light that appeared to the apostles on Mount Tabor), which God graciously poured out on the Russian land, so that the Russian land would preserve and establish His Power and Glory in the world and shine with His Light.

And so, having clarified the Russian person’s understanding of Orthodoxy, perhaps it is already possible to say what Russianness is for a Russian person. *For a Russian person, Russianness is the Radiance of the Power and Glory of God.*

Having defined Russianness (for a Russian person), let’s try to find out how it declares herself in Russian music.

Since Russianness is connected with Orthodoxy (it grows and is established in the bosom of Orthodoxy), it is obvious that when talking about Russianness of Russian music, we should be talking about *Orthodox music*. In other words, first of all, about *znamennoe penie*, i. e. *prayer singing in an Orthodox church*. (The *znamennoe penie* is based on a Russian folk lyrical song. In fact, *znamennoe penie* is a Russian folk lyrical song that has adopted Christianity, Orthodoxy). The question immediately arises: *is the znamennoe penie music, or is it a prayer expressed in a special way?*

There are two points of view on this issue. According to the first one, which belongs mainly to the clergy, but also to some researchers of Liturgical activities, *znamennoe penie* singing is a kind of prayer. This point of view was most clearly expressed by V. I. Martynov. According to the scientist, the material that makes up the content of *znamennoe penie* singing is a Word, and when singing it, a certain toneme is used, “which does not mean any particular sound, but a transition from one high-pitched level to another or a constant stay at the same level” [12, p. 109].

According to the second point of view, championed by composers, regents, and singers of church choirs, as well as some theologians, *znamennoe penie*

singing is a type of church music. For example, according to the famous theologian V. N. Lossky. As Lossky notes (by the way, in the work, the text of which is given as an appendix in one of Martynov's books!), in *znamennoe penie* singing, with all the meaning of the word, music plays a determining role. "The Gospel message,— Lossky points out,—is... a word (which.— *A.K.*) ... can only be a 'reference' to a more substantial word — ... the Embodied Word. The 'liturgical' word is a sermon... that ... does not tolerate 'vain words' that have not been purified by fire seven times. Music is designed to serve precisely this purified word, connecting with the Word of God..." [11, p. 237]. (The author of these lines supports the second point of view.)

The *znamennoe penie* at the moment of the performance of the "*Cherubic song*" — "*Cherubimskaya*" during the Divine Liturgy has a particularly deep, sacred content. At this moment, those singing in the temple are likened to angels singing in heaven (therefore, singing in the temple is called *angelic*). At the same time, the angels singing in the sky glow and become more and more enlightened, approaching the Source of Light — God! As St. Gregory Palamas writes: "(Angels.— *A.K.*) are light, and are always filled with light, and they themselves become more and more luminous ... rejoicing in joy near the First Light ..." [6, p. 224]. This means that those who sing like angels in the temple are also becoming more and more luminous, radiant...

Znamennoe penie existed in Orthodox Worship until the middle of the 17th century, after which it was replaced by *partes*. But what is amazing is that the *znamennoe penie* has not gone away, has not faded away. Like the once legendary city of Kitezh, which plunged into Lake Svetloyar, it plunged into the depths of history in order to radiantly shine with the Light of Russian music from there, from the depths of time!

Russian music had three bright flashes (glows), which consistently manifested themselves in three types of Russian music: *secular*, *ecclesiastical*, and *secular-ecclesiastical* (secular-ecclesiastical music is actually the "third layer" of Russian music, using the term "third layer" proposed by V. J. Konen to characterize a completely different music).

The first outbreak, curiously enough, which arose precisely in secular (!) music, was Glinka's opera "*A Life for the Tsar*" ("*Ivan Susanin*") (1836). How?

The fact is that Glinka's work on the opera was preceded by his work on the "*Cherubimskaya*" (which he created, focusing on the traditions of Russian church singing).

Glinka began working on "*Cherubimskaya*" in 1828, but did not finish, did not write the final part — "*Like the Tsar*", depicting the expectation and finding of the Heavenly King, but began to create the opera "*Life for the Tsar*", in the finale of which — "*Glory*", in fact, realized the idea of "*Like the Tsar*" (the coincidence of both melodic material and key is in C major). According to Natalia Beketova,

“‘Glory’ was originally an internal plot of the opera, ‘programmed’ by another ‘Like a King’” [2, pp. 59–60]. (Glinka’s “Cherubimskaya” was first performed in its entirety by the Court Singing Chapel in 1837, that is, a year after the premiere of “Life for the Tsar”.)

The second outbreak that appeared in church music was P. I. Tchaikovsky’s composition “*The Liturgy of St. John Chrysostom*” (1878). As Tchaikovsky noted, when creating this work, he dreamed of reviving the “primordial church-Russian singing” in the Russian Orthodox Church [17, p. 272].

Tchaikovsky uses elements of antiphonal sounding of various choral compositions in the “Liturgy”, striving to compose in the tradition and spirit of Liturgical singing based on antiphonal (angelic) singing.

The “Cherubimskaya” (No 6) is particularly expressive in the “Liturgy”, in which he follows Glinka’s “Cherubimskaya”. (Only if Glinka’s “Cherubimskaya” is in C major, and Tchaikovsky’s “Cherubimskaya” is in e minor — H major.) The finale of Tchaikovsky’s “Cherubimskaya”, “Hallelujah”, is sonorous, bright, and brilliant, with the composer many times exceeding the permissible number of “Hallelujahs”. In the everyday “Cherubimskaya” there are usually only three “Hallelujahs”, he has 11! According to Evgeny Tugarinov’s exact thought, “Tchaikovsky sings ‘Hallelujah’ 11 times, which expresses a certain symbolism of endless jubilation” [18].

The third outbreak, within secular church music, was G. V. Sviridov’s composition “*Chants and prayers*” (1980–1997). This work is performed on stage, but it has a deeply liturgical meaning (written in words from liturgical poetry). As Irina Brovina shrewdly noted, the structure of “Chants and prayers” “evokes associations with the variation and closeness of church services, where each chant represents an element in a higher-order structure” [3, p. 110].

In accordance with the tradition of antiphonal (angelic) singing, Sviridov uses a division into two choirs in some hymns. One part of the choir (the smaller one is probably the “parishioners”), the other (the larger one is probably the “angels”). And, of course, the Light. Due to the special fret organization of the chants, where the frets of the major and minor moods merge into one fret, an effect arises in them, called by Yuri Paisov the effect of the “mysterious glow of choral harmonies” [15, p. 185].

According to Sviridov, with the help of this effect, “a face of strong expressiveness is drawn or... The Divine face” [16, p. 207].

And last.

In Russian music, *bell ringing* has always been actively used, at all its historical stages. Without a doubt, *bell ringing is a characteristic feature of Russian music*. As V. V. Stasov exclaimed: “Once again, we have *bells*: the Russian school cannot live without them...” [14, p. 349]. And Boris Asafiev complained that “until now,

relatively little attention has been paid to the presence of Russian composers in [music.— A.K.] ... bell ringing” [1, p. 13]. What is the reason for this?

The fact is that the bell ringing is the most striking manifestation of *znamennoe penie* in Russian music. And since that’s the case, it means that *the bell sound used in Russian music is the most powerful expression of the Russianness of Russian music* (1).

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(1) For more information about our understanding of the Russianness of Russian music, see: [7; 8; 9; 10].

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CATEGORIES AS AN INVARIANT BASIS OF THINKING

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Abstract. *The article argues that the content of universal categories of thinking is woven into the context of socio-cultural existence and is not the result of arbitrary theoretical synthesis. Universal categories arise and develop throughout the history of cognition as special abstractions that fix the universal essential forms of being. From the epistemological point of view, the content of universal categories of thinking represent some kind of conceptual niches with infinite information capacity, which provide the possibility of cognition and definition of an infinite number of special cases through them.*

Keywords: *universal categories, invariant basis of thinking, unconventionality, ordinary and theoretical thinking, way of human existence, virtual communication, categorical level of thinking.*

Despite the fact that the analysis of the content of categories of thought has always been and always will be one of the main tasks of philosophical cognition, socio-cultural existence creates from time to time special concrete historical reasons for referring to the universal foundations of human life.

These reasons usually arise during periods of wars, revolutions, economic and political crises, when social transformations affect society as a whole and the lives of most people. It is during such periods that ideas about variability, fluidity and novelty as the main features of socio-cultural existence begin to dominate in the public consciousness, and sustainability, stability and universality are perceived as a “disappearing reality”, retention or return to which is impossible in human life.

Such a mindset visits humanity with such inescapable constancy that it should be perceived as self-refuting. However, it is not perceived as such. On the contrary, the very fact of the absolutization of the variability of the world is invariably accompanied by the oblivion of the inseparable connection between the universal definitions of being. This means that there is another cultural and historical reason to turn to analysis of the nature and functions of categories of thinking.

The existence of categories is determined not by the peculiarities of a particular subject of knowledge, but by the specifics of mental activity itself and, moreover, by the specifics of the human way of life, an integral feature of which thinking is. Universal categories arise and develop throughout the history of cognition as special abstractions that fix the universal essential definitions of being and become universal forms of thinking and theoretical comprehension of reality.

It can be said, that from an epistemological point of view, the content of universal categories of thinking represent some kind of conceptual niches with infinite information capacity, which provide the possibility of cognition and definition of an infinite number of special cases through them.

In a “pure”, consciously reflected form, categories exist only at the level of theoretical studies, their cognition and definition being a specific task of philosophy and theoretical sections of religion, art, morality (to the extent that these sections concern the question of categories expressing the ultimate goals and meanings of human existence). The categories of thinking are not created by philosophy. They are objects of philosophical analysis. It means, that categories are “philosophical” not because they belong to philosophy, but because philosophy makes them the object of special theoretical analysis.

It would be a mistake to believe, as R. Rorty does, that in everyday and theoretical consciousness there are different concepts of truth, good, beauty, etc. [4, pp.226–228]. The fact that ordinary consciousness does not reflect on the content of categories does not mean that it does not operate with these categorical forms. If, for example, the causal relationship between a person’s action and the result to which it leads had not been fixed in any way in the ordinary consciousness of a person, then this activity itself would hardly have been possible. The absence of a category of causality would mean that a person cannot establish in his thinking a causal form of connection between various phenomena. But the ability to think causally may not have a word expressing the general concept of causality.

Back in the early 20th century, exploring the content of the concept “good”, J. Moore came to the conclusion that the concept “good” belongs to those “innumerable objects of thought which themselves cannot be defined, because they are indecomposable extreme terms, the reference to which underlies every definition” [3, p.67]. However, what was heuristically significant in Moore’s ideas was not so much the thesis of the “indefinability” of the concept “good” itself, as the line of thought within which this thesis was formulated and which pointed to the involuntariness, unconventionality, predestination of the content of this term to any reasoning and definitions.

Moving in this direction, we are still opening the way to understanding the specifics of defining universal categories of thinking, the content of which is woven into the context of human existence and is not the result of arbitrary theoretical synthesis.

The peculiarity of the concept “good”, which Moore considered to be a fundamental “indefinability”, would be more accurate to call the fundamental unconventionality and intuitive clarity of the meaning assigned to all universal categories in natural languages. This feature of universal categories of thinking is due to the fact that their content is formed in the process of the historical development of human life and expresses the unity of the fundamental foundations of the socio-cultural way of mastering the world [1].

If scientific concepts are formed only at the level of theoretical consciousness and the terms denoting them are introduced into scientific theories by special definitions, then the situation with universal categories of thinking is fundamentally different. Categories belong to the human thinking, since, unlike scientific concepts, they are actually present in the everyday consciousness of any person.

The fundamental difference between natural language words denoting universal categories of thinking and all other words and terms is that the meanings of these words are determined by the very way of human existence, invariant with respect to any cultural and historical differences and types of activities. That is why we cannot bring into consciousness any other meanings of these terms. In other words, we cannot take the position of a meta-observer in relation to our own intelligence and the ways it “enters” the world.

The invariance of the meanings of terms denoting in various natural languages the categories of “cause”, “effect”, “necessity”, “chance”, “good”, “beauty”, “truth”, etc., is provided not by an agreement or contract between people, but by the universal laws of human existence, in the process of which the categorical structure of thinking is formed. Since categories are generated in the process of human existence, and are not the result of convention, they cannot become the object of arbitrary theoretical manipulation. This means that theoretical definitions of universal categories can be only analytical, i. e. those that explicate in their formulations the meanings of these terms that exist in natural languages.

Speaking of various “concepts” of necessity, chance, truth, good, beauty, etc., we mean actually different criteria by which we can verify individual statements as true, things as beautiful, and deeds as good. But even if someone considers as necessary what others consider as accidental, and calls true, kind, and beautiful what others consider to be the embodiment of evil, ugliness, and lies, the logical bases of evaluation will be the same: necessity, chance, truth, good, beauty, etc.— for

it is in these categories the universal characteristics of being and the fundamental goals of human culture are expressed.

All categories, including those that reflect the ultimate goals and meanings of human life — “truth”, “good” and “beauty”, are defined only as forms of mental activity. However, these forms do not determine the ways of their application or actual implementation, which creates the very possibility of

discrepancies in assessments based on categorical (including –value-based) grounds and practically an infinite variety of concrete historical interpretations as of the content of universal categories, as of the forms of embodiment of the fundamental values of culture [2].

If this ontological uncertainty were absent, and the essence of categories would not only be seen in contemplation as self-evident, but as self-evident would be embodied in the phenomena of reality and practical human activity, then the process of cognition, differences in assessments and the diversity of cultural and historical forms of application of categories and the embodiment of values simply could not exist. All categories would have a self-evident application, and values would find a self-evident embodiment once and for all.

Meanwhile, thinking operates with categories as mental forms commensurate only with the infinite variety of Being. It is the infinite information capacity, excessive in relation to each specific life situation, act or product of human activity, that turns categories into an invariant basis of thinking as such, incommensurable with momentary human actions in terms of stability and universality.

The a priori nature of the categories of thinking means that the content of the categories of thinking is not depends on the transitory nature of the cognizable reality and the cognitive process itself, since they contain knowledge of the universal definitions of any object that precedes its practical or scientific, experimental cognition. Whatever the degree of variability, fluidity of all things, categorical forms of thinking retain stability and certainty precisely because they are forms of organization of the sensually perceived in the consciousness of the cognizing subject. That is why no research can be considered as scientific and cannot lead to the acquisition of knowledge if the subject of knowledge does not distinguish between the phenomenon and essence, cause and effect, necessity and chance, possibility and reality, content and form, quality and quantity, etc.

In the era of information technology development, it is especially important to understand that

information noise is still far from knowledge, and in knowledge itself it is necessary to distinguish essential and non-essential. The illusion of continuous updating of the system of scientific knowledge and socio-cultural existence as a whole arises only when the subject of cognition has no knowledge of the laws of development of either being or thinking, and when categorical structure of thinking is deformed.

This happens because information consumption, which is not included in the process of people's daily objective and practical activities for the development of the natural and socio-cultural environment, cannot become the basis for the formation of a categorical structure of thinking. Virtual communication and countless symbolic cultural products that mediate a person's connection with natural and socio-cultural realities that are not imaginary, but valid means of satisfying one's material and

spiritual needs, become dangerous obstacles to the formation of a basic, categorical level of thinking of the younger generation.

Meanwhile, understanding the nature and functions of categories of thinking makes it possible

not only to operate successfully in the real world, but also to create a theoretical and methodological basis for a concrete scientific analysis of any object, based on the knowledge of the most essential and fundamental characteristics of all types of existence reflected in the content of categories.

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THE DEVELOPMENT OF A PERSON'S WORLDVIEW. THE ROLE OF A TUTOR IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Education humanization caused by changes in cultural and economic development of the whole society requires the change in paradigms. Such categories as education organizing strategy and direct educational process themselves give a new scale for researching pedagogical substance; new units that comprise the entirety of substance and conditions (external and internal) for personality development directly in the educational process are emerging. Tutoring is a historically formed special pedagogical standpoint that ensures students individual educational program development and provides the process of individual education in the institution of higher education.*

The adjective «humanitarian» today is perceived as «inherent to a person, to human nature». However, a person's relationship to being and to oneself is not firmly grounded at the essential level. The need to maintain comfortable conditions of existence prevents one from hearing the inner question: why? A definitive answer to this question cannot be obtained when attempting to clarify the problems of education in society at the present stage. For different social groups, it contains various competing meanings. Processes of humanization are desirable in every segment of society, but their effectiveness and levels of achievement inevitably vary both in qualitative assessments and in the outcomes of changes. The humanization of education, driven by changes in the cultural and economic development of society as a whole, necessitates a shift in paradigms.

A scientist is not one who provides the correct answers, but one who poses the right questions (Claude Lévi-Strauss).

A person cannot conceive their destiny independently from the destiny of humanity, the unified whole in which they live and through which the full meaning of life is revealed.

At every stage of the development of human society, the reflections of philosopher-thinkers began with an analysis of what surrounds a person, what lies at the center of their contemplation and thought, what forms the foundation of the universe, the Cosmos, and what the phenomena unfolding in their infinite diversity represent. Human beings have always possessed curiosity. The desire to understand the essence of the mysterious and unknown reflects a propensity for philosophical reflection. It is precisely philosophy that provides a systematic knowledge of the world as a whole.

Today, life urgently requires individuals to think and act independently and boldly in unfamiliar circumstances. Only such a radical turn can enable a person to return to truly valuable philosophical ideas and the noble paths to their realization.

In the educational process, the learner sets objectives, masters methods and educational content, and evaluates the results obtained. At each of these stages, problems may arise that are difficult to resolve without external assistance.

Common problems in the educational process:

- difficulties in the learning process (unclear content, unclear methods, etc.);
- interpersonal problems (for example, an unfavorable climate develops within the group, a particular member ‘pulls the blanket over themselves,’ or is excessively aggressive, passive, etc.);
- with self-esteem issues;
- with difficulties in applying acquired knowledge in practical contexts, among others.

All these problems can impede the effective assimilation of educational content.

The design of innovative learning based on the collaborative creative activity of the teacher and students underlines the necessity of mutually conditioned integration in the development of both the teacher’s and students’ personalities. Innovative education can help the teacher move beyond the subject-object ‘broadcasting’ approach to the learner. The central issue of the innovative approach in education is the teacher’s own readiness to accept and implement directions for collaborative creative activity with students.

In theory, two primary paths are identified in the innovative approach to education: the development and implementation of system-oriented and individually oriented programs.

What are system-oriented programs? In our case, these are programs aimed at the entire group as a whole, intended to prevent the emergence of problems or to solve those problems that are widespread.

The individually oriented actions of a teacher (tutor) are aimed at assisting any listener in resolving the problems they have encountered.

Philosophy, as the self-consciousness of society, has always paid special attention to contemporary reflection on significant societal changes: illuminating fading forms of life and fostering public consciousness of the necessity for change.

Never before has philosophy played as important a role in the life of society as it does in the modern era. Humanity's transition to a qualitatively new state necessitates a reevaluation of the existential foundations of human existence and the establishment of a new system of value orientations.

The phenomenon of tutoring as an innovation in the field of education originated in European universities of the 14th century: for instance, at Oxford and Cambridge, the tutor was perceived as a mentor. This era was marked by significant liberalism in education: students were, in essence, not assigned to a specific university, could 'move' from one course to another, and attended only those courses they personally preferred. The university limited students only by the requirements imposed on examinations, while the methods and means by which excellent knowledge of the subject would be achieved were left to the discretion of the student and their tutor. Tutoring initially served the functions of supporting the process of self-education.

The practical implementation of this type of education lies in locality — a certain concentration of efforts by its advocates and facilitators based on a transformed type of individual consciousness.

Such categories as the strategy for organizing the educational process and the educational and upbringing process itself establish a new scale for studying pedagogical reality; new units of analysis appear that embrace the entirety of reality and the conditions (both external and internal) of an individual's development throughout the learning process. The state of our society has long necessitated the implementation of a parallel educational paradigm based on dialogue, that is, the equality of partners.

Moving from theory to the practice of tutoring, the tutor is required to:

- create conditions for the group to work within the framework of this program (ensure that a group of 10–20 people has all the necessary resources);
- attend to the emotional climate and working atmosphere within the group;
- organize the work of the group and each individual learner with the study materials; to conduct group discussions on thematic assignments;
- to provide consultations to students during the completion of practical tasks and project development;
- to organize the process of evaluation and self-evaluation for each educational element individually;
- to offer individual assistance and support to students, both academically and psychologically.

Teaching the fundamentals of scientific knowledge should not be limited to merely conveying to learners the 'positive' sum of this knowledge, but should instead 'encourage' the student's capacity to develop an active personal position in engaging with and understanding knowledge.

The formation of a free and responsible individual should be placed at the center of the entire education system, with the system itself comprising numerous elements interconnected and interrelated.

One of the contemporary trends in global development, which underscores a fundamental aspect of preparing individuals for life in new conditions, is the dynamic growth of the economy, increasing competition, profound structural changes in the employment sector that necessitate continuous professional education, flexibility, and mobility, alongside a reduction in unskilled and low-skilled labor.

Today, life urgently requires individuals to think and act independently and boldly in unfamiliar circumstances. Only such a radical turn can enable a person to return to truly valuable philosophical ideas and the noble paths to their realization.

Philosophy, as the self-consciousness of society, has always paid special attention to contemporary reflection on significant societal changes: illuminating fading forms of life and fostering public consciousness of the necessity for change.

A human belongs to two worlds: the natural, corporeal world as its organic part, and simultaneously the psychic world — the world of consciousness, creativity, and freedom. These two worlds exist in different modes. The physical, material, natural world exists objectively, independently of human will and consciousness.

The human being embodies the dialectical unity of the objective-material and the subjective, of body and spirit.

Reliance on human talent and initiative is the most crucial resource for the economy and social development.

The effectiveness of integrating scientific research with the educational process is precisely what defines competitiveness.

The positive dynamics of the continuous renewal of information technologies and systems necessitate their active implementation not only within the educational environment but also across all spheres of social life.

In contemporary society, various types of consciousness evolve; these processes are conditioned by the fundamental orientations of a person's spiritual state. The inner world of the individual and their self-consciousness have long attracted the attention of scholars. This array of problems in education, arising from the recognition and acceptance of the life goal and the educational goal as equally important tasks, shifts the perspective of the 'scientific' understanding of 'education,' which inevitably leads to a global transformation in the fields of education and upbringing.

No matter how brilliant a pedagogical invention may be, it will, unfortunately, inevitably be deformed and distorted by practices grounded in the old system of beliefs.

The process of developing fundamentally new (innovative) pedagogical forms, lacking fundamental philosophical foundations, cannot be successful (cultural values, foundational worldview attitudes that meet the requirements objectively imposed on the individual in the context of modern society).

As contemporary university pedagogy places increasing emphasis on innovative learning, and during pedagogical practice students typically study both widespread and advanced pedagogical experiences, there arises a need for new approaches to the development of cycles of traditional and new pedagogical disciplines.

The primary element of the new approach is the adaptation of the student to innovative technologies. It is precisely the teacher-consultant (tutor) who creates an educational environment that enables the student not only to acquire knowledge and skills but also to solve real problems in their practical activities.

Scientific methods are actively applied in the educational process to enhance learning effectiveness. Research in cognitive psychology demonstrates that employing active learning methods, such as discussions and project work, can increase material retention by 25% compared to traditional lectures. This underscores the importance of implementing scientifically grounded methods that foster the development of analytical thinking and independent learning skills.

We can regard thinking as a source of infinite developmental resources; it is not merely a capacity of the human brain but, as L. S. Vygotsky asserts, possesses a suprasubjective substantial nature. Thinking itself provides the subject with the essential energy required for development.

Individual thinking, through the subjectivation of the substance of thinking, becomes one of the ways of self-development.

The knowledge that currently anchors the education system remains the central focus of pedagogical efforts aimed at developing the individual through thinking.

Thinking — the foundation of our life — is a direct reflection of societal conditions, and if we do not attend to it today, tomorrow will be too late.

The education system ‘is one of the key components of societal development.’ It influences personality formation, ensures the transmission of knowledge, and develops the skills and abilities of individuals” (Shipovskaya L. P.). In light of this, the application of scientific research in educational programs becomes especially crucial for creating a high-quality educational process.

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